

Division of Education
School of Education and Social Sciences

**How Algerian Teachers Engage with the Values Embedded across
the Second-Generation Curriculum**

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A thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of the
degree of Doctoral of Philosophy at the University of the West of Scotland

April 2024

Author's Declaration

This is to certify that to the best of my knowledge, the content of this thesis is my own original work, but for quotations and citations which have been acknowledged. This thesis has not been submitted for any other degree at the University of the West of Scotland or any other university.

Signed:

Date: 10/04/2024

Personal details withheld.

Dedication

I dedicate this work to:

The soul of my beloved mother Cherifa Abid, may she rest in peace and to the most precious person in my life, my father Mahammad Abid

My beloved siblings: Zohor, Mustapha, Soumia, Nadir, Souhila.

My beloved nephews and nieces: Yasine, Ilyes, Djamel, Hafssa, Imad, Cherifa, Ouis, Ali, Yasser, Mohamed, Ahmed

My beloved relatives-in-law: Wassila, Farida, Mustapha, Abd Lghani, Mohamed

All my teachers who taught me from Primary school to university

All my dearly loved family and friends.

Acknowledgements

Warm thanks go to:

The Supervisory Team

Dr. Carole Bignell, Dr. Yonah Matemba, Prof. Donald Gillies, and the assessor Dr. Andrew Killen for their constant support and endless patience, and constructive and valuable feedback.

UWS Student Support Services

I am grateful to UWS and PGR services in particular for offering a wide range of interdisciplinary events that contributed to our academic growth efforts to ensure doctoral students' progress and success.

The Sponsor

My deepest gratitude to the sponsor (Algerian government) for fully funding the course and for the opportunity itself.

Colleagues and Fellows in UWS

Special thanks also go to colleagues and fellows in UWS for their help, assistance, and encouragement.

Abstract

The study explored the perspectives of Algerian English as a Foreign Language (EFL) Middle School teachers on their perspectives regarding the implementation of values permeating the Second-Generation curriculum. In Algeria, this is an issue which far has received little attention in the discourse. The Second-Generation curriculum reform has infused values across the national curriculum with the aim of fostering cultural and national ideals and encouraging learning tolerance toward foreign languages and cultures. Focusing on the perspectives of EFL middle school teachers, the study captured how these teachers reflected on their understanding of the national values embedded in the Second-Generation curriculum, how they deliver these values in their teaching and challenges they face when delivering these values in their teaching. This was a qualitative study that adopted mixed method research design. Data was collected from semi-structured interviews with middle schools EFL teachers (n16), and an online survey completed by 64 teachers. The data gathered from the online survey was analysed descriptively. Thematic analysis, using NVIVO12 software were employed for the data gathered through semi-structured interviews. The findings indicated that while Algerian EFL middle school teachers had good understanding of the rationale for the values embedded in the Second-Generation curriculum, they were concerned about the introduction of these in the early years of middle school. The findings suggested also that teachers teach these values implicitly, as it is recommended by the stakeholders (educators and policymakers), using different methods for instance, role modelling, storytelling, and vivid examples. Some teachers agreed that this policy of promoting values education was not effectively applied as it was neither examined nor implemented effectively. Thus, this resulted in many limitations. There were also number of challenges that the teachers face during the enactment of the core values, among these challenges is the lack of effective training and lack of teachers' agency in policy making and curriculum reform. The limitations and challenges resulted in reform failure and teachers resisting the new reform.

Keywords: values education, character education, embedding values, EFL teachers, English language Curriculum, Second Generation curriculum, policymaking.

Table of Content

General Introduction	1
1.1 <i>Significance of the Study</i>	1
1.2 <i>Contribution of the Study</i>	2
1.3 <i>Problem Statement</i>	3
1.4 <i>Research Aims</i>	7
1.5 <i>Research Questions</i>	7
1.6 <i>Thesis structure</i>	8
Background and Context	10
2.1 <i>Introduction</i>	10
2.2 <i>The language context in Algeria</i>	10
2.3 <i>The Educational Schooling System in Algeria</i>	12
2.4 <i>The Context of Curriculum Reform in Algeria</i>	13
2.4.1 The Main Educational Reforms:	14
2.5 <i>The Second Generation Curriculum:</i>	16
2.6 <i>Conclusion:</i>	28
Literature Review	30
3.1 <i>Introduction</i>	30
3.2 <i>The Literature Review Process</i>	
3.3 <i>Definition of Values</i>	30
3.4 <i>The Implementation of Values in the Curriculum</i>	38
3.4.1 Methods of Implementing Values within the curriculum	43
3.5 <i>The Importance of Including Values in School Curriculum</i>	44
3.6 <i>Teachers Perspectives about Values</i>	46
3.7 <i>Issues Effecting Values Implementation</i>	47
3.8 <i>Teachers Resistance</i>	49
3.9 <i>Conclusion</i>	51
Research Methodology	52
<i>Introduction</i>	52
4.2 <i>Philosophical Underpinnings: Social Constructivism/Interpretivism</i>	53
4.3 <i>Strategy of Inquiry</i>	54
4.3.1 Qualiative Approach	
4.3.2 Sequential Explanatory Mixed-method design	

4.3.3	<i>Data Collection Process and Tools</i>	63
4.3.3.3	<i>Online Survey</i>	66
4.3.3.4	<i>Semi-structured interviews</i>	68
4.3.3.5	<i>Mediated Interviews</i>	69
4.3.4	<i>Data Analysis Process and Techniques</i>	70
4.3.4.1	<i>Thematic Analysis and NVIVO</i>	70
4.4	<i>Researcher Positionality and Reflexivity</i>	71
4.5	<i>Ethical Considerations</i>	72
4.6	<i>Informed Consent/ participants' information sheet</i>	73
4.7	<i>Confidentiality</i>	74
4.8	<i>Quality and Validity in Qualitative research/ Semi-structured Interviews</i>	75
	<i>Conclusion</i>	78
	PERCEIVING THE CORE VALUES.....	79
5.1	<i>Introduction</i>	79
5.2	<i>The core values do not foreground the Second Generation curriculum reform</i>	79
5.3	<i>Understanding the meaning of the core values</i>	83
5.4	<i>The Rational of embedding the core values in the Middle School curriculum..</i>	86
5.5	<i>The aim of embedding the core values in the Middle School curriculum.....</i>	90
5.6	<i>Prioritizing and valuing the core values</i>	92
5.7	<i>Some core values contradict with the students' culture</i>	95
5.8	<i>Conclusion</i>	
	ENACTING THE CORE VALUES.....	97
6.1	<i>Introduction</i>	97
6.2	<i>The Representation of the core values in the policy documents</i>	97
6.3	<i>Algerian EFL Middle School Teachers Perform Values through Being Role Model</i>	99
6.4	<i>Algerian EFL Middle School Teachers Enact Values through Authentic problem-solving situations</i>	100
6.5	<i>Algerian EFL Middle School Teachers enact values through Story telling</i>	102
6.6	<i>Algerian EFL Middle School Teachers enact values through Vivid examples/real life situation method.....</i>	102
6.7	<i>Values in Middle Schools Are Embedded in the Lessons of the English Language Curriculum</i>	102
6.8	<i>The role of the teacher in enacting values is more than a curriculum translator or knowledge provider.....</i>	103

6.9 Conclusion *Error! Bookmark not defined.*

CHALLENGES AND AFFORDANCES OF ENACTING CORE VALUES

7.1 Introduction 105

7.2 The Challenges 105

7.2.1 The SGC reform failure 105

7.3 Teachers' Training 106

7.4 Family interferes in the process of fostering values in the school 107

7.5 Teachers reflect on their own Values while engaging with the core values 108

7.6 Lack of teachers' agency and accountability 109

7.7 Teachers' resistance of the SGC Reform..... 110

7.8 Teachers lacks Interest in teaching values 111

7.9 Affordance/ Coping strategies 112

7.10 Social Media helps the teachers in their experience of teaching values 112

7.11 Teachers Collaboration helps in sharing knowledge on how to deal with values in the classroom. 113

7.12 Workshops, study days, seminars help teachers in developing ways on how to enact values 113

7.13 Language teacher Teaches Values in the First Place.....

7.14 Conclusion 115

Conclusion 115

8.1 Summary of the process..... 115

8.2 Summary of the findings and the implications..... 116

8.2.1 Algerian EFL Middle School teachers' perspectives of the core values..... 117

8.2.2 Algerian EFL Middle School teachers experience in enacting core values in the classroom 120

8.2.3 The Challenges and Affordances encountered by teachers while engaging with values 120

8.3 Limitations of the study 122

8.4 Recommendations..... 123

8.4.1 Recommendations for teachers..... 123

8.4.2 Recommendations for policymakers 124

8.4.3 Recommendations for further research 125

8.5 Personal Development..... 126

List of References.....

Appendices.....

List of Tables

Table 01: The structure of the Educational System in Algeria.

Table 02: Main Reforms Implemented in the Educational System in Algeria.

Table 03: Middle School English Language Curriculum in the Second-Generation Reform.

Table 04: The List of Core Values for the Curriculum of English.

Table 05: Demographic Data of the Participants of the Online Survey.

Table 06: Demographic Data of the Participants of the Semi-structured Interviews.

List of figures

Figure 01: Framework for Design adapted from Creswell (2018).

Figure02: Creswell (2003) Sequential Explanatory Mixed Method Design.

Figure 03: The rationale behind introducing these values is clear.

Figure 04: the aim of embedding the core values in curriculum is clear.

Figure 05: The policy document provides teachers with the way to teach these values.

Figure 06: There was an effective training for this reform.

Figure 07: I was involved in the decision-making of this reform.

List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

EFL: English as Foreign Language

SG: Second Generation

SGC: Second Generation Curriculum

CV: Core Values

Ts: Teachers

STs: Students

Cr: Curriculum

T: Teacher

PD: Policy Documents

SA: Strongly Agree

A: Agree

N: Neutral

D: Disagree

SD: Strongly Disagree

UNs: United Nations

USAID: US Agency for International Development

TVET: technical and vocational education and training

Chapter One

Introduction

1.1 Significance of the Study

Education has always been considered a complex process particularly in the modern society, where many contradictory factors, amplifies this complexity. Among these issues, there are tensions between the individual, social, national, universal, and spiritual factors (Kumar and Pandey, 2012). The moral and economic issues have significant influence on the ‘axiological springs’ of education (Etherington, 2013) which requires a serious and systematic reflection for the formative action, besides effectively exploring the philosophical perspective of values in education (Etherington, 2013). In other words, axiology is crucial in education as it provides an understanding of how values should shape educational goals and outcomes, as well as how educational systems can be designed to foster positive values and moral development in students. There is a shared belief that the aim of effective education is not only to develop and enhance pedagogical skills and abilities but also to promote values and good character. The notion of teaching values is not recent however, recently there has been a growing demand by not only governments but also educators and communities for the teaching of values in schools’ curriculum, which has led to the implementation of values education (Etherington, 2013). Teaching values in schools can establish the necessary principles to begin to address a country’s diverse values orientations. Furthermore, values education can contribute to the personal and professional development of individuals; therefore, such education may result in a positive social change. Thus, there have been many attempts from different countries in the world to construct and implement the values-based curriculum. Among these countries, Algeria introduced values to the Fundamental schooling level, primarily in Middle School in 2016 through a reform called Second Generation (MNE, 2016). Values education means to instil the essential values to the young generation to properly behave in a society (Aspin, 2007). In addition, it may set differently expectations in different countries based on their social, cultural, economic, socio-historical, and socio-political reasons (Sihe, 2019). Values that are typically integrated into the school curriculum can be delivered through a variety of mediums. They can be presented in the explicit and implicit curriculum (Sihe, 2019). However, there is still an ongoing debate on how to teach them at schools (Hartman, 2006). Some researchers

believe that values should be taught explicitly (Pass, 2007; Lloyd & Poel, 2008; Etherington, 2013), as young learners may not comprehend values when taught implicitly (Narvaez, 2001). Others affirm that values should be embedded in the curriculum so that students can acquire these values and reflect on them without direct instruction (Kohn, 1997; Paice, Heard and Moss, 2002; Muhamad, et al. 2013). In either way, every school should have its own set of values and culture (Deal and Peterson, 1999). The issue of values education has always raised important philosophical and pedagogical questions as to what values are, the nature of values, what values should be taught and how, therefore much research has been conducted in these areas. However, in the Algerian context, there is still little attention has been given to exploring teachers' experience in interacting and engaging with values in their daily practice in the classroom, there is insufficient knowledge of how teachers understand and interpret these values being embedded in the curriculum, what methods they employ to transfer them to the students as part of the curriculum. Furthermore, Sunley and Locke (2010) affirmed that there is still a lack of empirical studies on what values teachers share especially for middle school. This ongoing debate call for more research to be conducted in this area. Thus, the choice of this study foreground two main reasons the importance of the topic and a gap in the literature.

1.2 Contribution of the Study

This research study on the experience of Algerian EFL Middle School teachers' experience in engaging with the values embedded in the curriculum will have significant contribution at national and global level.

At a national context, this research is a pioneer study in the Algerian context an aspect of Algerian education that has not yet been researched. Most research conducted in the Algerian context has focused on teachers' comprehension, and implementation of a competency-based approach in the Second Generation curriculum and the students textbooks in the new reform, The competency-based approach and methods of teaching, project-based learning, teachers' beliefs, teachers' intercultural sensitivity, and multiple intelligences in textbooks, the English language teachers implementation of curriculum in Algerian Middle Schools (Mirza, 2017; Boukhentache, 2018; (Khalid and Ghania, 2019; Baghoussi and El Ouchdi, 2019; Selougi, 2020; Othmane and Bouyakoub, 2020; Boudouaia et al., 2022; Senani, 2022). However, there has been no attention devoted to exploring the values embedded in the curriculum neither to the teachers experience and engagement with these values in schools, despite this being considered the unique contribution of the Second-Generation reform.

Thus, the study can be compelling in the Algerian context as it can enhance people's awareness of the introduction of values in school curriculum.

This study can initiate a cooperation between EFL Middle School teachers and stakeholders through which stakeholders will be aware of teachers' understanding and perspectives toward the values embedded in the school curriculum.

Furthermore, this study will inform stakeholders on how teachers transfer the values to the students and will inform the stakeholders about the teachers challenges or otherwise the affordances they encounter during their interaction with values in the classroom. The study will also help policymakers to be aware of the limitations of the policy of introducing values into the curriculum and raise awareness of teachers' needs and feedback. Furthermore, will inform the policymakers of better ways to support teachers' practice. Thus, the study will enhance the teachers experience in interacting with values in the classroom and it will help in the quality of values implementation in curriculum, which would be reflected and influenced in better practices by teachers in promoting the essential values to the students.

The study will alert the government and policymakers about the reality of how core values embedded in the curriculum being implemented by EFL Middle School teachers in the teaching of English language curriculum.

This study can be a resource document to policymakers through which it can help in understanding the implication of the policy of introducing values into school curriculum and teachers experience in engaging with these values, thus this may lead them to reflect on how to replicate any limitations or difficulties which may help in enhancing its quality. In other words, the study will provide feedback for their policy.

Teachers, on the other hand will benefit from the results of the current study by gaining better knowledge on values implementation in school curriculum, this insight may lead to a reconsideration and re-conceptualisation of the necessary strategies for integrating embedded values in curriculum.

Inspectors and Middle School principals will find the results of this study useful by gaining better understanding of the teachers experience in engaging with values. Highlighting the intended limitations, and challenges or otherwise the affordances will lead the inspectors to reflect on their possible contribution to this process by improving their participation and involvement in improving teachers experience in engaging with embedded values.

At global context, this study will contribute to the existing body of knowledge of teachers experience in engaging with values embedded in school curriculum by situating the model of Algeria in a wider research context.

This study will contribute to the literature by presenting the experience of Algerian EFL Middle School teachers in engaging with values introduced to the curriculum and providing new results from a new context.

Therefore, the results of this study can be considered later by researchers in other contexts. as the study will help in understanding how teachers may perceive the values being embedded in the school curriculum. It will help in identifying what methods are employed by the teachers to transfer these values and how they interact with the values in their daily teaching practice. The study will also shed light on some problematic aspects concerning the intended challenges that teachers may face during their experience in interacting with values in classrooms and schools. In addition, the limitation that may result from introducing values in school curriculum, or otherwise the affordances or other supporting factors that might be highlighted by the teachers that help them or teachers benefit from them during this experience.

The key findings of the study include, first the Algerian EFL Middle School teachers perceive core values such as identity, national conscience, citizenship, and openness to the world as not being foregrounded in the Second-Generation curriculum reform. Teachers have varying understandings and attitudes towards the policy of embedding values in the curriculum, with some valuing the teaching of values in schools while others expressing concerns about teaching values at an early stage. Furthermore, teachers tend to teach these core values implicitly, as recommended by stakeholders, rather than through explicit instruction. Some of the methods used by teachers to implement the core values in the classroom include teachers being role model, authentic problem-solving situation, storytelling, and vivid examples.

The study identified potential challenges faced by teachers in enacting the core values, lack of effective training appears to be on the top list of their concerns. Teachers own values sometimes influence their way of enacting the core values and may intervene in the process. On the other hand, teachers reported no affordance of the policy of introducing the teaching of values through the SGC, however they highlighted some coping strategies that helped them in their experience of enacting core values, and which also minimize the effect of the challenges they faced. Among these coping strategies are, the different social media platforms which they use to share, discuss different concerns related to the teaching of values as well as exchanging

ideas, teaching methods, and recommendations. Teachers' collaboration and academic events also help teachers in the implementation of core values within school curriculum.

The study highlighted a number of limitations and shed light on areas that need further exploration and investigation, the way the core values tackled in policy documents, it needs to be thoroughly described and discussed, the documents should describe the role and task for the teachers to do clearly, designing effective training programme for teachers, considering teachers opinion and feedback on values education, evaluating the feedback or the outcome of introducing the teaching of core values within school curriculum. The current study tackled how values are taught in the classroom as reported by the teachers however there is no real sense of how the values are actually enacted in classrooms. Therefore, there should be further studies exploring this area.

The data also revealed that there is contradiction between teachers requesting more guidance in enacting values within the curriculum and between call for more independence and accountability. Therefore, there is also a need for more researches to tackle this concern in details.

These findings contribute to the existing literature on values education, teachers' perspectives on teaching values, and the challenges teachers may encounter in implementing values in the classroom, particularly in the Algerian context. Also, the results of the current study may benefit future researchers by providing an opportunity for further research needed in this area, implications, and international comparisons.

1.3 Statement of the Problem

Introducing values to curriculum is highly important and succeeded to grab the attention of many researchers. Algeria was among the countries that adopted values into the Middle School curriculum in the Academic year 2016-2017 through a reform called the Second Generation, which was first declared by the former Minister of Education Mrs. Noria Benghabrit (Elcherouk, 2016). The policy of embedding core values of identity, national conscience, citizenship, and openness to the world were introduced for the aim of instilling the Algerian culture, history, and country's heritage on students, also to value and share national cultural diversity with its regional cultural differences. The four main categories of values indicated above also have also sub-divisions such as, social, moral, professional and other types, these sub-values were preferred to promote some social values for instance, respecting

others, respecting neighbours, valuing family and social relationships, respecting animals' rights, valuing healthy food and supporting healthy lifestyle, valuing travel as source of knowledge, valuing education, encouraging creativity and scientific invention, sports and leisure activities and many others (Ministry of National Education, Teacher's guide 2017-2018). The Algerian government when adopting this policy of embedding values seems to have high hopes through the promises mentioned in the Official Bulletin. Therefore, the policymakers designed new curriculum content, set aims and objectives to be achieved, designed new students' textbooks, and defined the process of teaching in the policy documents, which are delivered the teachers to implement. However, this process seems to discard the key factor in the process- 'teachers' -and to neglect the critical role they play as there is no evidence provided as to how the new policy was introduced to the teachers, how teachers perceive the introduction of values, and how they might implement this policy in their everyday teaching.

Existing literature supports that the teacher has very critical role in enacting values and implementing them in schools. Therefore, research should focus on teachers' experience and perspectives on interacting with values in the classroom. In order for the process of instilling core values on students to be conducted successfully, teachers should have certain awareness about values education in the first place, how to successfully teach of these values in the classroom using different methods that might help, and how a teacher may avoid any unexpected issue that might appear during this process. In addition, they have to be effectively prepared and trained for the task. However, the teaching of values can be implemented in different ways and the existing body of knowledge did not arrive to one precise way to conduct values. Furthermore, the existing literature reported some issues that teachers may face while engaging with values, or factors and challenges that may hinder the process to be conducted successfully. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct much research on what are the possible challenges or factors to suggest possible solutions and recommendations. Often, educators and policymakers come to know about the implications of a policy, how beneficial it is, how effectively it has been implemented, and what are the outcomes; whether it has succeeded or failed, through the students' results. However, this would be more relevant to a pedagogical policy where the students' results would reflect their pedagogical skills and progress. A policy that focuses on promoting values to students to build their characters can only be evaluated and examined through exploring teachers' perspectives and experiences, or it could also be examined through investigating the learners' experience and perspectives. This research chose to study the teachers' experience and perspectives because teachers are key factor in the process

of embedding values in the school curriculum. Also, it may not always be possible to explore the students' experience if they are too young (early education) thus, they cannot reflect on their experience. Second, there is possibility that these values are transferred to students implicitly and the students themselves are not aware that they are required to acquire these values. Thus, the optimal way to get feedback about the policy of embedding values in the school curriculum is through exploring teachers' perspectives and experience. Based on this, there was a need for this research to be conducted to shed lights on how teachers perceive and understand the policy first, how they intend to implement it in the classroom, and to identify any possible challenges and limitations that might result from the teachers' practice of this policy.

1.4 Research Aim and Objectives

To address the above problem, this study aimed to explore the Algerian EFL Middle School teachers' perspectives and implementation of the core values underpinning the SGC reform. To support the aim the following are the objectives of the study.

-At theoretical level, exploring the teachers 'understanding and perspectives toward these core values.

-At practical level, investigating how teachers actually interact and enact these core values during their teaching in the classroom. In other words, the study aims to identify what methods, mediums techniques are employed by the teachers to address the values.

- To investigate the difficulties and challenges that EFL teachers encounter during their experience in engaging with the values that are embedded in the Middle School curriculum.

-To determine the major factors that hinder the EFL teachers from successfully engaging with the core values.

- To identify the affordances or supportive factors that help the EFL teachers during their experience of interacting with the core values in the classroom.

1.5 Research Questions

From the objectives, the following are the research questions guiding the study:

1. How do teachers perceive the core values underpinning the second-generation curriculum?

2. How do teachers enact the core values underpinning the second-generation curriculum?

3. What are the challenges or affordances, if any, the teachers encountered in engaging with the core values underpinning the second-generation curriculum?

1.6 Thesis structure

In addition to the abstract, introduction and conclusion, this thesis has six main chapters that are structured as follow:

Chapter two “the background and context”, includes background information about the language situation in Algeria, along with brief overview about the schooling system in Algeria focusing on the fundamental level. In addition to listing and discussing main reforms that have been implemented in fundamental school level, the chapter highlights the Second-Generation curriculum reform and the policy of embedding values which is the main focus of this research.

Chapter three “the literature review”, chapter defines key terms that informed this study, and critically considers relevant studies that have been conducted in the same area of the research of educational values, teaching and enacting values, and values pedagogy reviewed. The different results, hypothesis and theories resulted from previous studies are also presented; more precisely, this chapter presents how values are introduced in curriculum and how they are either taught or enacted, what methods are used in this process and how teachers engage with them. Furthermore, the chapter also discusses some potential issues that have been reported in the literature, which resulted from introducing or teaching the values as part of the school curriculum. Besides, the experience of values implementation and teaching was described in some countries such as South Africa, Kuwait, and Turkey that share some similarities with the Algerian context; geographical location (South Africa), similar ethnic group and religion (Kuwait), and similar religious orientation (Turkey).

Chapter four “The research methodology”, chapter outlines a detailed and comprehensive description of the empirical study, presenting the rationale for the choice of the research design, research method, the tools of data collection, the tools, and methods of data analysis. The chapter also discusses the research paradigm, research design, pilot study, research strategy, the analysis process. The last part of the chapter focuses on factors of validity, trustworthiness, and reliability of data, besides other ethical considerations of confidentiality and anonymity.

-The discussion of findings is divided into three chapters according to the three research questions, each question is discussed in separate chapter.

Chapter Five “perceiving the core values”, this chapter discusses the analysis of the data from both the online questionnaire-survey (64 participants) and the semi-structured interviews (16 participants) in regard to the first research question “How do teachers perceive the values underpinning the second-generation curriculum?” The presentation as well as the interpretation of the findings are considered. The data is presented and discussed thematically, following the order of the research questions, aim and objectives. Some of these themes are supported by numerical data from the questionnaire. Data presented in relation to the first research question informs discussion about teachers’ perspectives of national identity, conscience, citizenship and openness to the world values that are embedded in the Middle School’s Curriculum.

Chapter Six “enacting the core values”, this chapter discusses the data based on the second research question “how do teachers enact these values in their daily practices in the classroom?” The findings resulted from the analysis of the questionnaire survey presented in form of graphs. Following this, is a discussion of findings resulted from 16 semi-structured interviews. The aim of the second research question is to explore how teachers enact these values to the students in the classroom, what methods, techniques, or strategies they employ in their everyday teaching.

Chapter Seven “challenges and affordances of enacting values within school curriculum” this chapter presents the analysis of the data generated from both tools regarding the third research question, “what are the challenges or the affordances if any, do teachers encounter during engaging with the core values?” The aim of the third research question is to identify challenges and affordances if any, faced by the Algerian EFL Middle School teachers during their experience in engaging with the core values of national identity, conscience, citizenship, and openness to the world.

Chapter Two

Background and Context

2.1 Introduction

In this chapter, the background and context for this study are described. The chapter will explain the language situation in Algeria which will help to understand why the current study focuses on English language curriculum as well as answering why EFL teachers have been recruited in this study. This chapter outlines the schooling system in Algeria, as this will signify why particularly Middle School context has been chosen for this research. Furthermore, the chapter introduces the main reforms that have been implemented in schools related to the reform of the Second-Generation curriculum and the policy of values inclusion which is the main focus of this research. Thus, this discussion will help the reader to establish the context underlying the research, to recognize the rationale and key problem of the current study. In other words, this chapter is a foundation to the current study. However, this is just to give a sense why this research is needed, a detailed review of the literature will be discussed later.

2.2 The language context in Algeria

Although the focus of the current study is on the teachers' experience on engaging with the core values, this study will investigate these core values in the curriculum of English language and the participants recruited in this study are teachers of English. The purpose of this selection is, first, the focus of this reform was on teaching/learning foreign languages, particularly teaching of English language. Noticeably, the Algerian government is making great efforts to promote the English language learning in Algerian schools and the Ministry is paying a lot of attention to different professional teachers' training programmes through seminars, study days and conferences. In addition, the Algerian Government is offering travel facilities to EFL teachers who are interested in exchange programmes and scholarships with English speaking countries (Goura and Ziani, 2021). In addition to this, the Second-Generation curriculum that is the focus of policy reform on this research requires teachers to address the language variety in Algeria and the different ethnic groups that compose the Algerian society by spreading and enhancing values of nationalism and citizenship to unify and integrate the population (the Official Bulletin, 2008). Therefore, it is important to briefly introduce an overview of the language context in Algeria which will help in understanding why this policy was introduced and why this study is needed.

Algeria represents a good example of 'linguistic plurality or diversity' (Medjahed, 2011; Djebbari, 2016, p. 6). Algeria is multilingual country, and this can create competition or linguistic conflict between these spoken languages, dialects, and varieties. In Algeria, there are three main language groups: Arabophones, which represent the vast majority 70–75% of the whole population, Berberophones represent 25–30% settled in different places in Algeria, and Francophones. The Francophones are usually bilingual (Arabic–French or Berber–French); they often live in coastal Mediterranean cities (east and west) as the French colonialism mainly settled in these areas (Benrabah, 2014).

After the independence in 1962, the Algerian Government announced Arabic as the national and official language of the country (Arabization) as the stakeholders at that time believed, that it was ideal to spread the Arabic language and eliminate French language use as it was

considered a colonial remnant. This policy was announced by the first president Ben Bella, and then by his successor Boumedienne (PCGN, 2003; Maamri, 2009). Benrabah (2014) mentioned that there are two types of the Algerian Arabic dialect: the Algerian dialect that is spoken by the north population and the Saharan (desert) spoken dialect that is spoken by those of the south. On the other hand, Berber has four spoken varieties "Tamashek" which is spoken by the "Tuaregs" of the Sahara, "Mzab", "Shawia" and "Takbaylit". The Berbers felt themselves targeted by the policy of Arabization by replacing their languages by the Literary Arabic Benrabah (2014) but the policymakers mainly were trying to establish a language that can unify the different ethnic groups, especially that Arabic language was mastered by the majority at that time. As a result, in April 1980 they requested an acknowledgement of their language and culture. Later, in 2002, the Berber was recognized as a second national language yet not official Benrabah (2014). Therefore, they continue to ask for their language to be acknowledged as an official language. In 2016, the Government fulfilled their request and announced Berber (Amazigh) as a second official language of Algeria (Poggeschi, 2016). This situation in Algeria represented the language antagonism or friction between the dialects or the local languages. Tabory and Tabory (1987) noted of the historical context:

The Algerian situation is complex, as it is at a crossroad of tensions between French, the colonial language, and Arabic, the new national language; Classical Arabic versus colloquial Algerian Arabic; and the various Berber dialects versus Arabic. The lessons from the Algerian situation may be usefully applied to analogous situations by states planning their linguistic, educational and cultural policies.

(p. 64)

Thus today, the standard Arabic is considered as the official language, French is the first foreign language and English is the second foreign language. Hence, English language is taught compulsorily until the Middle School and continues to be taught during Secondary School as well as university level. Compared to French, English language does not seem to have a crucial role in the social life of the Algerian people, because it is not historically linked to their social life as opposed to French, which is considered a fact in the history of Algeria, it was a language left by the French colonialism and continues to be (Boulaia and Boumalek 2017). Moreover, English is not the students' natural communicative environment outside the classroom. Thus, it is commonly used in formal setting (classroom). EFL teachers are considered the main source that can provide the learners with the necessary knowledge about the English language (Goura and Ziani, 2021). This is not the case for the French language, as the population's competence in French reached one million that were able to read it and six million could speak it after the independence in 1966 (Bennoune, 2000; Gordon, 1978; Heggoy, 1984; Lacheraf, 1978, cited in Benrabah, 2014). Belmihoub (2012) and Djebbari (2016) gave another explanation to the situation, since 1962, five languages have been introduced in Algeria. The Algerian Colloquial Arabic and Berber (which are commonly used in informal daily interactions), the Modern Standard Arabic, French as a second language or as a first foreign language and later (1980s-1990s) English was recognised as a foreign language or as a second foreign language, but not the French language, which was more frequently used in social settings.

However, in the recent years, the status of English language has changed due to the recent political and economic developments in Algeria; the policymakers believed that French language should be replaced by a more powerful and influential language in term of media,

technological, economical, and academic advancement, they agreed that English language would be the ideal alternative (Banrabah, 2014). Consequently, there has been an increase of awareness among people concerning the importance of learning this language. As a result, “The status of English as a foreign language does not change, but its value within the Educational reform has increased” (Boulahia and Boumalek 2017, pp.7-8). Another reason explained by David Gordon in 1963, who was a sociologist and leading Algerian poet, during his interview stated that:

In ten to fifteen years, [...] Arabic will have replaced French completely and English will be on its way to replacing French as a second language. French is a clear and beautiful language, [...] but it holds too many bitter memories for us.

(Gordon, 1966, quoted in Banrabah, 2013, p. 90)

Therefore, the foregoing explains why the Algerian Government began promoting the teaching of English language, French will be always regarded as colonial language that reminds the Algerian citizens of the brutal colonialism. In addition to English, other foreign languages such as German, Spanish, and Russian also existed in Algeria, but their introduction was not as important as English (Belmihoub, 2012) for the reason mentioned above.

This competitive situation between the dialects and languages is certainly challenging for policymakers and stakeholders when designing the educational programmes, they have to be careful and selective in term of selecting the content, structure, language of structure and others. This sensitivity accounts, in part, for the numerous reforms the Government has introduced. In addition, the content of the curriculum certainly must promote and enhance solidarity and integration between the different ethnic groups, and it should not by any means encourage friction or disagreement.

2.3 The Educational Schooling System in Algeria

It important to understand the structure of the educational system in Algeria, as the policy of embedding values in the school curriculum was introduced primarily to Middle Schools and later to primary schools. The Secondary and University levels were not included in the recent reform through the introduction of the Second-Generation curriculum. Algeria considers the fundamental schooling as an initial establishing phase of knowledge, which lays the base for the following levels of education. Furthermore, the four years of Middle School are important foundation years for the intellectual, emotional, physical, and social development of the child. These years will help the students to gradually acquire competencies at all levels of school Education and to continue learning even after leaving school (Ministry of National Education, 2016). Accordingly, it is crucial that reforms and revisions be implemented at this early education stage. Therefore, this research studied the values-inclusion in Middle School level. It is also important to outline the structure of the school system in Algeria and the difference between the four levels: Preparatory, Fundamental, Secondary and University or Higher Education level.

The Educational system in Algeria was divided to gradual (progressive) stages according to previous scientific conception that humans during their life, they go through different steps each has special characteristics (Torki, 1982). Bellalem (2008) described the structure of the schooling system as follows:

Level	Description
<p>Preparatory level</p> <p>It lasts for two years, from age 4 to 6 years.</p>	<p>The Ministry of National Education determines the conditions of this stage. Its aim is to help the Algerian families to ensure a high level of education for their children by developing their physical and mental identity, as well as preparing them for fundamental schooling when they reach age of six-years. The language of instruction during this phase is Arabic (The Decree of Organizing and Managing the Preparatory School, Act N°=11).</p>
<p>Fundamental level</p> <p>It lasts for ten years, from age 6 to 16.</p>	<p>The Presidential Decree of the Official Gazette of the Algerian Republic established this phase in 1976. It combines two levels Primary and Middle schooling. Education in the first stage is unified to all children and it is devoted to mastering basic skills about mother tongue ‘Arabic’, religion, mathematics, first foreign language ‘French’, and history/geography. However, during Middle School level, there is a variety of modules; it combines between linguistic, social, and scientific modules. The student are required to pass a national examination called “Basic Education Certificate” or Middle School Certificate (BEF/BEM) in order to follow their studies at the secondary school (Lycée).</p>
<p>Secondary level</p> <p>Last for three years, from age 16 to 18.</p>	<p>The first year is a foundation course, which includes mixture streams; Literary streams based on studies in Humanities and Social Sciences, Scientific Streams includes Biology, Mathematics, Physics and Chemistry. Technological Streams (Applied Technology). This phase concluded by a Baccalaureate examination (BAC) as a condition for pursuing studies in Higher Education.</p>
<p>Higher Education level</p> <p>Currently LMD system.</p>	<p>The students who succeed their BAC (Baccalaureate examination) exam are directed to follow their studies at university for an undergraduate degree, in a subject of their choice. However, those with low grades are mainly unable to make any choice and mainly referred to other available subjects.</p>

Table 01: The structure of the Educational System in Algeria.

2.4 The Context of Curriculum Reform in Algeria

The focus of this research is on embedding values in the school curriculum, and this policy was introduced through a reform called the Second-Generation curriculum (the Official Bulletin, 2008). It is important to outline some important reforms that have been implemented to the educational system in Algeria during post-colonial period and which have led to the recent one.

The brutal French colonialism, which lasted for 132 years, tragically influenced the Algerian culture and language. The literacy rates for reading and writing among Algerians remained at around 90% of populations that were illiterate with just 5.5% of the population that were able

to read and write, and only in Literary Arabic (Benrabah, 2014). Furthermore, after the hardship (a civil war begun in 1991 and ended in 2002, also known as the black decade) that Algeria witnessed in 1990's, the educational system was devastated and there was an urgent need for some reforms in all sectors. Initially in Education these aimed to re-establish peace and reconciliation at the beginning of 2000. At this time, The Algerian Government considered education as a crucial factor in the development of the economic and politic sectors of the country (Toualbi-Thaalibi,2006; Tawil,2006; Ministry of Education, 2006). Hence, it has always been prioritized in the reform programmes.

The movement of reformation and inventiveness was collocated with several meetings between the Algerian and UNESCO Officials, where on the 2nd of October 2003, the UNESCO agreed to fund these educational reforms (Tawil, 2006; Ministry of Education, 2006). This project was named as 'The programme of Support for the Educational Reform in Algeria (PARE)'. There were further engagements in this context during 2003 and 2006 in order to test the validity of these reforms and establish future decisions (Tawil, 2006).

The National Commission of the Educational reform (CNRE) was assigned by the Algerian government in 2000 with the aim of evaluating the situation of the educational programme and recommending any required reforms that matched the updated democratic system and economic development (Ministry of Education, 2006). In 2001, the CNRE provided feedback stating that there is a need for renovating and revising the system to meet the challenges of the 21st Century (Tawil, 2006). In response to this, the policymakers saw the necessity for radical change to address three key aspects of education. First, reforming school structure, reforming and evaluating teacher training, which involved improving the knowledge and skills of teachers and inspectors and reforming teaching syllabuses and textbooks by elaborating and introducing new teaching programmes, providing and evaluating new teaching resources and materials. In addition to introducing new teaching methodologies to meet the programme objectives. In nutshell, according to the policymakers a successful reform needed to address three key factors the school structure, the curriculum content and teachers' training programmes.

2.4.1 The Main Educational Reforms

Reforming the Educational system has become a necessity, whether because of the current situation of the Algerian school or because of the changes recorded in various fields at the national and global levels, which impose themselves on the school, as an integral part of Algerian society. Among these changes, at a national level for example the emergence of political pluralism. Furthermore, at an international level, for example the globalization of the economy is required (the official bulletin-the orientation law N°08-04 23, 2008). Therefore, issues of school reform are "no longer an area of discussion, but have become urgent and vital" (Bengueneb, Atallah and Djourdem, 2021, p. 52-53).

The following table outlines the main reforms that were introduced to the Fundamental education in Algeria.

Reform	Description
Arabization (1962)	After the independence in 1962, the Algerian Education system was influenced by the European example and mostly conducted in a foreign language (French). It was also taught by foreign teachers. The Algerian government agreed to gradually increase Arabic sessions in all levels, all subjects were taught in Arabic, and there was a decrease in the time devoted for the teaching of French language (Benrabah, 1999). This policy of course favoured national integrity and unity.
Fundamental Schooling System (1976)	This reform addressed the Primary schooling; it aimed at integrating the primary and secondary schooling together to become 9 years. Where the subjects are taught in Arabic, except for foreign languages. At that time, English was taught until Middle school at age of 13. However, many educators criticised this movement, as they believed the teaching of foreign languages at early schooling is more efficient. Steinberg (1993), Oyama (1976) and Tahta (1981), and Scovel (1988) believed that children at a younger age tend to acquire the language easily and effectively and tend to acquire a perfect or almost perfect accent, whereas older people could learn only the syntax and vocabulary of a language (Rezig, 2011).
English in the Primary School (1993)	In 1993 a new policy was introduced for the aim of supporting children to learn foreign languages at an early age; offering them the chance to choose between the foreign languages to be taught; either French or English as a compulsory foreign language. This policy did not last as the majority of parents choose French over English (Nadia, 2011).
First generation Curriculum, Competency Based Approach (2003)	This reform emphasized the use of Competency Based Approach that was referred to as the First-Generation Curriculum. However, it was under constant review and criticism until the school year of 2016-2017 when a new program was introduced to the Algerian pupils at the level of Middle Schools named the Second-Generation Curriculum (Goura and Ziani, 2021).
Second Generation Curriculum (2016-2017)	In the view of globalization, the policy makers have given much importance to teaching of foreign languages, precisely English. Hence, a new curriculum was designed to promote communication at the first place and “to deepen universal values” (Boulahia and Boumalek, 2017, p.48).

Table 02: Main Reforms Implemented in the Educational System in Algeria.

Some of the reasons for reforming the educational system were political or social reasons rather than academic or pedagogical. For instance, the Arabization policy was implemented with the aim of strengthening Arabic and Muslim identity among Algerians. It also worth mentioning

that it was nationally criticised because first, as previously mentioned the Berbers claimed that the policy targeted their language and culture. Second, a shortage of Arabic speaking teachers, led the government to hire more than 1000 teachers from the Arab world, mainly the Middle East and Egypt, in order to secure the Arabization policy (Benrabah, 2005; Nadia, 2011; Mami, 2013).

Another reason for adopting the Arabization policy according to Benrabah (2010) is that, after the independence in July 1962, the leaders of Algeria at that time adopted the policy of “Arabization” as a national language in order to reduce the conflicts and tribal differences. As such, they were influenced by “assimilation” as “a model of nation building”. (p.59) which traced back to the liberal revolutions in the 18th Century, where the population are expected to be monolingual (speaking the same language) as this might help the citizens to be alike, sharing the same thought patterns, behaviour and habits in other words becoming more united. The supporters of this model believe that countries who apply this model such as the USA, China, France are considered as secured and united nations. In addition, the fundamental schooling reform was applied to replace the French language by English language to reduce the spread and the influence of French language. This taught was also shared by Miliani (2001) who stated that the policy of fundamental schooling failed because it was a political decision rather than Educational one.

2.5 The Second-Generation Curriculum

The Algerian government set three main objectives for the school, these objectives are education, socialisation, and qualification (The Official Bulletin, 2008). Therefore, they aimed at designing a comprehensive reform to build a harmonious and efficient educational system in order to allow the Algerian society to face the multiple challenges of the actual and the future era (Official Bulletin, 2008). The reform also aimed to achieve the scientific and technological conditions that can ensure sustainable development. The Second-Generation curriculum (Ministry of National Education, 2016) reform has very promising objectives in terms of emphasising values, competencies and adopting a communicative teaching approach as it was built upon three main elements, which are communicative competencies, core values and cross-curricular competencies (Goura and Ziani, 2021). Four axes were considered in structuring the new curriculum; cognitive axis, which includes the logical organization of knowledge, pedagogical axis that addresses the educational status and evaluation. The format axis that ensures the comprehensive harmony of the curriculum through designing curricula units and activities as well as setting integrated objectives to all subjects; the value axis that ensures the values of identity and belonging to Arabism and Amazigh in a limited geographical and time frame as well as social, cultural, and universal values (Bouhafs, 2017; Ministry of National Education, 2016). Accordingly, the school must contribute to perpetuating the image of Algeria, as an Islamic country, an integral part of the Maghreb, Arabic nation, Berber,

Mediterranean and African country, and it must be closely linked to its geographical, historical, human, and civilizational foundations.

The following table describes the aspects of the curriculum of English language through the Second-Generation reform.

Second Generation Curriculum/ English Language	Description
Communicative-Competencies	The students will be able to interact, interpret and produce oral and written messages/ texts of average complexity; a descriptive, narrative, argumentative or prescriptive type, using verbal or non-verbal support (written texts, audio, and visual aids).
Core Values	<p>Identity: the students value three dimensions of their identity (Arab, Islamic, Amazigh) and expresses them using English.</p> <p>National conscience: students are conscious and proud of their rich historical, linguistic, and cultural heritage.</p> <p>Citizenship and openness to the world: they demonstrate their respect for the nation’s symbols and readiness to protect them.</p>
Cross-curricular competences	<p>Intellectual: students use their critical ability/autonomy/creativity to process different types of texts.</p> <p>Methodological: they are actively involved in pair or group work. Develop strategies and effective study methods.</p> <p>Communicative: They acquire the ability to communicate with others through ICT.</p>

Table 03: Middle School English Language Curriculum in the Second-Generation Reform.

The above table shows that according to the new reform, the goal of teaching the English language in Middle School is to equip the learners with the necessary language tools they need for effective communication, as this can help people in the society to live in harmony with the modern time. It is also to promote both the national and global principles and develop critical thinking skills. Besides, recognising today’s and tomorrow's changes and difficulties in order to contribute to the formation of good citizens. Providing all students with access to science, technology, and world culture while avoiding risks of acculturation (Ministry of National Education, 2016).

The construction of the Second-Generation reform (Ministry of National Education, 2016) was based on the following: inclusiveness, which set building effective curriculum for each educational stage. Harmony, by explaining the relations between the various components of the curricula of the years and in all phases and fields to address the disintegration of the First-Generation curriculum and separated the competencies incidental to ensure the harmony of

horizontal curriculum. Applicability, by adapting the process of adaptation to the conditions of implementation. Readability means simplicity, clarity, and accuracy. Finally, *prima*, which means the reform, has to be consistent between the objectives of training carried by the curriculum and educational needs (Ministry of National Education, 2016). Speaking about the objectives it is noticeable from the table above (table 03) and the goals stated that there is a great focus on the morality side of education, and it is considered as important as the pedagogical development. Thus, the values-inclusion into school curriculum is the unique contribution of the Second-Generation curriculum. By this policy, the stakeholders believe that the value education or the character education are important for developing well-rounded individuals who can make positive contributions to society, culture, and the natural environment.

The policymakers in Algeria are aware of the importance of value education, thus they support the introduction of values in school curriculum. Instilling essential values such as identity, citizenship, honesty, integrity, and respect help in building strong characters and personal growth for individuals to become responsible and accountable citizens. Besides, this may also foster critical thinking, students will be encouraged to think critically and reflect on their actions, which helps them to make better decisions and solve problems. Promoting social values aims to spread and support social harmony among people in society through imparting integrity, cooperation and respect the diversity (Official Bulletin, 2008 and MNE, 2016).

2.5 The Core Values Introduced in the SGC

The introduction of the SGC reform highlighted a unique contribution to education system which is introducing three important core values of national identity, conscience, citizenship, and openness to the world to be taught as part of the curriculum (MNE, 2016). The implementation of the new reform maintained the same pedagogical approach which is competency-based approach (CBA), This approach was applied since 2003 (MNE, 2016), the focus was more on instilling the core values in pupils through the school curriculum. These core values are rooted in the declaration of the 1st of November 1945 by the FLN General Secretariat (Official Bulletin, 2008). This statement issued by the Algerian National Liberation Front on the insurgency to face the French occupation, the statement also included the principles, values, characteristics, and constituents of the Algerian society which must be instilled and fostered again after being targeted by the French colony (Official Bulletin, 2008). Therefore, stakeholder impose explicitly on teachers the task of enacting the core values (Official Bulletin, 2008 and MNE, 2016). On the other hand, in 2015 Algeria took part and

signed up in the United Nations (UN's) sustainable development programs, which required all countries to be involved in promoting lifelong education and promoting national and universal values (National Curriculum Committee, 2015). The national values associated with those values that promote the pupils' s identity, nationality, belonging as well as those promoting citizenship. On 1 January 2016, the world officially began implementation of the 2030 Agenda for sustainable development (USNDG, 2030), the transformative plan of action based on 17 sustainable development goals to address urgent global challenges over the next 15 year, among these goals is to ensure that all people have access to quality education and lifelong learning opportunities. This Goal focuses on the acquisition of foundational and higher-order skills at all stages of education and development; greater and more equitable and inclusive access to quality education at all levels, as well as technical and vocational education and training (TVET), and the skills and values needed to function well and contribute to society (The Sustainable Development Goals Report, 2023).

Moreover, Bouhafs (2017) believes that Algerian government implemented the teaching of core values as a result of the influence of the US Agency for International Development (USAID) which plays a major role in education and curriculum changes in many countries. USAID's commitment to education extends beyond academics, it encompasses character development, inclusivity, and resilience, ensuring a brighter future for learners worldwide. The U.S. Agency for International Development (USAID) plays a crucial role in promoting education worldwide (USAID, 2021). Furthermore, it supports character education in schools and its education policy aims at increasing access to quality education for marginalized and vulnerable children and youth (USAID Education Progress Report, 2021). Literacy, numeracy, and social-emotional skill development as well as strengthening education institutions and promoting equity and inclusion (USAID Education Progress Report, 2021). Ultimately the goal is to create a world where education systems enable all individuals to thrive and contribute to society (USAID Education Progress Report, 2021). In this sense the policy of introducing the core values to be taught in schools as part of the taught curriculum through the SGC reform was an answer for a global call for the implementation and the development of character and values education.

Following this, it is crucial to discuss the intentions of the stakeholders (Ministry of National Education) on how these core values should be taught in the classroom. The supporting documents including “the curriculum of English, the teacher's guide, and the yearly planning” tackled the core values and some instructions for the teachers to follow (Smara, Chenni,

Bouazid, and Boukri, 2018). The current study is exploring the EFL teachers experience, thus the focus is on the curriculum of English language. The table below lists the different core values that should be taught in each level, the Middle School phase is divided into four levels or classes (MS1 stands for Middle School 1).

MS1	MS2	MS3	MS4
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Socializing -Respect -Honesty -Living together -Being proud of one's country -Knowing and understanding the other through flags, currency, dwellings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Sharing experiences -Staying healthy and keeping fit -Respect of neighbours -Socialising 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Living with others and accepting/respecting them -Being proud of family and extended family with respect -Protecting pets -Protecting one's health and the environment -Valuing great achievements in the field of science, sport... -Respecting animals rights -Accepting the other with qualities and defects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Being honest and able to talk about embarrassing and difficult situations -Respecting elder people/family advice -Being an active reader/open to other cultures -Understanding the other/respecting differences in eating, dressing habits -Valuing national and universal landmarks, cultural heritage Valuing the great achievement in all field of life/science, technology, arts, sports, literature, history -Being proud of national outstanding figures/ national heroes -Solidarity in times of catastrophes/ illness -Being proud of belonging to a nation/ culture/ religion -Knowing and respecting cultures of the world through celebration days

Table 04: The List of Core Values for the Curriculum of English

The three categories of core values of national identity, conscience, citizenship, and openness to the world are the general or the broader axis, under each one of them there is a list of sub-values. These sub-values represent the broader or the general subsequent. Also, each level has different sequences or unites each unit or sequence focuses on precise values to be instilled. The teacher's guidebook (Smara, Chenni, Bouazid, and Boukri, 2018) structures the different lesson content and procedures that should be followed by the teacher. According to the teacher's guide (Smara, Chenni, Bouazid, and Boukri, 2018), the teachers has a lesson to present for instance in MS3, unit two there is a lesson about "the past tense", initially the

teacher needs to decide about the lesson focus or the language skills to be developed (listening/writing), then the teacher should define the objective for the lesson, in this case the objective is that “at the end of the lesson, the pupils will be able to narrate past events, experience, and childhood stories using past simple tense with irregular verbs”. Then the target competencies “interact, interpret, and produce”. What materials or teaching aids the teacher is going to use for instance, handouts, images, and/or the textbook. The following step is defining the cross-curricular competencies which is divided into four categories “intellectual competency, methodological competency, communicative competency, and personal and social competencies”. Identifying the core values to be integrated in the lesson, in this lesson for example the core values that the teacher is going to focus on are “socializing, valuing the past to build better future, respecting the difference, respecting elderly people as they are the source of our historical and cultural heritage, and valuing childhood memories.” Moving to the lesson procedures or framework which is consisted of the warm-up (asking the pupils about their childhood for example), presenting and explaining the lesson, and then practice (giving pupils different activities to practice what they have learnt) (Smara, Chenni, Bouazid, and Boukri, 2018). In a nutshell, the teacher needs to integrate the core values in the lesson, it can be grammar lesson, vocabulary, or practice. Then choosing what language skill among the four skills to focus on (reading, listening, writing, or speaking), the objective of the lesson and the chosen core values help the teacher to plan the lesson forward. The lesson is divided into four phases, the warm-up, presentation, practice, and use. During the last stage which called as use or the production (MNE, 2016) the teacher can test and evaluate the students’ understanding of the lesson and ensuring whether he/she could effectively conveyed the key values through activities and tasks for instance, written expression or oral expression tasks.

2.6 Background History of Values and Character Virtues

According to Arthur, Kristjánsson, Walker, Sanderse, Jones, Thoma, Curren, Roberts (2015) the historical background of character and virtue is rooted in ancient philosophical traditions, particularly in the works of Aristotle and other prominent thinkers. The concept of character and virtue has its origins in ancient Greek philosophy, notably in the works of Aristotle (384-322 BC) (Arthur et al., 2015). Aristotle's ethical system emphasized the importance of virtues in achieving human flourishing and living a good life. Aristotle's ethical framework focused on the development of moral virtues as a means to achieve eudaimonia, or flourishing. He identified virtues such as courage, temperance, and justice as essential for ethical living (Arthur et al., 2015). The ideas of Aristotle on virtue ethics were further developed and integrated into

Christian moral theory by theologians like St. Thomas Aquinas in the thirteenth century. This integration helped solidify the importance of virtues in European moral thought. Later, in the eighteenth century, various moral theories emerged, but it was in the twentieth century that European philosophers revisited Aristotle's ethical ideas and promoted "virtue ethics" as a distinct perspective in moral theory (Arthur et al., 2015).

Scholars like Joseph Pieper (1966) in Germany, Vladimir Jankelevitch (1949) in France, and Elizabeth Anscombe (1958) in the UK played significant roles in reviving the concept of virtue ethics and emphasizing the importance of character in moral philosophy (Arthur et al., 2015).

The renaissance of Aristotelian virtue ethics led to a resurgence of interest in character education and moral development in various fields, including education, psychology, and philosophy. Therefore, scholars and educators began to explore how Aristotelian virtues could be applied in modern contexts to foster ethical decision-making, personal growth, and social responsibility. It influenced the educational practices, with a growing emphasis on character education in schools and universities. Thus, Educators recognized the value of cultivating virtues such as honesty, kindness, and perseverance in students to promote not only academic success but also moral integrity and well-being. As a result, educators sought to integrate virtues into educational curricula, pedagogical approaches, and school culture to nurture students' ethical growth and character formation. The practical application of Aristotelian virtue ethics involved translating theoretical insights into actionable strategies for character development and moral education (Arthur et al., 2015).

Values can originate from various sources and influences, shaping individuals' beliefs, attitudes, and behaviours. For instance, the cultural background as values are often instilled through cultural norms, traditions, and practices within a society or community. Cultural values can encompass beliefs about family, religion, work ethic, respect for elders, and societal roles. In addition, family plays a crucial role in transmitting values to children. parents, siblings, and extended family members impart moral, ethical, and personal values through upbringing, role modelling, and direct teachings. Also, many individuals derive their values from religious teachings and doctrines. Religious institutions provide moral guidance, ethical principles, and a framework for understanding right and wrong behaviour. For example, according to the Islamic world the core of akhlaq education is in the spiritual purification and obedience to God (Sutomo, 2014). The word akhlaq is from Arabic (akhlaq) and it shares the common semantic meaning with the English word "character", temper, moral, morality (in English) (Wehr,1971)

however, the word “akhlaq education” is a specific term in Islamic education (Sutomo, 2014). According to this ideology akhlaq is to live harmony in horizontal communication between human beings and vertical communication with God (Khaliq or Creator). Besides, moral, character, and ethics are associated with the efforts to manage the interaction of individuals for the better communication in social life, while akhlaq is reviewing more details to the individual to take care spiritual purification (Sutomo, 2014).

On the other hand, according to Arthur et al. (2015) and Jubilee Centre for Character and Virtues (2015) schools and educational institutions play a significant role in shaping values through formal and informal education. Curriculum content, character education programs, and interactions with teachers and peers can influence students' values. Furthermore, life experiences, including successes, failures, challenges, and relationships, can shape individuals' values. Personal reflections, critical incidents, and moments of moral dilemma can lead to the development or reassessment of values. In modern era, media, including television, movies, social media, are having direct and strong impact on individuals' values by portraying certain behaviours, attitudes, and societal norms. Media influences can shape perceptions of beauty, success, relationships, and ethical conduct. There is also peers and social networks influence which can also impact values through shared beliefs, group norms, and peer pressure. i.e., Individuals may adopt values held by their friends, colleagues, or social circles. Last but not least, philosophical and ethical theories, such as utilitarianism, deontology, virtue ethics, and existentialism, can provide intellectual frameworks for understanding and evaluating values. These theories offer different perspectives on moral decision-making and ethical principles.

As a result of this renaissance, ‘character’ and ‘virtue’ have recently witnessed a resurgence of interest, in political and educational circles, and also among the wider public worldwide. In education for instance, student ‘flourishing’ is increasingly being seen as an overarching aim of educational efforts, with good character considered a constitutive part of this aim (Walker, Roberts and Kristjánsson, 2015:85-86). In the UK, the Labour Shadow Education Secretary Tristram Hunt (2014) commented that character can and should be taught in schools. He argued that character and resilience are vital components of a rounded education and good preparation for a career. In the UK for example, 84% of parents believe that teachers should encourage good morals and values in their students (Jubilee Centre for Character and Virtues, 2013) and 91% of adults surveyed said that it is important that schools help children develop good character (Jubilee Centre for Character and Virtues, 2014).

2.7 Universal Values and the Experience of Values Education in the Arab World

The concept of universal values, as applied in countries incorporating values education into their educational systems, refers to fundamental principles that transcend cultural and geographical boundaries (Grönroos, 2011). These values serve as a moral compass guiding individuals towards ethical behaviour, respect for diversity, and social responsibility Grönroos (2011). By integrating universal values such as honesty, compassion, justice, and integrity into education, countries aim to cultivate a shared understanding of ethics and morality among students, fostering a sense of global citizenship and interconnectedness Grönroos (2011).

In the context of values education, universal values play a pivotal role in shaping individuals' character, attitudes, and behaviours. By instilling universal values in students, countries aspire to nurture a generation of individuals who are not only academically proficient but also morally upright and socially conscious (Alazmi and Alazmi, 2020). The promotion of universal values in education systems contributes to the development of well-rounded individuals capable of navigating complex societal challenges with empathy, integrity, and a sense of collective responsibility (Alazmi and Alazmi, 2020). Moreover, the incorporation of universal values in values education programs helps bridge cultural divides, promote inclusivity, and foster mutual understanding among diverse communities (National Curriculum Committee, 2015). By emphasizing universal values alongside culturally specific values, countries create a foundation for harmonious coexistence, respect for differences, and collaboration towards common goals. Through values education grounded in universal principles, countries aspire to build cohesive societies based on shared ethical standards and a commitment to the common good (Nishimura, Hussein, Erickson, Gallardo-lacourt, and Angelopoulos 2022).

the Arab world has witnessed subtle changes to behaviours of human communication which have degenerated trust and eroded competence festering in the community as a major illness leaving no true leadership in view. In turn this has affected the understanding of cultural identity and purpose of many young Arab individual. Among the essential tasks is the establishment of character and behaviour. Character education has ebbed for centuries in the Arab world and was linked to religious and moral virtues. Whilst there is no research into character education in Algeria, such research studies that might inform this study have been undertaken in other parts of the Arab world.

An experiment conducted by Mattar and Khalil (2011) at Hayah school, Hayah is a privately owned school, it is an International Academy established in 2003 and based in Cairo- Egypt. The school's language of instruction is English and supplements its international curricula with Arabic studies, religious studies, and Character Education. Character education programme at Hayah school runs from early childhood to high school, it is applied in elementary, middle, and high school. The program is taught as a separate subject with specific lesson plans. The sessions at Hayah involve the students in readings, writings, discussions, and role plays around respect, empathy, gratitude, loyalty, integrity, and responsibility. The aim of character education is to communicate high levels of moral development taking into consideration collective cultural codes, human behaviour, components of identity and the causes of identity crises of young Arabs in order to promote effective social habits and cultivate ethical goal oriented productive future leaders, with further focus on equity, efficiency, and excellence that is lateral to the cultural necessities of the Egyptian community(Mattar and Khalil, 2011). The programme

Allow the new generation to face the challenges of modern society and ambiguities of the new era without giving up their beliefs and values (Mattar and Khalil, 2011).

The Character Education (CE) sessions designed at Hayah are based on the concept of service learning to ensure the applicability of the programme to real life situations and give the students hands-on experience as opposed to the traditional classroom lecture. Activities in the classroom promote cycles of empowerment and excellence, through a values-based atmosphere, which allow students to move to increasingly higher levels of moral development. Discussions around the core values of Hayah and case studies allow space for critical thinking and problem-solving skills to develop. The development also promotes stages through which children must pass in order to move to a “higher stage” of development. The programme also popularized the use of “moral dilemmas” as one method for fostering increasingly higher levels of moral development (Mattar and Khalil, 2011).

The program’s initial design was based on Alruya curriculum. The Alruya curriculum is a self-leadership and management character education program. There are six main pillars of Alruya that range from good character, social obligations, social etiquette, communication means and methods, student rights, diseases of the heart and milestones (Mattar and Khalil, 2011). The program also took into account international perspectives such as those of the five major theorists writing for the National Commission on Character Education (Wilson 2000) where all agreed that educators must serve as role models, school and classroom climates must be caring, collaborative, and civil, Teachers must establish an interpersonal atmosphere where respect is continually practiced, students at Hayah are between the ages of four and seventeen and are enrolled in grades K through 12, and students at Hayah are between the ages of four and seventeen and are enrolled in grades K through 12 (Mattar and Khalil, 2011).

Implementing the Character Education program at Hayah begins from elementary, the K – stage which is “planting the seed” followed by the early childhood learning. The elementary school program is where the entire school becomes a community in which all participants—children and adults alike—work together to foster values of caring, helping, respect, and tolerance. The approach involves training the adults in a child’s life to model, teach, and embody core principles. Grade 5 material is embedded with morale behaviour activities suitable to the age and experience of the students during the forty-minute Character Education sessions. The classroom is not teacher – centred but rather designed to promote communicative learning and student engagement (Mattar and Khalil, 2011).

One of the most successful activities with grades 4 and 5 is Garage Sale is not the actual sale process but rather the academic collaboration on tasks and cooperatively learning in groups to set up the garage sale and negotiate business deals with fairness, honesty, and respect. Out on the field, a game of Silent Football rules is simple, no talking (and thus avoiding getting exasperated or aggressive with one another) and a strike does not count unless the ball is passed onto at least two other members of the team. The field activity promotes and teaches team spirit, self-restraint, and patience. Other successful methods used by teachers at Hayah school for the aim of fostering character education are, Role Modelling by introducing students to a renown or appealing role model who demonstrates in their life or achievements the ability to differentiate between right or wrong and do what is right is one of the most successful Character Education tasks as it entails debate and ethical decision making. The school also exhorts parents: “If you want your children to be people of character, you need to be working on your

own character on a regular basis” (Gauld & Gauld, 2002). The Learner Participation is the general knowledge session allows students to work together in groups to brainstorm the question prompts set by the teacher. The students lose points if they do not consult other members of the team before finalizing their answer. This healthy competitive atmosphere broadens student knowledge in different fields (economics, science, technology) as students are required to search for up-to-date information in various areas of knowledge. Furthermore, the multi-sensory engagement is the laboratory session which gives students the opportunity to discover their individual strengths and enjoy experimenting. The sessions held in the laboratory is a physical environment which prepares the students for experimentation with new and foreign ideas like origami, cooking, or mechanics just to mention a few examples. The lab process is one of self-discovery and learning (Mattar and Khalil, 2011).

However, despite the extensive efforts invested in designing the Character Education program implemented at Hayah, the Character Education team sensed the need to involve the parents of the students studying at Hayah in order to ensure that the Character Education core values advocated were extended into the home and beyond (Mattar and Khalil, 2011).

In Lebanon, the Centre for Educational Research and Development (CERD, 1997) has highlighted “building character” as one of the main general goals for the new Lebanese curricula: “It must be taken into account in the character building of an individual; the ability to self-realize, the sense of responsibility and the commitment to citizenship through the following fields: the mental cognitive field (knowledge and skills), the emotional affective field (attitudes and values), and the psychomotor field (behaviour). These abilities are enhanced through cultural, social, artistic and sports activities that match the individual’s potentials and his desires. Also, they can be reinforced by integrating them with civil education and suitable learning subjects” (CERD, 1997). Thus, cognitive development is not the sole purpose of schooling; character development is equally important (DeRoche and Williams, 2001).

In the Lebanese context, few Anglo-phone private schools, have initiated character education programs several years ago (Ghamrawi, Ghamrawi, and Shal, 2015). Meanwhile, the Lebanese public schools do not yet have any plan for adopting character education programs, despite the existence of international research body that emphasizes their positive impacts on the learning process (Ghamrawi, Ghamrawi, and Shal, 2015). The public-school leaders perceive character education as a secondary mission of school education and thus prioritizes schools’ role in academic achievement. Their vision towards character education goes opposite to the general goals of the Lebanese curriculum which highlights “Building Character” as one of its major targets (CRDP,1997). This finding is inconsistent with the research studies that emphasize the school’s role in developing character education as a condition for a society to survive and this socialization must be done by various sectors of society; family, community, media, and mainly schools (Berkowitz, 2012).

The study of (Ghamrawi, Ghamrawi, and Shal, 2015) indicates that character education remains as a theoretical goal of the Lebanese education system. The Lebanese public-school leaders prioritize the academic role of schools on character development despite the fact that “Building Character” is a major goal of the Lebanese curriculum (Ghamrawi et al., 2015). The Lebanese public-school leaders valued the importance of comprehensively defining character to include thinking, feeling and doing, the creation of a caring school community, and the role of schools in providing opportunities for moral action. On the contrary, they belittled the role

of school community in promoting the foundation of good character, the school's comprehensive intentional proactive approach to character development, the role of schools in offering a character related academic curriculum, the shared responsibilities of all school staff members in character development, and the importance of assessment in character development. These findings widely diverge from the principals of effective character education (CEP, 2014). Therefore, the goal of "Building Character" in the Lebanese curriculum should get realized. Then the first step would definitely require building the capacity of Lebanese school leaders to act as champions of change and as incubators who can provide full support for such notion. Principals need to recognize that schools are places for the overall development of students and not only their cognitive abilities. Any reform effort should focus on leadership, as leadership lies at the heart of the success of any educational reform (Ofsted, 2000) Character Education and Character Education programs are not exceptions to this rule.

In the UAE, Moral education was introduced in private and government schools in September 2017, it taught in schools for the first time in textbooks and there are no exams. The programme has four main pillars which include character and morality, individual and community, civic studies, and cultural studies. Pupils in public and private schools receive 45 minutes of moral education every week, the course was initiated by Sheikh Mohammed bin Zayed, Crown Prince of Abu Dhabi and Deputy Supreme Commander of the Armed Forces. The pilot scheme was trailed in 19 schools in January 2017, and moral education was implemented for grades one to nine in all schools across the country in September 2017 in both government and private schools (National newspaper 2017). The knowledge side highlights the importance of integrating it through many channels, social media, books, etc... concentrating on social initiatives (project management, initiatives such as volunteering, innovation, community service, interaction, and cooperation. The said initiative "aims to promote ethical values among school students as well as noble concepts, such as tolerance, respect, and community participation. the subject is integrated with the national education curriculum" (Emirates News Agency, January 2017). The moral curriculum that implemented in public and private schools has been developed with great care through cooperation with a group of experts and specialists in the academic and social fields from a country; these efforts have resulted in an advanced curriculum based on learning styles. Modern, interactive and beyond classroom boundaries to include informal, innovative learning environments (AlAli, 2020). Dr. Al Nuaimi further iterated that the trials of the 21st century necessitated the government, educators, and parents to work together to teach ethics and community values to young people, this is to build an educated and cultured society that is deeply committed to its national identity as well as moral values (AlAli, 2020). Miriam Al Zaabi, one of the educators stated that although the "curriculum has been changed a lot, it was focusing only on getting kids more creative and innovative, and they have forgotten how to respect even each other's innovations" (The National, October 2016). Therefore, Sara Al Suwaidi, the Acting Manager of Curriculum Division of the ADEC has organized a three-day training program for teachers. The training program aimed to enhance the efficiency of the teachers and to ensure that they acquired the necessary knowledge and skills needed for teaching the newly introduced subject (Emirates News Agency, January 2017).

Head teachers across the UAE believe staffs need to be given specialised training to teach moral education classes in schools (AlAli, 2020). given the novelty of the Moral Education Subject, it is necessary for the teachers to be well-trained in order for the initiative to fully

attain its objectives as Ruetters (2013) observed that nearly 60% of education preparation program graduates perceived that their programs inadequately prepared them for the 21st Century Classroom (Levine, 2006 as cited by Ruetters, 2013). The training programme designed in the UAE gave emphasis on the importance of the role and engagement of a parent in educating morals to children. To this end, Sheikh Mohammed quoted that “we look forward to the support of parents...their role is pivotal as they represent the first line in instilling ethics and a positive attitude. Home and family are the cornerstone for raising and educating children” (The National, October 2016).

On the other hand, in order to be able to bring out the potentialities in the hearts of students, it is necessary for the teachers themselves to be role models of humanistic values such as love, truth, right conduct, peace, and non-violence in their daily lives (Ishii, M., 2010). Teachers are role models for the next generation, investing time and effort in ensuring that every child is a proactive and responsible member of the wider community in which they live (The National, October 2016). The centre for Curriculum Redesign comes up with a Character Framework coming from inputs from more than five hundred teachers from around the world, and from their research emerged six essential qualities: mindfulness, curiosity, courage, resilience, ethics, and leadership. According to AlAli (2020), the successful implementation of character education in the UAE requires a holistic approach where both schools and parents are involved. As schools try their best to train and prepare teachers to be qualified educators of character both in instruction and content, the parents must also be made to recognize their role in instilling ethics and a positive attitude to their children. The engagement of the two shall provide a synergistic effect in educating the right morals and character to students. He added that an education program, must include six essential elements, namely: mindfulness, curiosity, courage, resilience, ethics, and leadership. Though taught formally, these elements must be practiced informally, to allow students to grasp the concepts better. Create a positive school culture and climate that includes high-quality teaching and learning, environment, sense of community, and staff leadership. In addition, teachers should not only be well versed with instructions, content, and evaluation, more importantly, they should also be emulators of the morals they are teaching. AlAli (2020) believed that the challenge is the fact that parents are still to "buy in" to the importance of moral education, "We need to involve parents in the teaching process to help them buy in to the idea. Thus, schools should have projects that are interesting to them."

2.8 Conclusion

In a multilingual country like Algeria where also different ethnic groups live together, teaching values became a necessity. Algeria introduced a policy of embedding values in Fundamental School level through a reform called Second Generation; this policy was introduced primarily in Middle Schools, as this level is considered a foundation phase where students develop their intellectual, emotional, physical, and social skills. The stakeholders agreed on three main values that should be promoted, identity, national conscience, citizenship, and openness to the world. The aim is not only to eradicate any societal conflict between the ethnic groups but this policy also national objectives such as making students aware of their culture, language, history and develop their characters by preparing them to professional life through which they can contribute to the evolution of the society and the country as well. There are other objectives which can be considered international, for example introducing the students to foreign cultures

and languages, train them to be open to diversity and tolerate differences, teach students how to communicate effectively with others and how to be able to introduce and express themselves.

Chapter Three

Literature Review

3.1 Introduction

This chapter contextualizes the chosen study, it also provides a historical background, describes the area of research, and identifies the gap in the existing literature, it is also the part where key terms and terminologies are introduced. More precisely, this chapter critically deliberate the relevant and existing studies that have been conducted in the area of values education, teaching and enacting values. The different results, hypothesis and theories that resulted from previous studies will also be tackled. Earlier in this chapter, there is brief description of the process of reviewing the literature, later the key term ‘values’ is defined and how it differs from other concepts such as norms, beliefs...etc, followed by a discussion of different research conducted in the area of values education and values pedagogy; the teachers experience of dealing with values in the school curriculum was described in countries similar to the Algerian context such as South Africa, Kuwait, and Turkey. The different methods through which these values are implemented and the role of the schools and the teachers in implementing values are also reflected in this chapter. Furthermore, other parts which may also contribute to the process of promoting values such as ‘family’ and its critical role is explored. The choice of these themes was guided by the research questions that worked as a framework for the thesis content.

3.2 Defining Key Terms

3.2.1 Values

It is important to build a clear understanding of the term values and how it differs from other key concepts that might be used as synonyms to the term ‘values’ before discussing the implication of this term in education. Values are the criteria by which members of society evaluate individuals, objects, events, concepts or ideas, actions, as either good, desirable, worthy, or wrong, worthless, and undesirable. (Shaver and Strong, 1976). Similarly, Schwartz (2011), stated that values are the criteria by which individuals evaluate whether people, events, or behaviours are good or not, according to human beings’ classification. Indeed, how can people perceive, evaluate, and judge other individuals’ behaviours and actions, as good or not, also on what basis, this would not be possible without defined and stated values. Moreover, values are the underlying abstract motivations of individuals. They help people understand, justify, and explain norms, attitudes, and behaviours (Feather, 1995; Rokeach, 1973; Schwartz,

1992). This means that values are abstract just like emotions, feelings, and morals. On the other hand, human values emerge due to different individuals' experience, psychological needs and societal demands (Rokeach, 2008). These are originated from institutions within the community or culture. Thus, values are factors that directly influences human life and society in a positive or negative way (Tonga, 2016).

Other terms such as attitudes, beliefs, traits and norms are sometimes used by people as synonyms to the word 'values. However, each term of these has a distinctive meaning (Schwartz, 2012), attitudes for example, reflect the evaluations of people behaviours, events or any objects whether are good and desirable or bad and undesirable, this could be concrete (ice cream) or abstract (progress), values in this case help to determine and underlie people's attitudes. In other words, if these attitudes promote a certain value, then they are considered positive and if they hinder it, they would be considered as negative. Beliefs on the other hand, are "ideas about how true things are related to particular ways, for example, war never solves problems, and Africa is larger than Europe" (p.16). Also, what characterizes beliefs is that people differ in how certain these beliefs are true. Furthermore, norms are the guidelines or rules that show the members of society how to behave, for example, "we should stand up when the national anthem is played". Yet people are not always certain about how much they should agree or disagree with these specific norms. Regarding the relation between values and norms, values affect people's decision on whether to admit or dismiss these norms.

3.2.2 Virtues

Aristotle and other Greek philosophers created virtue ethics, a branch of philosophy that examines an individual's character, in the Western tradition (Aristotle) (Rachels and Rachels, 2007). The main idea is that a "good" person will act in a proper manner, and one should cultivate the characteristics that allow them to do so.

Telos and virtues are two fundamental ideas in virtue ethics, Telos: Knowing one's own or one's profession's telos, or ultimate goal or moral aim, is crucial. The profession's moral and practical goals are both outlined in the telos. Virtues are character qualities that lead to success in both life and the workplace and can be acquired via repetition and habit (MacIntyre, 2007). According to Plato (Book IV), there are four cardinal virtues in classical thinking: applied wisdom, courage, temperance, and justice. But there is no universal list of virtues, and society's unique values will determine how certain virtues are regarded (MacIntyre, 2007). Virtues are not discrete qualities; rather, they function together rather than separately. For instance, it is risky to possess bravery without restraint (MacIntyre, 2007). There are three categories of

virtuosity; One is an extensionally analogous virtue to Aristotle's agreeableness virtue, a hybrid civic-moral social-gluer virtue. The second is phrenetic contemplation, which is an intellectual virtue that involves moral integration and sensitivity. The third is a complete and distinct moral virtue that possesses the typical Aristotelian characteristics of a golden-mean structure and an emotional motivator (MacIntyre, 2007). The important differences that Aristotle makes between civic virtues (covered in the Politics) and moral virtues (examined in the Nicomachean Ethics), especially agreeableness. As we may see "in our travels," the moral virtues are essentially universal and stem from a shared human nature (Aristotle 1985: 208). It is obvious that there cannot be one single goodness [virtue] which is the perfect goodness of the good citizen" due to the diversity of constitutional structures. In general, the civic virtues have a greater impact on a larger number of people than constitutions or civilizations.

Examples of moral virtues may include courage, justice, honesty, compassion, gratitude, humility, integrity, and respect. The blocks of character virtues are; Intellectual Virtues: Character traits necessary for discernment, right action and the pursuit of knowledge, truth and understanding for instance, autonomy; critical thinking; curiosity; judgement; reasoning; reflection; resourcefulness. Second, moral virtues which enable us to act well in situations that require an ethical response. For example, compassion; courage; gratitude; honesty; humility; integrity; justice; respect. The civic virtues which are necessary for engaging responsible citizenship, contributing to the common good such as citizenship; civility; community awareness; neighbourliness; service; volunteering. There is also performance virtues that have an instrumental value in enabling the intellectual, moral and civic virtues such as; confidence; determination; motivation; perseverance; resilience; leadership; teamwork (James and Kristajan, 2022). There also different components of virtue, for example virtue perception which signifies noticing situations involving or standing in need of the virtues. Virtue Knowledge and understanding i.e. understanding the meaning of the virtue term and why the virtue is important, individually and as part of a well-rounded, flourishing life of overall virtue, and being able to apply the virtue to episodes of one's own and others' lives. The virtue emotion refers to feeling the right virtue-relevant emotion in the right situation in the right way. In addition to the virtue identity which is understanding oneself as strongly committed to the virtues. Besides, virtue motivation is having a strong desire to act on the virtues. The discernment and deliberative action about virtues, including handling situations where virtues conflict or collide called virtue Reasoning. Last but not least is the virtue action and practice which refers to doing the right thing in the right way (James and Kristajan, 2022).

3.2.3 Morality

Morality is the individual's personal assessment of the values involved in differentiating between good and poor actions, or right and wrong. It may involve classifying and defending one's own acts or evaluating the morality of others (Gert, 2005). According to Kant (1996), morality is the will behind an action taken out of obligation, regardless of the outcome. According to Kohlberg (1981), an action's morality depends on the circumstances around it; it is not "moral" in and of itself. Moral concepts, according to Dewey (1975), are those that guide and restrain moral behaviour. He adds that morality is not inevitably the result of these concepts but rather is encouraged by actual experience. Collins (2008) defines morals as a set of shared values that are acknowledged to exist in every religious group, albeit in a different form. He offers three moral tenets. The first is about treating holy objects with appropriate reverence and (in the case of Christianity) about keeping the Sabbath. The second, though partially supplanted or reinforced by law, is focused on adhering to social norms. The third is asceticism, which is characterised as giving up sensuous pleasures in order to achieve a high level of spirituality.

Comenius (1910), Aristotle, Kant (2001), and Plato all emphasise the need of moral education in achieving a greater good. Aristotle and Plato discuss how a successful society depends on producing excellent citizens. Aristotle emphasises the significance of putting virtues into practice in order to achieve eudaimonia, or flourishing. According to Plato, moral evolution is restricted to the philosophical examination of virtues and truths, rather than the practical interpretation. They both agreed that moral education of some kind was necessary to develop moral citizens and capable leaders.

It seems that the word "moral education" was more commonly used in the 1960s and 1970s (Ward, 1969; Wilson, 1972; Hirst, 1974). More recently, the term has been employed in relation to character education (Eaude, 2016). According to Ofsted (2018), moral education is the capacity to distinguish between good and wrong, comprehend the law, and exhibit consequences awareness. According to Bayer (2017), moral education adopts a Socratic method to teach people how to apply reason as opposed to emotion.

According to Arthur (2005), there is ambiguity in the notion of moral education because it depends on whether the curriculum was founded on moral relativism or moral absolutism, which may vary depending on the political context. According to Dewey (1975), moral education cannot be achieved through direct instruction. According to him, moral education aims to help children develop into thoughtful adults who can function in a democratic society

by addressing every topic and contact they may have in the classroom. According to Dewey (1966), the direct instruction paradigm is authoritarian and intended for a small number of people to dominate a large number of people (Freire, 1996; Woolley, 2010). For instance, moral education is now included in the Social, Moral, Spiritual, and Cultural (SMSC) development strand of the English education curriculum (Ofsted, 2018).

3.2.3.1 Developing Morality

Dewey (1975) alludes to Plato's (1956) observation that the intricacy of the meanings of moral words makes it difficult to teach morality or how to be virtuous. According to Dewey (1975), moral development occurs more often through regular behaviour than through particular lectures. He also suggests that the entire curriculum should centre around and be concerned with moral development. According to Dewey (1975), a child's surroundings and social interactions help shape their morality. From a moral relativist standpoint, a youngster should learn virtues that are appreciated by others around them instead of following a strict code of morality. He explains how toddlers pick up skills through imitation, and how the routine behaviours they mimic cause them to internalise the values of the culture they live in. According to him, moral instruction that is unique can only convey to every child what other people believe—it cannot help them acquire or instil morality. According to Dewey (1975), didactic education could only be successful in assuring that every kid received the same knowledge about morality and virtues—not that they would actually experience the lived growth of morals—because of the particular nature of the child. This aligns with Comenius's (Komenský, 1910) ideas about establishing the proper environment for a child's moral and intellectual development. Rather than forcing information upon a child, Dewey (1975) believes that discovery helps them establish their moral code. This is because forcing information on a child result in followers rather than inquisitive learners. Woolley (2010) concurs, arguing that with a loving approach from their teachers, kids can form their own moral code by their own experiences and errors.

Carr (1991) draws attention to the conflicting theories surrounding moral development. The behaviourist theory promotes conformity and holds that because of outside influences, children will react to stimuli in a predictable and regular manner. In contrast to a democratic approach, this habitual reaction to an authoritarian approach suggests that children would learn the right or moral way to behave as a result of this action (Woolley, 2010).

Although behaviourist tactics are widely adopted by schools (Greene, 2016), Carr (1991) notes that there is little evidence to support their effectiveness since they do not address the role that agency or feeling play in this response. According to the behaviourist perspective, children respond to their environment through conditioning rather than moral indoctrination, which is sometimes referred to as "blind conformity" (Carr, 1991). This brings up the question of whether a good deed committed only out of duty or responsibility may still be justified as moral or virtuous (Carr, 1991; Kant, 1996).

Although morality develops early in life, according to Halstead and Taylor (2000), morality helps a child form, articulate, and defend their own values. They list other non-school factors, such as family, classmates, the community, other organisations, and the media, that contribute to a child's value development. This implies that an internal belief system is influenced by the environment (Bowlby, 1997; Mercer, 2018). Other than the media (which can include music and literature), all other impacts are dependent on relationships (Taylor and Halstead, 2000). It should be noted that although the media seems to have some influence, it is unknown how it affects children's values. However, given how commonplace social media use is, this issue may need further investigation. According to Halstead and Taylor (2000), partnerships and regular social interactions help people build their values unconsciously. Schools need to provide children with the opportunity to debate tales and events in order to help them develop and make clear their own personal values, given the increasing diversity of views (Halstead and Taylor, 2000).

3.2.4 Character Education

Character, according to Aristotle (2014), is an active state that is stable and drives an individual to act in a particular way. This behaviour can be both positive and negative. Aristotle (2014) makes a distinction between the virtues of intellect and character, stating that virtue of mind originates from instruction while virtue of character originates from habit and is focused on feelings, behaviour, and thought. According to Arthur (2005), character education has historically been associated with didactic, behaviourist methods that focus on reinforcing and controlling innate behaviour.

In a similar vein, Kohn (1997) backed character education's promotion of the idea that virtues should not be questioned or contested. According to him, these kinds of programmes promote conformity by rewarding kids for acting in the proper way—as determined by their teachers—rather than helping them work through problems. They also associate this with right-wing

religious ideologies (Jerome and Kisby, 2019). It also includes any activities that help students cultivate positive qualities and character traits (DfE, 2019). Martin (2020) pointed out that although the DfE's definition of character education appears broad and ambiguous, it might also give schools some leeway to choose not to implement the mandated character education (NatCen Social Research & the National Children's Bureau Research and Policy Team (NCSR and NCBaPT) 2017).

In light of the significance and imperative nature of character education, numerous nations endorse various endeavours aimed at integrating the subject into school curricula. One such initiative is the Jubilee Centre for Character and Virtues, which receives funding from the UK government in an effort to advance British national values (Martin, 2020). Additionally, the Knowledge is Power Programme (KIPP), an American effort aimed at enhancing character, has been implemented in 224 schools nationwide to date. A Christian social reform agency primarily creates the character education materials that the present UK government promotes (Martin, 2020). However, Jerome and Kisby (2019) assert that James Arthur, the Centre Director of the Jubilee Centre, exhibits a strong bias by only choosing candidates who share his beliefs, implying a lack of objectivity or balance in the presentation of the information.

Suissa (2015) brought up another issue regarding character education, which has to do with "individualism." According to Suissa, character education places the blame for societal issues at the feet of the individual rather than empowering kids to think politically by asking questions like "how people like us are to live together," which strengthens the argument for citizenship education (p. 110). Furthermore, Greene (2016) cautions against teaching that might make right because it puts vulnerable children at risk and fosters an environment in which it is assumed that kids should blindly obey adults who are bigger, older, or more powerful than them. Character education, according to Kohn (1997), has two distinct goals: to explicitly teach principles to students and to help them grow into "good" people. (Martin, 2020). One may argue that the former intention has always been a feature of primary school teaching, and most instructors would probably suggest it as one of their primary goals (Halland Simeral, 2015). The Jubilee Centre for Character and Virtues' programmes urge schools to implement a more structured approach to character education, which is the latter goal (Martin, 2020).

3.3 Moral Education, Character Education, and the Teaching of Citizenship

Dewey (1966) discusses the value of a democratic teaching style in the classroom. According to Dewey (1966), a democratic society cares about education because it wants to create a

community in which people may coexist and cooperate. His ethos was primarily driven by two ideas: encouraging people to think about the experiences and viewpoints of people who are seen as different from themselves and working cooperatively for the common good (Gordon, 2016; Dewey, 1966).

Whether taught directly or implicitly, these concepts are represented in all educational institutions (Kant, 2001; Plato, 2013; Komensky⁶, 1910). Glasser (1986) advances the concept of citizenship education by encouraging a democratic approach in the classroom to foster the social skills that are necessary for society. According to Woolley (2010), democracy is associated with citizenship and active learning, whereby educators choose to collaborate with students instead of imposing their will on them in order to achieve a "common good" (Woolley, 2010, p.66). It is not a novel idea to use education to advance moral and spiritual growth. Though from slightly different perspectives, Plato (c427-347 BC) and Aristotle (364-322 BC) both emphasised the significance of moral development. Aristotle emphasises the significance of putting virtues into practice in order to achieve eudaimonia, or flourishing (2014). According to Plato, moral development is restricted to the intellectual examination of virtues and truths, as opposed to the practical interpretation (2013). They both agreed that moral education of some kind was necessary to develop moral citizens and capable leaders.

Comenius (1910), Aristotle (2014), Kant (2001), and Plato (2013) all emphasise the need of moral education in achieving a greater good. Aristotle (2014) and Plato (2013) discuss how a successful society depends on producing excellent citizens. Comenius (1910) and Kant (2001) both want people who are fit to live in the heavenly kingdom. Additional distinctions include whether the goal of moral education is to produce submissive subjects or engaged and reflective citizens (Plato, 2013; Aristotle, 2014; Kant, 1996; Komensky, 1910).

According to Rorty (1998), educational philosophies can be divided into three primary groups: theories of knowledge, political education, and moral education. This implies that the three can be distinguished from one another but given their intertwinement; it is unclear how this can be done (Martin, 2020). Using a Kantian perspective on moral development, Roth (2015) highlights the significance of helping children to develop critical thinking abilities as a means of enhancing their conduct and academic performance. He suggests that information in the absence of thought can only lead to a thoughtless recall of facts rather than a thoughtful response. Chater (2000) issues a warning that moral education, values education, citizenship,

and personal, social, and health education can all be used as tools to force children to adopt the "correct" principles that have been externally developed.

In contrast, Freire (1996) criticises the methods used by states to design and carry out their educational programmes in an effort to produce and manage obedient citizens. Instead of creating values in collaboration with the stakeholders, he challenges the notion of forcing them upon the school community. The imposition of values is related to Freire's "banking" theory of education, which dehumanises and produces submissive, unthinking subjects rather than cultivating critical consciousness. Dewey (1996) poses the question of whether the goal of "teaching them what to think" schooling is to promote the development of an authoritarian society in order to impede the expansion of individual autonomy and accountability. Carr (1991) discusses the distinction between producing good subjects and educating good citizens. Maybe schools should use this question as a guide for deciding what moral, virtue, values, or character education is supposed to be about in their particular environments. Moral virtue is simply an inclusive component of a current term known as "character education". Character education is a contemporary old domain that encompasses various terms of values education, moral education, civic education, social-emotional learning, citizenship education, and positive youth development (CEP, 2014).

3.4 The Implementation of Values in the Curriculum

Three approaches are explored in the existing literature on values education when considering the implementation of values in school curriculums (Thornberg and Oğuz, 2013). These three approaches are first, the traditional approach is traditional and classical, initially introduced in the work of Durkheim (1961), it also supports the direct instruction of values by an adult. The purpose of the traditional approach is the explicit transmission of values in order to assist learners in conforming to societal norms and rules (Jones, 2009). Second approach is the progressive/constructivist approach, which means the implicit teaching of values. In the implicit approach, the learners are required to imply their reasoning, personal judgement, discussion and interaction in order to arrive to the fair conclusion (Ferreira & Schulze, 2014; Kohlberg, 1981). In addition, this approach offers to the student an active role to deduce the values from the values transmission process (Nieuwenhuis, 2007). The following approach is the critical approaches which is a compromise between both explicit and implicit implementation (Thornberg and Oğuz, 2013). Similarly Berkwitz (2017) identified three approaches of implementing the practice of moral virtues within school curriculum. The direct instruction paradigm which has origins in Aristotelian philosophy; it advocates inculcating the young with the virtues of society. There is a strong focus on the training of habits or virtuous behaviour (Ryan, Lickona, Berkowitz). The indirect instruction paradigm focuses on building a child's understanding (Kohlberg) and socio-moral development (Piaget), which in turn emphasizes the interpersonal interactions of peers under the guidance of caring adults (DeVries, Lickona, Watson, Berkowitz). The community building paradigm focuses on the

environment and caring relationships (Nodding) and on building moral communities (Watson, Berkowitz).

Building on this discussion, a study conducted on embedding values in the South African curriculum for the senior phase (Maphalala and Mpofo, 2018), The research did not mention any details on what was the intention of policymakers from introducing these. As for the research design, the research followed a descriptive case study, as the aim was to describe the implementation of values in the South African curriculum and semi-structured interviews were used to collect the data as a tool to maintain rich data and deeper description of the teachers' experiences as the semi-structured interviews emphasise the significance of the participants' lived experiences (Mertens, 2014). A purposive sampling technique was used for the aim of ensuring that data being collected from those who are involved in the phenomenon being studied regarding their experiences and perceptions (Merriam, 2009).

The study found that the schools in South Africa foster values either formally (explicitly), informally (implicitly) or both. In other words, the schools in South Africa use the three approaches explored by (Thornberg and Oğuz, 2013). The schools that foster values both formally and informally believe that the students are aware of the values the school is intending to deliver. Yet, the implicit model of education recognizes that values should occupy every aspect of the school system i.e., values should be represented not only in the curriculum, and teachers' behaviours and attitudes but also should be reflected in the school environment and work corporations between the staff. Thus, the entire school community becomes the model they desire the students to maintain in terms of values (Veugelers, 2013). In addition, some other schools believed that values taught formally in the school and informally in various activities. Mainly the claim that Veugelers (2013) is trying to raise is that delivering values in the classroom should be explicit, but at the same time implicit through the extracurricular activities. Extracurricular refers to the informal activities that is usually introduced as a 'voluntary' basis; at lunch times, after school hours, at weekends or during holidays, such as sports, clubs, societies, school journeys (Kelly, 2009). In short, the schools should explore both methods, formal and informal. For example, in early age schooling the values should be better taught explicitly as the children are unable to get the hidden intention of delivering these values. However, in middle to advanced ages, values should be delivered implicitly as this may help to instil values in the students, it could also be a way to evaluate the students understanding and opinion on these values.

The crucial point is that during the 1990s, the definition of values and the function of values in schools (explicit or implicit) were addressed and examined, resulting in a substantial body of study and literature (Arweck& Nesbitt, 2004). There are various points of view on values education, Dewey (1902), for example, the school is a crucial part in this world; thus, the students learn throughout the school, not just in the classroom. Dewey (1902) is referring to the way children acquire or learn values is not only through the official syllabus or only through the planned lessons but also outside the classroom. For example, when the child sees mutual respect and collaboration between teachers and administrators or school principals, he/she will maintain these values. Moreover, in a society, students must play their roles as members of societal environment and accept responsibility for their actions (Lovat, 2009), in other words, the critical aim of the school is to foster the sense of identity and citizenship in the students. In a social context, students are supposed to make decisions about values, which should encourage them to learn something in school (Billington, 2003). In other words, the values introduced in

the school curriculum should not be imposed as well they should not contradict with the students' values, culture, background, or beliefs. Stromquist (2007) stated that students should consider schools to be important cultural settings where they are influenced not only by their teachers but also by the school environment. The school environments and atmosphere on the other hand should reflect a supportive and positive place where these values are promoted. As a way of enhancing the students' identity and citizenship for example, the school can deliver this in several ways such as, hanging national flag, pictures of national heroes and celebrities, the content of the textbook should also be carefully designed and selected in a way that reflects all these aspects. In short, this paragraph tackled the implicit way in which values are delivered to the students or what could be considered as hidden curriculum. Bilbao, Lucido, Iringan, and Javier (2008) claimed that hidden curriculum or unintended curriculum is the physical condition of the classroom, school environment, and the mood of the teacher or the students, the teacher-learner interaction, the peer influence, and other factors that may affect the process of delivering the lesson. Grathon (2000) agreed with Bilbao et al. (2008) definition, according to him hidden curriculum exists but not everybody is aware of i.e., it is hidden simply because it is not planned. Kelly (2009) added further explanation to the term 'hidden curriculum':

it is all '... those things which pupils learn at school because of the way which the work of the school is planned and organized, and through the materials provided, but which are not in themselves overtly included in the planning or sometimes even in the consciousness of those responsible for the school arrangements such as, the social roles.

(p.10)

Another way from which hidden curriculum can be seen in relation to values, for example when the students come across pictures or mottos on the school walls that convey explicit and implicit messages, imitating the teachers' behaviours since they regard them as role models, especially in primary school. Thus, teachers have an impact on students' values, as well as their cognitive and psychological growth (Arweck and Nesbitt, 2004). Furthermore, they are regarded as one of the most important determinants of society's future. What referred to as hidden curriculum, is the targeted values that the school and the teachers want the students to indirectly acquire without explicitly teaching them (Arweck and Nesbitt, 2004). These educational values should establish a society based on tolerance, respect, justice, freedom, and human dignity, which will produce socially committed citizens (Morales-Vives et al., 2013). In short, what is to be said in this discussion is the implicit method of conveying values represents the hidden curriculum.

3.4 Pedagogical Approaches for Values Education

Lickona (2012) highlighted the 7 E's of teaching a character trait to be the best practices by creating, the 7Es refer to, first "explains it" which requires defining the character virtue, illustrates it, and discuss its importance. Second, examines it in literature, history, and current events. Exhibits it through personal example. In addition to "expects it" through codes, rules, contracts, and consequences. Experience it directly is another way through which a teacher can teach character virtue in the classroom. Character virtue also requires to be "encouraged through goal setting, practice and self-assessment. Evaluate it and give feedback. According to Arthur, Fullard, and O'leary (2022), there are ways of cultivating virtues of character, the neo-Aristotelian view of the psychology of moral development identified a number of pathways to becoming virtuous, which is through the typology of 'character caught', 'character taught', and 'character sought' (p.11).

a) Character caught, character development begins through a process of osmosis where pupils gradually pick up and internalise traits of reacting and acting that they witness around them within the ethos of their home/classroom/school/university, and the same occurs for professionals in their workplaces. Character can be caught through a positive school community, formational relationships, and a clear ethos. In this process the teachers should, acknowledge their influence as character educators, facilitating character education in their classroom and beyond. In addition to engaging in internal and external professional development in character education, identifying improvements for practice, also supporting pupils through pastoral care and mentoring, offering pupils guidance on their character development, and utilise research in the field to evaluate and improve their practice (Arthur, Fullard, and O’leary, 2022).

b) Character taught, virtues can be taught explicitly as part of classes in moral or character education, PSHE, religious education, and social and emotional learning – or indeed in any standard school subject. Character education can be taught through a school’s formal curriculum using teaching and learning strategies, activities, and resources. There are approaches that can be used in this process for instance, a discrete and bespoke timetabled subject, focussing explicitly on the teaching of character and virtue. Existing subjects, identifying opportunities to include character and virtue within the curriculum. Citizenship Education, developing the character and virtues needed to be an active and responsible citizen. Religious Education, using personal beliefs and world views to explore character and virtue form time, providing a daily platform to discuss character and virtue. Assemblies, bringing the whole school community together to explore character and virtue through a shared language. According to Arthur, Fullard, and O’leary (2022) There also strategies used for teaching character education in and out of the classroom, these strategies are:

Discussion-based learning where pupils engage with moral and ethical issues through teacher-guided and pupil-led interactions. Independent learning that encourages pupils to think critically and take responsibility for their own character development. Reflective learning which guides pupils to consider their character through critical reflection. Co-operative learning which involves pupils working together, encouraging teamwork and communication. Enquiry-based learning that encourages curiosity, challenging pupils to ask and answer open-ended questions. Experiential learning which offers pupils opportunities to be active learners through a range of virtue-forming experiences. And virtue literacy which develops virtue perception, virtue knowledge and understanding, and virtue reasoning (Arthur, Fullard, and O’leary, 2022).

The teacher can also employ different aids, resources, and activities to facilitate the cultivation of character virtues. stories that are focussing on moral and ethical complexities, moral dilemmas that encourage pupils to discuss and reflect on situations requiring an ethical response, current affairs reflecting on the presence or absence of virtue in news stories. In addition to moral exemplars which inspire pupils to live virtuously. Debates and discussions of the key moral and ethical issues. The literature, including poetry and historical narratives. Themed days or weeks focussing explicitly on character and virtues. School trips as a way of encouraging pupils to engage with a range of people and places as well as sport which may help in developing character through team and individual activity. Other activities may include creative arts including music and the visual arts, also drama to encourage pupils to understand

the perspective of others, and the reflective journal keeping focussed on the personal character development of pupils (Arthur, Fullard, and O'leary, 2022).

c) **Character sought**, involves the desire to discern and freely pursue one's own character development. It involves reflection and ultimately planning and setting one's own character commitments i.e. commitments to worthwhile living. It can be introduced and guided by the teacher at an earlier age. Character can be sought through chosen experiences that occur within and outside of the formal curriculum. Leadership can help in instilling character virtues through offering opportunities for pupil leadership, establishing thriving extra-curricular activities, planning organised school events that allow pupils to demonstrate their character, organising residential trips that provide challenging experiences in new environments, inviting a range of inspirational speakers into school to motivate pupils' character development, encouraging external facilitators to recognise opportunities for character education in their clubs and activities, and encouraging pupils to engage with work experience or apprenticeships as preparation for future employment(Arthur, Fullard, and O'leary, 2022).

According to Arthur (2005), there are several ways to teach character education, including employing moral stories in the classroom, moral examples from literature, history, and religion, and didactic instruction and role modelling of desired values and qualities. Additionally, Arthur (2005) notes that a useful and well-executed tactic for reiterating these ideals and character traits is the utilisation of outside organisations, such as service initiatives. As one might expect, the techniques are in line with the Jubilee Centre for Character and Virtues (Jerome and Kisby, 2019). The current government has authorised the centre, which provides materials and guidelines to promote the character education programme with the stated goal of influencing the "future attitudes and behaviours of the British people" (Jubilee Centre for Character and Virtues, 2019). However, character education research revealed that elementary schools, rather than focusing on individual subjects, developed students' characters and well-being through the school's ethos and values (DfE, 2017). Likewise, Carr (1991) notes that externally designed programmes place moral and social restrictions on the individual. All of these approaches to value thinking can be developed within democratic or authoritarian contexts, and they can be used in conjunction with authoritarian methods in educational settings (Skinner, 1974). A teacher's lack of confidence in their teaching method can lead to confused and ultimately unsatisfactory practice when they seek to mix incompatible authoritarian and democratic ideologies (Porter, 2014). Additionally, Chater (2000) emphasises how crucial it is for teachers to take ownership of their lesson plans and their approach to teaching.

According to Woolley (2010), democratic learning is the antithesis of authoritarian methods to education. According to him, the authoritarian methods are more focused on negative than on "Active participants" and "Recognised partners" (Woolley, 2010: 74). This begs the question of whether democratic learning environments in schools require values teaching because morality is ingrained in human nature (Glasser, 1992). Given that students are less able to function without external motivators or direction, schools that take a more authoritarian approach may find it beneficial to teach the values demanded more explicitly (Skinner, 1974).

Using a different methodology, Piaget (1997) suggests that moral development occurs in three separate stages. The child is not required to obey regulations throughout the first stage, which lasts from ages three to six. Ages six to nine are then followed by a morality of restraint, when kids start to see norms as something that are set in stone and enforced from the outside. In the

third stage, kids think that rules can be changed with compromise and discussion. This is in line with Piaget's theory of the transition from egocentrism to cooperation and the understanding of one's place in society (Mercer, 2018).

Philosophical debate has long surrounded the educational and cultural issue of how to raise morally upright citizens. Due to the impossibility of defining virtue, Plato (1956) addresses the challenge of determining whether virtue can be taught. He comes to the conclusion that moral behaviour is the result of a combination of knowledge and sound judgement, but that moral behaviour is driven by a virtue instinct rather than being learned or inherent. Aristotle (2014) makes a distinction between the virtues of intellect and character, stating that virtue of mind originates from instruction while virtue of character comes from habit and is concerned with feelings, behaviour, and thought.

Comenius expands on the notion of virtue development via action, arguing that, in the early phases, virtue, piety, and knowledge are produced via action, education, and prayer (Komenský, 1910). Referring to schools as "workshops of humanity," he suggests that moral beings should be formed there and suggests that virtue and piety should be taught via action and tenderness rather than via violence (Komenský, 1910: 71). Comenius emphasises the significance of the teacher modelling virtue through a nurturing approach, exhibiting a sincere interest in the student, and identifying the factors that inspire the student to educate in the manner best suited to the In order to develop their morality, he also suggests that people memorise biblical stories, verses, psalms, and catechisms (Komenský, 191).

Schools are under increasing pressure to demonstrate their effectiveness, but measuring the character of an individual or the impact of a character education intervention is extremely difficult. Because of the complex nature of character, and the specific difficulties attached to observing virtue in practice. However, it is not feasible or desirable to aim for the aggregation of individual character and virtue profiles, as the results can become counter-productive, philosophically, psychologically, and educationally. Discretion and circumspection are therefore required in any aspiration to measure virtues holistically; caution in the use of self-report measures is especially advised.

It is possible to evaluate the development of components of virtue, as earlier noted. different methods will apply to evaluating the development of virtue knowledge/understanding, on the one hand, and virtuous emotions, on the other. The first is to evaluate how a school's culture and ethos contribute to character education. To evaluate the effectiveness of a character education strategy, activity, or approach. For a self-reflection on 'personal' character and virtues undertaken by pupils themselves. This might be recorded at regular intervals during a pupil's educational journey, for example, in a journal. Evidence gained from peers, teachers, and parents would support this process. According to Brooks (1993), a character education consultant, implementation of a character education program must include a pre-assessment of goals and a post assessment of results.

3.3.1 Methods of Implementing Values within the Curriculum

The way teachers deal with values either implicitly or explicitly, achieved by different methods. Halstead and Taylor (2010) listed different methods of values education; direct instruction and special programmes of study, Discussion, collective worship (maintain religious practices),

circle time, use of stories, personal narratives, and peer mediation philosophy for children: or as described as Socratic dialogue (Ross, 1996). Which consists of; discussion techniques, conceptual analysis, formulation of the notions, the use of examples and so on (Lipman, 1984, 1987). Teachers may develop several methods according to the nature of the value and the aim. Teachers in South Africa for example, prefer strategies such as case study and role-play (Maphalala and Mpofu, 2018). The role-play is a teaching method that promotes enquiry-based learning, in which learners are given a situation or a problem to which they must respond by assuming a particular role play where they will be able to construct their own knowledge through exploration and problem-solving play (Maphalala and Mpofu, 2018). Whereas the case studies require learners to come up with solutions to a particular problem or a scenario, in this case the teacher may give the students scenarios or open-ended questions to answer or require them to develop multiple solutions to the case (Maphalala and Mpofu, 2018). Research conducted by Al-hooli and Al-shammari (2009) for the aim of examining the experience of teaching and learning moral values in the kindergarten curriculum in Kuwait where both qualitative and quantitative methods were used through questionnaire, observations, and interviews, suggested that in the kindergarten, most values transferred during story telling activity as most of teachers believed that the best way to teach moral values at this early stage education is through story and puppet shows as recommended by their supervisors in their colleges. One teacher among those who participated in Al-hooli and Al-shammari (2009) study declared that the children are very good observers, therefore, teachers should be a good model, it is necessary while teaching values, to create a common social area in the classroom, give responsibility to every student, contribute to the development of their values, give students the opportunity to make decisions, and encourage them to cooperate (Colnerud, 2006; Halstead and Taylor, 2000). Al-hooli and Al-shammari (2009) on the other found that some teachers are more effective than others in teaching and guiding children to moral values. The observed data also suggested that teachers frequently do not seem to have a wide variety of pedagogical strategies at their disposal for addressing moral values. In short, teachers have different preferences of the methods of implementing values, during which they consider students level and the type of value to be deliver as this may help them to choose the optimal method.

3.4 The Importance of Including Values in School Curriculum

Values are a broad concept that includes fundamental beliefs and principles (Halstead & Taylor, 2000). Values also relates to other fields such as values education, moral education, and citizenship education (Taylor, 1994). The tendency to address the concept of values in educational research has been steadily increasing, as well the number of studies in the literature on values education in various disciplines (Bills & Husbands, 2005; Lovat & Clement, 2008; Thomson & Bernhardt, 2010; Webster, 2010; Moosmayer & Siems, 2012; Law, 2013; Thornberg & Oğuz, 2013; Sundström & Wolming, 2014; Choo, 2015). It is commonly believed that even though the technologies we employ change from century to century, humans will always need established values to be understood (Tonga. 2016). Gökçe (2021) added that it is not possible to establish common norms and standards of behaviour in society without a shared set of values. As previously mentioned in the definitions of the term ‘values’ that people need values to be able to perceive each other’s acts and behaviours. Besides, several scholars such as Durkheim and Weber (as cited in Gutterman, 2010), Schwartz, 2012 and Tuulik et al. (2016) have underlined the relevance of values in society, values are needed in order to explain personal and social transformations, which also could explain why educators agree that addressing the issues that undermine social order and disrupt societal peace can be

accomplished through effective values teaching (Deveci & Selanik Ay, 2009). Furthermore, values will help humans to stand against negative social and world changes as nowadays values such as capitalism, individualism, and competitiveness dominate the values that used to support social unity and cooperation (Ünal 2002, 2006, 2011, and 2016). For example, previously people used to care more about group-interest and society-interest, but the challenges introduced by the 21st century made people selfish and egoistic, which means they only care about their self-interest, their success without considering others or the general welfare of the public or the society. Some of these challenges highlighted by Holden (2000) who said that educators and politicians view poverty, unemployment, violence, racism, and gender inequality to be key concerns and challenges of the 21st century. Gökçe (2021) added that due to modernization, economic and technological developments, a competitive environment among countries in the global world over time has been increased. Moreover, social issues, aggression, intolerance, and bad behaviours have an impact on the children. Values can also change in accordance with societal changes and can reflect societal changes (Gutterman, 2010; Rokeach, 2008; Schwartz, 2012; Tuulik et al., 2016). Obviously, what was believed in 20th century is no longer nowadays and this will definitely affect the shared and common values. To summarize the discussion above, it is of paramount importance that values should be part of the schools' curriculum regarding the role values play in educating the students and eradicate bad behaviours in society.

The schools play a critical role in promoting values and ensuring that the acquired values continue to exist (Halstead, 2005). This means that school helps the students to maintain the values that were acquired at home. Gökçe (2021) confirmed that schools provide a moral environment in which the shared values and beliefs of the society are delivered to students. Thus, schools are one of society's most powerful agents for sustaining its values. For centuries, authorities have regarded education as a valuable tool for embedding and perceiving behaviours and values in future generations (Gökçe, 2021). Authority and Governments use schools as a mean to not only teach and educate but also to embed the national values (Gökçe, 2021). Indeed, education is a process that the state controls through the curriculum in order to sustain its social control system (Ünal 2005, 2013). Accordingly, Authorities intended values could be seen in hidden curricular activities; images and quotations of historical heroes, for example, these are associated with national values. In nutshell, throughout history, schools have played a vital role in transferring society's common values to future generations (Gökçe, 2021), this relatable to the Algerian case; the curriculum reform of 2016-2017 the government believes that national identity, national conscience, citizenship and openness to the world are significant values that should be enacted in schools so that every student will maintain them (Ministry of National Education, 2016).

Teachers on the other hand have crucial role in teaching and promoting values. Teachers are “treasure troves of values” (Brady, 2011; Lashley & Barron, 2006; Shein & Chiou, 2011). In other words, teachers are the source of values, which means students got their values from them in the first place; they are both a reflection of today's society and the shapers of the next generation, as they represent a region's current cultural value (Gökçe, 2021). Consequently, students regard teachers as role models because they bring a variety of professional and personal values to the classroom. As a result, teachers have a significant potential to deliver their values to children, particularly through the school's informal curriculum (Gökçe, 2021). Hidden curriculum as opposed to taught curriculum; students are not directly imposed to

specific information, but they can indirectly get a lot from teacher's behaviour, speech, attitude, the way the classroom is decorated, or the picture drawn at the school's walls as previously explained.

3.5 Teachers Perspectives about Values

Since the current study focuses on teachers' perspectives on values, some studies that have similar focus were reviewed. Gökçe (2021) conducted a study to explore teachers' perspectives on what values should teachers have, what values should be maintained by the school principals and what values should be transferred to the students at school. This study was conducted with 263 preservice teachers from different fields where a questionnaire was handed to them as the researcher believes that the questionnaire is more relevant to reach the participants' beliefs about the essential values of education without any social desirability bias (Bhattacharjee, 2012). As a way of exploring the teachers' subconscious values as well as eliminate the social desirability mistake that might occur because of the existence of others in the classroom, thereby the teachers were asked to immediately write the first five values that came to their minds. The findings suggested that values the teachers must have are, virtue, sympathy, equality, affection and respect. The findings are in accordance with Schwartz (2006) cultural orientation structure. According to Schwartz's classification, these values are associated with egalitarian orientation which regards others as morally equal and work voluntarily to build productive relationships.

Teachers also believe that the main five values that School Principals should have, virtue, equality, justice, sympathy, and discipline. According to Gökçe (2021) the results are in line with the structure of the cultural dimensions of Schwartz (2006) egalitarianism orientation. In addition, the five core values that students should acquire at schools are virtue, respect, affection, conformity, and sympathy, again these set of values are also in line with the egalitarianism orientation. The findings indicate that the teachers expect students, to maintain high-level egalitarian values and low-level hierarchical values in schools. Furthermore, these values that the teachers support the students to acquire are classified as cultural, professional, and moral values.

In the Algerian context, stakeholders are expecting teachers to deliver national core values through the second-generation curriculum, these values as previously mentioned are, national identity, conscience, citizenship, and openness to the world (The Orientation Law, Ministry of National Education, 2016). These set of values that are mentioned in the policy documents are more aligned with Hofstede (1989) model, which considers values as national typology.

Karabacak (2021) conducted research on examining values education from teachers' perspectives in Turkey. Among the aims of this study was to investigate how values education should be delivered to students. Should it be an 'independent values education course, or should it be interspersed among the contents of certain suitable adjacent subjects?' (p.272). This study is qualitative and was conducted in a case study, this model or approach used in methodology to allow deep investigation and description of how a system or phenomenon works through collecting different data (Merriam, 2013). Besides, purposive sampling of 36 teachers from nine primary schools were chosen for the study, they should have at least 10-year teaching experience. A semi-structured interview tool was used to gather the data. Deep examination of the literature studies, consulting the views of three experts in the field and pilot interview followed by the researcher for the aim of designing the interview questions as well as ensuring

the format, content, validity, lucidity, and comprehensibility. For the data analysis, the researcher followed Marshall and Rossman's (2011) seven steps; first, data obtained then transferring the audio-recorded to written forms using NVIVO 12. Second, interviews were read several times to confirm their accuracy. The following step was to code and examine the interviews using inductive analysis. Next, generating independent codes by the researcher and three other experts separately. Defining themes and subthemes from the findings. After that, data was interpreted, explained and described. Finally, after interpreting the findings a conclusion presented.

Karabacak (2021) study revealed that most teachers believe that values should be included in all subjects of the curriculum as a certain way to increase respect of values. Limited number of teachers see that it better for values to be integrated with the Religion and Ethics class, those teachers believe that values are 'faith-based' and thus should be more of a religious course. Another limited number of teachers claim that values should be better taught separately as a 'Values Education lesson or as a school culture', supporters of this view believed that values are not only in religion or culture, 'value is life itself' (p.277). Another viewpoint believe that values should be given as Turkish lesson. Other findings of this study also suggested that the values the teachers emphasized such as respect for human rights, equality, freedom, peace, justice, and democracy are the primary values that should be maintained by the students. This study obtained very interesting data. However, it would be worthwhile to include how teachers would want to enact or deliver these values.

3.6 Issues Effecting Values Implementation

It is important to look at the potential issues, limitations or challenges that may result from introducing values in the school curriculum. Among the reported issues in the literature, a concern raised by the parents about the fact that some teachers fail to be role model and fail to represent good behaviour consequently even if the values are taught explicitly, the students will not maintain them (Maphalala and Mpofu 2018). Most of these parents indicated that some teachers are known to drink, share cigarettes and even engage in sexual relations with learners. These of course considered inappropriate in the South African culture and society. This can be the case in other schools and in other countries, this simply means that sometimes the school is not a safe and adequate place to teach values that the students are supposed to acquire to become a better person and an effective citizen in society thus it is a challenge that hinders the values to be taught in the schools. This is interesting point; however, it is worth mentioning that the context matters, and this could differ from one context to another. In other words, what might be seen as inappropriate or taboo in some cultures, may not necessary be in others. For example, drinking alcohol is not considered as inappropriate act in the UK thus a teacher who drink alcohol does not failed to represent a good model for his students. However, in Algeria drinking alcohol is considered as a heinous or a shameful act, thus a teacher who drinks alcohol will fail to represent a good model for the students.

Another widely debated challenge in the existing literature is whose role is to foster and promote values; is it family (parents) or school (teachers). Many studies informed this debate (Solomons and Fataar, 2011; Powell's, 2010; Tonga, 2016; Maphalala and Mpofu, 2018). Parents believe that teachers are best to be role models and foster values (Powell's, 2010) because children spend most of their time at the school (Maphalala and Mpofu, 2018). Teachers on the other hand, believe that students commit some behavioural mistakes because some

values were not fostered at home; the ultimate responsibility to develop these values lies with parents (Tonga, 2016). Or in fact, it can be a shared responsibility between teachers and parents (Tonga, 2016). This partnership is crucial as both of them have critical role to play (Solomons and Fataar, 2011), because the values-learning process begun informally at home and carried out formally in schools (Yazıcı, 2006). Besides, the interaction between schools, families, and society may offer a variety of chances for promoting values such as personal growth, democratic involvement, and economic development (Aspin, 2007).

The contribution the family has in the process of promoting values is perceived either a positive contribution or an issue that negatively interfere the schools' role of transferring values. For some, family is considered as the starting point of values education, it is the foundation of all upbringings and where an individual's educational journey begins (Tonga, 2016). For the first time, children witness and learn how to speak and share feelings in the social environment of the family (Tonga, 2016). Based on this, each individual is the result or the product of his or her surroundings and environment (Duru, 1975). In the other hand, for some others this was perceived as an issue that effect the effective values teaching within the school curriculum as children learn in comparable ways and what they learn differs from one family to another due to each family's distinct worldview and value system (Bozkurt, 2010). The values preferences for the schools and families can result in a conflict between the two as have been reported in the literature; sometimes families do not support the values being fostered in the schools, also there is an issue in transferring these values into behaviour (Karabacak and Nermin, 2021). Families sometimes consider those teachers' training programmes to be inadequate (Aktepe et al., 2020; Çelik, 2020), this is in line with what has been revealed in the study of Maphalala and Mpofu (2018) concerning the fact that some families are concerned about the school not being a safe place for teaching values or that some teachers fail to be role model of good values for their children.

It is important to mention that individual education is greatly influenced by both the family and the school. Cooperation between family and school is regarded as critical in students' academic, social, and personal development (Kocabaş, 2006). In short, we cannot restrict or confine this role one part and disregard others who might have same important role to play. In my opinion, teachers, school principals, society as well as families have a crucial and critical role in promoting values. Thereby, policymakers when introducing the values in the curriculum, they have to carefully consider the different backgrounds the students belong to, especially in multicultural or mixed-origin society like Algeria. Algeria for example has different ethnic groups, such as Arab, Amazigh, Shawiya... In this case, the values that should be taught in the schools have to boost their unity and should not focus on what could result in any kind of discriminations or quarrels.

Another factor that can affect or influence the process of promoting values is when teachers' personal beliefs, values, principles and preferences interfere in how to teach and what to teach because their decisions and choices are a reflection of their values (Harland & Pickering, 2011). Particularly if the values introduced in the curriculum contradict with the teachers' values because somebody's values are reflected on their daily activities, attitudes, and behaviours. Thus, examining preservice teachers' views is important because they carry existing values that may influence the future value development of society (Gökçe, 2021). Furthermore, throughout preservice education, their professional values, and beliefs, which they have acquired since childhood, are strengthened, or changed (Lortie, 2002; Zeichner and Gore, 1990). This claim

highlighted the importance of teachers training programme where the teachers believes, and values will be reviewed. Richardson (2003) added that during preservice teaching programme, changes in teachers' beliefs are critical. The preservice teachers begin to form their professional values during their preservice education (Voinea and Palaşan, 2014). In other words, teachers training programme help novice teachers to build their teaching and professional values.

3.7 Teachers Resistance

Due to similar potential issues or difficulties that might result from introducing values to school curriculum or other similar policies, teachers may resort to resistance. The policy of introducing values to school's curriculum might be introduced through a reform for instance, in Algeria the core values of identity, national conscience, citizenship and openness to the world were introduced through a reform called the Second-Generation curriculum (Bouhafs, 2017; Ministry of National Education, 2016) as it is mentioned in the policy documents. It is likely that for each curriculum reform or policy, to find two opposing stands of those who are resilience to this change and those who resist it.

Resistance on the part of teachers usually refers to their desire to maintain existing practices (former curriculum) despite the changes that they deem undesirable and troubling (Giles, 2006). The classical literature considers teacher resistance as a sign of a policy or a reform failure (Zimmerman, 2006). The resistor on the other hand might have a psychological incapacity of willing to change (Achinstein and Ogawa, 2006). In other words, sometimes teachers do not support the changes and reforms introduced by policy makers, their reaction of refusing these policies called resistance. It is important to highlight this as the current study examined teachers' perspectives and experiences toward a policy of embedding core values in Middle School curriculum.

The Literature views teachers' resistance as either a positive rection or an issue to be solved. Some research considers resistors as traditional, passive, they lack professional knowledge, conventional, stubborn and their students are not interested in their way of teaching ((Van Veen, 2005). Therefore, their resistance is regarded as conservative and a problem to be solved (Rosenholtz, 1989). Other studies support teachers' resistance (Gitlin and Margonis, 1995), as it has positive rational (Achinstein and Ogawa, 2006; Giles, 2006; Van Veen et al., 2005). Because the resistance act enables teachers to reject the imposed policies and programmes, or other instructions that contradict with their teaching' principles and believes. In fact, both stances seem to have valid arguments, sometimes the reform contradict with what teachers believe is the best for their students, particularly teachers are the ones who best know their students, in term of their level, capacities and learning. However, teachers need to know that even if the actual curriculum is good, yet it is important to introduce new policies that help the students and the educational system to be up to date with all aspects introduced in the society and the world.

There are reasons of why some teachers resist change as have been documented in the literature. Among them, when a reform fails to set a clear reason and aims of the change (Greenberg & Baron, 2000) as this affect teachers' willingness to support and accept the change (Greenberg & Baron, 2000). In addition, the experience of former failure or unsuccessful reform may develop wary for teachers to accept any further attempt for a new reform (Greenberg & Baron, 2000). Furthermore, there is an anxiety of the unknown as teachers have more self-confidence when maintaining familiar tasks, familiar methods and teaching familiar content (Fullan, 2001;

Greenberg & Baron, 2000). Moreover, when the school is not a supportive and safe environment for the change, teachers are not ready to embrace any new introduced practices and it is likely that teachers develop defensive reaction and maintain their old practices (Goleman, Boyatzis, & McKee, 2002). Zimmerman (2006) stated that denial could be another reason for resistance, he added that denial is a feeling or behaviour that teachers have at the beginning of the reform process. It is more of an impedance and rejection.

On the other hand, there are also several ways to overcome resistance. Initially to overcome a resistance it is important to find out who is resisting change and why (Duke, 2004) which requires from the principals to consider teachers' perspectives and figure out how teachers' attitudes, social norms and behaviour fit in the school context (Kennedy and Kennedy, 1996). One of the issues that causes resistance is that teachers are not part of the decision making even though they best know the students and their needs (Short and Greer, 2002). This can be resolved through providing opportunities for teachers to participate in the decision making (Zimmerman, 2006).

The following is teachers' resistance experience in Algeria and the United Arab Emirates. Troudi and Alwan (2010) conducted qualitative interpretive research about female teachers' feelings during curriculum change in the United Arab Emirates, 16 Arab female secondary school teachers of English participated in this study. Two rounds semi-structured interview along with reviewing curriculum documents and other related materials were used to collect data. The study revealed the fact that teachers are excluded from curriculum design and development, effect teachers negatively as their role is limited. One of the participants in this study stated, 'I am just the teacher', this reflect the authoritative top-down policy, which made teachers resist the policy instructions. Some others claim that introducing a new reform could be challenging for teachers. Thus, they prefer proceeding with the old strategy. The findings also suggested that teachers resort tacit resistance towards the change, where they express extreme dissatisfaction with the new curriculum as whole. However, Troudi and Alwan (2010) also stated that the teachers in the other hand emphasize the disadvantages or faults in the materials, more than focusing on other positive aspects. They noticed that some teachers may criticise the teacher's book without even consulting it as a way to justify why they retain their old technique and strategies. At the end, the study recommended considering teachers voice in curriculum reform and development as this will effectively 'eliminate negative psychological effects such as marginalisation and powerlessness' (p. 107). In short, teachers may resist change and they have the right to, but this does not always mean that the policy is faulty; their resistance can reflect their dereliction. In this case, the teachers were not opened to change without being familiar about many aspects of this change.

Bouhania (2020) conducted research on the perspectives of EFL secondary school teachers toward competency-based approach. Twenty teachers from eight secondary schools in southwest of Algeria participated in this study, the researcher used the questionnaires to collect data. According to Bouhania (2020), since 2003 (when the CBA was first introduced) two opposing tendencies emerged among teachers, pupils, syndicate, and parents. Those who were resilient to this policy and supported the educational system and pedagogical reforms and those who were resistant to it. The findings of his study revealed that 61.5% of teachers believe that the content of the book is not adequate for the students' level, do not ease the reading and comprehension task, is also unclear in term of instructions and the content do not reflect the students' socio-cultural context. 75% of teachers are convinced that the students are still unable

to face real-life situations whether inside or outside the class, which means the reform fail to address this and thus, the aim was not achieved. The factor of ‘time’ in teaching within CBLT (competency-based language teaching) in the Algerian schools. 70% of teachers see that the time is not respected, 65% said the timing is not procedural, 90% not practical and 60% not helpful. The last questions have obvious and clear-cut answers that the teachers lacked any ICT technology training.

3.8 Conclusion

This chapter dealt with the key terms that informed this research, it also discussed a list of studies conducted in the same area and link between them. This chapter presented how values are introduced in curriculum and how they are either taught or imbedded in the curriculum, what methods are used in this process and how teachers perceive and enact them. The chapter also discussed some potential issues that have been reported in the literature, which resulted from introducing or teaching the values as part of the school curriculum, at the end it raised a discussion about a phenomenon of teachers’ resistance, which may result from teachers’ rejection of a change or dissatisfaction of a new introduced policies or reforms. Based on this, the literature review chapter framed the path that the study followed, as it helped the researcher to gain familiarity with the current knowledge and literature in the chosen field. Therefore, this helped in identify the boundaries and limitations of this field as well as identifying the gap in the research. Thus this gap was the focus of the current study.

Chapter Four

Research Methodology

Introduction

In this chapter, a detailed and comprehensive description of the research methodology is presented. The study followed a qualitative approach with a mixed methods design of data collection tools that examines the EFL Middle School teachers' perspectives and experience in implementing the core values that were introduced across the Second-Generation curriculum. Initially in this chapter, the qualitative research design is described, the research paradigm that frame the study is tackled. Later in this chapter, the methodology or the research strategy is discussed. The tools of data collection chosen to gather primary data were online survey and semi-structured interviews. The data resulted from the online questionnaire was analysed descriptively. On the other hand, the thematic analysis and NVIVO software were used for the analysis of the data gathered through interviews. The last part of this chapter considers concerns of validity, trustworthiness, and reliability of data, besides other ethical issues of confidentiality and anonymity. The processes of piloting the study and the data collection are also discussed. The resulted knowledge and outcome of this chapter will answer the research questions.

4.1 The Qualitative Methodology Model:

Figure 1: Framework for Design adapted from Creswell (2018)

This research design adopted from Creswell (2018) as a research model to be followed, the design helped me to organize the work structure, as with getting a depth and width understanding of the different milestones that I should hit during the research study. Creswell (2018) highly recommends the use of a framework to provide guidance for all stages of the

research, considering three main elements: the type of assumptions, which the researcher must decide on before starting the fieldwork, the procedures of the project called strategies of inquiry. The techniques and the tools of data collection, data analysis and the writings, which called methods. This model can be followed in any research and by either qualitative, quantitative, or mixed method approach. As per the current study, the researcher had clear idea about the topic and the aim of the study, after developing research questions, the task was to identify the roots of the research on philosophical positions that helped in framing the study. The nature of knowledge to be studied (ontology) and what is to be studied (epistemology) are called the paradigm of the study. Besides, how this knowledge is going to be studied is the called methodology. In addition, these philosophical assumptions, and the aim of the study, help the researcher to identify the research approach (qualitative), the research method (mixed methods) as well as the tools of data collection (online survey and semi-structured interviews). And finally, the tools and techniques considered in analysing the data.

4.2 Philosophical Underpinnings: Social Constructivism/Interpretivism

Defining the paradigm of the study is crucial as it contains philosophical assumptions that are used as lens to the world (Mertens, 2010). The paradigm must be determined at the early stage of the methodology chapter (Grix, 2019). Educational research has identified four major research paradigms: post-positivism, constructivism, transformative, and pragmatism (Mertens, 2010). The philosophical assumptions are ontology (a type of social reality), epistemology (the relationship between the nature of knowledge, the reality of the researcher and the target), axiology (the nature of ethics), and methodology (how to obtain results) (Patton, 2002).

My research aimed at examining EFL teachers' perceptions and their experiences in engaging with the core values within the Middle School curriculum. The study focused on human beings and their interaction with external world in social life where their experience is taking place (Gray, 2009) which means that meaning and knowledge are generated and constructed by participants socially. Based on the research questions and the aim of the study, the study was framed by social constructivism and interpretivism, as I believe that reality or knowledge is socially constructed and that we come to know about this reality through our contacts with others. In addition, people construct knowledge and reality; this means there are multiple realities and meaning, which also means that it is up to the context (social context) to define the meaning. Furthermore, people have different interpretations of meaning and this supports the use of the interpretivism approach. The social constructivism paradigm examines the problem (what is to be studied) from participants' perspectives where the meaning is based on the community and the knowledge is socially constructed or bounded. In other words, the aim is to rely on the participants' perspectives as the focus of the study (Creswell, 2014). Thus, the knowledge should be socially constructed by the participants of this study, and the researcher's understanding of reality should be derived from the individual who experienced it (Schwandt, 2000). In other words, the individuals or the participants seek to develop meaning of their social lives and the researcher has to examine the situation through the different views of the individuals involved in the study (participants), to get their understanding of the situation, to explore how they make sense of their lived experiences and to focus on interactions, contexts and environments (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018).

This approach of social constructivism is viewed as equated with interpretivism as they both emphasise the social world is interpreted and perceived by the participants (Robson and McCartan, 2016). It is not possible to tackle ontology without considering epistemology, as they are inseparable (Grix, 2002). In other words, the integration of ontology and epistemology is essential because our understanding of reality is inherently linked to how we perceive and interpret it. Without considering the epistemological aspects of how knowledge is acquired and validated, our ontological inquiries may lack a solid foundation. Similarly, exploring ontology without acknowledging the ways in which knowledge shapes our understanding can lead to incomplete or biased interpretations of reality. Hammond and Wellington (2013) explained that there is more than one way to express the meaning of constructivism, but in general, it is about people as “meaning makers” which means in this world where we live, people seek meaning for things around us. They also argued that ‘constructivism approach is sometimes referred to as interpretive/interpretivist approach which indicate a focus on how a social world is interpreted by those involved in it (Burr 2003 and Gergen 2009). Robson and McCartan (2016) believe that usually researchers that adopt the perspective approach, apply qualitative methods where the rationale usually is to understand the situation as far as participants are concerned. In methodology, the interpretivism position support the use of ‘smaller-scale casing, exploratory approach, interview, and the language used is always ‘explore concepts, unsettle ideas, engage with social actors, negotiate understanding’ (Hammond and Wellington, 2013, p.90). Social constructivism and interpretivism are ‘typically seen as an approach to qualitative research’ (Creswell and Creswell, 2018, p.7).

4.3 Strategy of Inquiry

4.3.1 Qualitative Approach

The current study is qualitative in nature with the use of mixed methods design for data collection through online survey and semi-structured interviews. This approach is ideal for the research aim which is understanding the Algerian EFL Middle School teachers’ perspectives on the core values that were introduced by policymakers to be taught through school curriculum. In addition, exploring the teachers experience of the implementation of these core values. Thus, the study is seeking, perspectives, opinions, emotions, and different experiences each teacher had when implementing these core values underpinning the SGC curriculum. These were gathered through deep discussion around the phenomenon using semi-structured interviews, the data later on were analysed, described, reported and interpreted qualitatively with a support of some numerical data that were gathered through the online survey.

Before defining the qualitative approach and its importance for the current study, it is crucial to highlight the difference between methodology and methods. Opie (2007) recommended:

Researchers should make their position clear in terms of the methodologies and methods they use in accordance with their ontological positions, as failing to do so makes them vulnerable to criticisms of unacknowledged bias.

(p.21).

The researcher needs to make clear where his research is standing in term of methodology and methods as this will increase the credibility of the research and the research findings. Methodology and methods are two distinct concepts in research, each plays a crucial role in the research process (Opie, 2007). Opie (2007) added, the key differences between methodology and methods are that methodology refers to the overarching theoretical framework and principles that guide the research process. Also, it involves the systematic study of methods, tools, and techniques used in the research study. Whereas methods refer to the specific techniques, procedures, and tools employed to gather and analyse data in a research study. In other words, methods are the practical steps taken to collect, measure, and interpret data. Furthermore, methodology focuses on the rationale behind the selection of specific research methods, the overall research design, and the philosophical underpinnings that shape the research approach (Sunder, 2016). In this sense, methodology encompasses the overall strategy of how research is conducted, including the theoretical perspective, research design, data collection methods, data analysis techniques, and interpretation of results (Sunder, 2016).

On the other hand, methods focus on the practical aspects of data collection, such as surveys, interviews, experiments, observations, and statistical analysis techniques (Sunder, 2016).

In a nutshell, methodology provides the theoretical and conceptual framework that guides the research process, while methods are the specific tools and techniques used to implement that framework and collect data. Methodology sets the overall direction and approach of the research, while methods are the practical means through which data is gathered, analysed, and interpreted (Cohen et al 2007). Understanding the distinction between methodology and methods is essential for researchers to design and conduct rigorous and systematic research studies. In this sense, a qualitative approach will be a typical example of a “methodological approach” that brings together mixed methods in order to achieve the research objective of this study. A study in which mixed methods design is used, it involves integrating both quantitative and qualitative techniques within the same framework to leverage the strengths of each approach (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004). This demonstrates how the methodology shapes the overall research design. The methods within the mixed methods approach would include the actual data collection tools and analytical procedures used for both quantitative and qualitative data (Levitt, Bamberg, and Creswell, 2018).

Embarking on the concept of ‘qualitative research approach’. According to Newby (2010) qualitative research is an approach to research used to understand social phenomena from the

point of view and the perspective of the participants or in other words those included in the study. It focuses on understanding the meanings, experiences, and perspectives of individuals or groups, it is typically used to collect rich, in-depth data, allowing researchers to search on complex issues and gain insights into the subjective experiences of participants (Newby, 2010). Similarly expressed by Saha (2022), qualitative research is particularly useful when the goal is to gain insights into individuals' experiences, perceptions, and behaviours, providing a rich and detailed understanding of the studied phenomenon.

The research studies focusing on the lived experience of people are well-suited for qualitative approach which tend to seek meanings that people develop on the events, processes, and structures of their lives: their perceptions, assumptions, prejudgments, presuppositions (Van Manen, 1977). Gururajan and Hafeez-Baig (2014) also agreed that qualitative research is often used in social sciences, healthcare, and management studies, where a deeper understanding of human behaviour, attitudes, and motivations is essential. In this sense, qualitative approach is useful for studies aiming at examining social phenomena, assessing human behaviour, and offering thorough descriptions of experiences and perspectives. It is common for researchers to use qualitative as well as quantitative approaches to create a mixed methods study based on questions or research hypotheses (Newby, 2010). Researchers who implement qualitative approach believe that there is not a single truth, therefore “people can subscribe to different views”, also in studies using this approach, the finding or data “may not necessarily take the form of numerical data” but would value the idea that relationships, personalities, feelings, and every other aspect of our existence and self-expression are valid sources of knowledge that can be utilized to comprehend the world (Newby, 2010, p.46).

While qualitative research is valuable for its ability to capture the complexity and context of a phenomenon, it is important to acknowledge its limitations. Qualitative research may be criticized for its subjectivity, potential for researcher bias, and challenges in generalizability. However, when used appropriately and rigorously, qualitative research can provide valuable insights that complement quantitative findings and contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of a research topic (Neergaard, Olesen, and Andersen, 2009). To address the limitation of the qualitative research approach, researchers can utilize this approach along with mixed methods which integrates both qualitative and quantitative methods as believed by Gelo, Braakmann, and Benetka (2008). They declared that the integration allows researchers to capitalize on the strengths of each method to compensate for the weaknesses of the other, leading to a more comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the research topic (Gelo,

Braakmann, and Benetka, 2008). In other words, researchers can surmount the limitations of the qualitative research approach by incorporating mixed methods as it empowers researchers to enhance the rigor, depth, and inclusivity of their qualitative studies, ultimately yielding more robust and insightful research outcomes.

For this sense, the qualitative approach is suitable for this study as it helped me to achieve the aim of the study which is providing thorough description and interpretation of the experience of the Algerian EFL Middle School teachers in perceiving and implementing the core values within the school curriculum.

4.3.2 Sequential Explanatory Mixed Method design

Although the current study is qualitative, it used the mixed methods design at the level of the tools used to gather data. The use of mixed methods for the current study allowed me to combine the strengths of both quantitative and qualitative methods and benefit from the distinct characteristics of each tool. Gathering numerical data through using online survey about the teachers' understanding of the core values introduced through the SGC reform and their perspectives on teaching these values through curriculum of English language in the classroom. Then using interviews to incorporate the qualitative data to better understand quantitative findings (Creswell and Plano-Clark, 2017).

The initial data resulted from the online survey helped me in informing the design of the semi-structured interviews by identifying initial themes, generating initial understanding of teachers' perspectives of the SGC, core values and their experience in enacting values within the curriculum. These insights guided the formulation of other questions to be included in the semi-structured interviews in order to be discussed deeply and widely during the interviews, for an in-depth understanding of the teachers' experience. The answers of the online survey gave me a sense on the questions clarity, relevance, and comprehensiveness which was valuable in enhancing the interviews' effectiveness in capturing the desired information. Thus, this effectively captured the perspectives, experiences, and feedback of participants, ultimately enhancing the quality and relevance of the data collected for the research study.

Starting with the online survey helped me in comparing online survey findings with the draft of the semi-structured interviews to ensure that the questions align with the points raised in the questionnaire as participants were provided with a space after each section to elaborate with their answers or for any additional comments and make sure that these were all covered during interviews. It helped in refining and validating the content and the structure of the interviews

such as the sequence of questions and the overall flow, The awareness developed through the answers provided in the online survey helped me to approach the interviews' questions sensitively and ethically, ensuring participant comfort and willingness to provide honest responses.

Following Creswell (2003) sequential explanatory mixed method design model, I started the process of data collection by using a quantitative method which is the online survey, followed by a qualitative tool of semi-structured interviews. Creswell's (2003) model helped me in combining both quantitative and qualitative methods in a sequential manner. It enabled gaining a comprehensive understanding of the studied phenomena through using multiple sources of data. The explanatory research design allowed for a more in-depth exploration of research questions as well as providing a richer interpretation of the findings.

Figure 02: Creswell (2003) Sequential Explanatory Mixed Method Design.

Creswell's sequential explanatory mixed method design is a research approach that involves collecting and analysing quantitative data first, followed by collecting and analysing qualitative data to provide a comprehensive understanding of the research question (Ivankova, Creswell and Stick, 2006). This design allows researchers to combine the strengths of both quantitative and qualitative methods, enhancing the depth and breadth of the study findings (Grattan, 2023). The sequential nature of this design ensures that the qualitative phase builds upon the results of the quantitative phase, providing explanations and insights that go beyond what each method can achieve individually (Jones, Mple and Mokri, 2013).

Researchers adopting this approach typically start with quantitative data collection and analysis to identify patterns or relationships, followed by qualitative data collection to explore the underlying reasons or mechanisms behind these patterns (Bayron, 2023). By integrating both types of data in a sequential manner, researchers can offer a more robust interpretation of the research findings (Meek, Redstone and Moghaddam, 2020). This model is particularly valuable in fields such as education, psychology, and medicine, where a comprehensive understanding of complex phenomena is essential (Scott, Nerminathan and Alexander, 2015). The Creswell (2003) sequential explanatory mixed method design offers a systematic and rigorous way to

conduct research by combining quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis in a sequential manner. This approach enhances the validity and reliability of research findings by providing a more holistic understanding of the research topic.

Using this design in data collection offers several benefits to researchers. First, by integrating both quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis within a single study, researchers can gain a more comprehensive understanding of the research problem (Ivankova, Creswell and Stick, 2006). This approach allows researchers to confirm the findings of one phase with another, thereby enhancing the reliability and validity of the results (Rafiq, Ameen and Jabeen, 2018). Additionally, the mixed methods design provides an opportunity to collect detailed and comprehensive qualitative data to support quantitative findings, contributing to a more robust interpretation of the study outcomes (Alhassan and Agyei, 2020).

Furthermore, the mixed methods design enables researchers to analyse data in a broad manner, as it allows for the collection of both qualitative and quantitative information to answer the research question effectively (Karp and Gallagher, 2019). This approach also enhances the rigor of investigations by incorporating instrument-building, triangulation, and data transformation models, adding depth and validity to the research process (Creswell, 2004). Moreover, the integration of qualitative and quantitative analyses throughout the study progression allows researchers to observe trends and patterns in the data, leading to richer insights and a more nuanced understanding of the research topic (Walker and Boyer, 2018). The use of mixed methods design in data collection empowers researchers to gather a more holistic view of the research problem, enhance the reliability and validity of findings, collect comprehensive qualitative data to support quantitative results, analyse data broadly, and improve the rigor of investigations through various methodological frameworks.

4.3.3 Pilot Study

My study received ethical approval from the Ethics Committee of the School of Education and Social Sciences at the University of the West of Scotland. The following step was to pilot the study, the aim was initially to test out the tools of data collection and to address the internal validity of the study. It is believed by Oppenheim (1992) and Morrison (1993), that piloting a research study has several functions, principally to increase the reliability, validity, and practicability of the data collection tools. To assess the chosen method for data collection and examining the validity of the study content before applying it for the fieldwork. I trailed the survey with some of my Algerian PhD colleagues and interviewed others from the same

population. I have chosen this specific population as they are familiar with the Algerian education system, they were in middle schools before, during their schooling, they experienced some of the reforms adopted to the system. In addition, some of them are to be teachers and lecturers in future, so they are more likely to reflect on my questions and ideas aiming to confirm the validity and reliability of the chosen tool (Silverman, 2014). The pilot study was successfully conducted and resulted in the refining the tools of data collection. Both the online survey and the semi-structured interview were trialled and piloted. The pre-test study is often implemented on small numbers of the target sample also the participants of the pilot study should not be among those of the main study, as such participants would be already engaged in the research study and this would affect their behaviours, responses and the data collected from them (Haralambos and Holborn, 2008). The other crucial element covered was the recruitment of participants, as I was not sure how to successfully recruit the participants through social media platforms.

I contact the potential participants via Facebook, a forum where I have contact with most of my Algerian colleagues. Three Algerian PhD students, two of them are doing PhD at the University of the West of Scotland and the third one is doing PhD in China University. Five EFL Middle School Teachers (some of them were my colleagues at university and others were invited by my colleagues), a former trainer teacher and a Director of the National Centre of Research in Social and Cultural Anthropology whom I know from social media) were all included in the pilot study. The consent form (See Appendix 02) and the participants' information sheet (See Appendix 01) were also sent to the volunteers so that they could familiarise themselves with the study, understand their requirements in terms of participation and what they are signing for, formalize their consent as well. The same was planned for the participants of the main study. The other reason for providing the two forms was, to get feedback from the volunteers on whether the forms provided enough information about the study and the aim of the study, as well as to identify any other concerns that the pilot participants may have.

I shared the online survey with the six volunteers via Messenger (three EFL Middle School Teachers, three PhD researchers). One of the teachers was a friend of mine who after graduation started her job at a Middle School in Bechar/Algeria, and I asked her to invite her colleagues to take part. She approached about six but only two agreed to participate. I realised that recruiting participants is not as straightforward as I thought it would be, so I decided to limit

the number to these three and leave others who might be interested to contribute to the main study.

The interviews were conducted through WhatsApp and Messenger calls depending on what best suited each participant. Two EFL Middle School Teachers, a former trainer teacher and a Director of the National Centre of Research in Social and Cultural Anthropology were invited to take part in the interviews. I decided to include other types of participants (e.g. PhD researchers, trainer teachers) for the fact that they might view the interview questions from different angles, and this would help me to evaluate the tools from different perspectives. In other words, the Algerian PhD researchers are familiar with the methodology and methods related concerns, Moreover, they are familiar with the educational system in Algeria and thus they will reflect on the structure of the questionnaire, the question types, validity, reliability and practicability of the questionnaire, in addition to the content of the questionnaire.

Although the focus of the study is to explore EFL teachers' perspectives, it was helpful at this stage to explore other perspectives and insights from people who are considered experts in the field of education as well as research. The piloting of the semi-structured interviews with them were fruitful; they helped me to find out new and interesting information about the Second-Generation Curriculum and associated teaching processes. In addition to that, I could also reflect on how questions during interviews might be asked, what other elements to consider in the interviews and other important ideas to be included that are not already mentioned. The interviews with the EFL Middle School Teachers helped me to reflect on the wording of the question; and to decide on whether they were clear or ambiguous, easy or difficult, also the way they answer them For example, if I did not get an answer pertinent to the point I thought I was addressing in a question, I realise that there was an issue with either the way the question is worded or the participants' understanding of the question which may require changing the question (format, structure, wording) or followed the discussion by a supporting question to get a more full explanation in case of short answers being given. A checklist (see Appendix 05) was sent to the participants after the pilot study that contained eleven elements or factors: timing, readability (ambiguity/difficulty), clarity (content/meaning), validity, reliability, practicability, redundant/irrelevant items, attractiveness (interesting /boring), facts (brining something new does not exist in real-life) structure (too long/too short) and whether it contains any sensitive/ threatening/ intrusive/offensive Items. I adopted the idea from Wilson and McLean 1994, Verma and Mallick (1999), Krosnick and Presser (2010), Dillman et al. (2014), when they talked about the fifteen elements or characters that the piloting of the questionnaire

helps the researcher to achieve in the main study. These elements are, Clarity, validity, can operate the purpose of the research, eliminate ambiguity and difficulty in wording, readability for the target audience, type of the questions and format, feedback on response categories. Also, to identify omissions and redundant and irrelevant items. To gain feedback on leading questions, to gain feedback on the attractiveness and appearance of the questionnaire/ burden , to gain feedback on the layout, sectionalizing, numbering and itemization of the questionnaire, to check the time taken to complete the questionnaire, to check whether the questionnaire is too long or too short, too easy or too difficult, to identify how motivating/non motivating/ sensitive/ threatening/ intrusive/ offensive items might be and finally, to identify commonly misunderstood or non-completed items, to try out the coding/classification system for data analysis.

Accordingly, the participants were asked to evaluate the online survey and semi-structured interviews in light of the checklist provided. They were also asked to indicate how long it took them to answer the online survey. Participants also commented on the other elements by putting a tick. For example, if they considered the online survey and the semi-structured interview to be readable, they would tick both columns, or if only the online survey considered readable then they would tick only the column of the online survey. In the case of ambiguity or difficulty, they would write this along with mentioning the question number.

The pilot study was useful in finding out some potential problems. Kim (2011) states that the pilot study is an effective way to test the research instruments intended to be used in the study. The piloting helped me to, re-structure some questions from general to more specific and re-worded questions that were poorly worded. Two of the participants in the pilot study suggested to start both the online survey and the semi-structured interviews with introductory questions about the reform of the SGC, the core values; what are these core values and what is their definition. These questions work as warm-up to start the discussion and communicate openly during the interviews, the warm-up questions help the participants to brainstorm and generate their ideas which will lead to a productive and insightful interview. One of the participants, suggested to include questions about collaboration between the teachers and between the teachers and administration in instilling values as this may help to have insights and understand teachers experience in perceiving and enacting values outside the classroom but inside the school environment. Later on, these changes were applied to both tools and updated accordingly. These changes suggested some additional questions and rewording of some questions, also restructuring the order of the sections from general to specific (see Appendences

3 and 4). The changes did not affect the nature and the aim of the study. On the other hand, the pilot study also allowed me to focus on some issues that might influence the validity or the effectiveness of the study or the process of data collection such as, poor participants' response that might result from lack of understanding of the questions. The pilot also provided insights into any further questions that might result in further developing new ideas for the main study. Finally, it gave me a chance to verify the intended length of time for both the online survey and the semi-structured interview and whether my initial intentions were practical or not.

4.3.3 Data Collection Process and Tools

After applying the necessary changes resulted from the pilot of the study, I started searching for different online forums of the EFL Middle School teachers in Algeria for example, 'Middle School Teachers of English in Algeria, Middle School Teachers' circle, Middle school Teachers of Bejaia/Oran/Bechar (these are cities in Algeria). These forums are available in different social media platforms, mainly Facebook. After joining them I start sharing my online survey that was created in google form format, between one to two responses were received in a day. After reaching a considerable number of around 40 responses, I started having initial ideas of the data and I could reflect on some aspects that will require further discussion during the interviews. The feedback I obtained also resulted in editing the interview questions and submitting amendments request to the ethics committee to the School of Education and Social Sciences at UWS. I received an approval for the amendment request application after a week, I started approaching participants for the interviews in the same way i.e., advertising on different Facebook' groups about participants needed to take part in semi-structured interviews. Also, through sending emails or messaging in either WhatsApp or/and Messenger, in addition I asked my friends and colleagues to spread the word. When the participant agreed to take part, the informed consent and the information sheet were sent to them for the aim of familiarizing themselves of the purpose of the study, the regulations and guides of anonymity, data confidentiality, and the right to withdraw or withdraw any responses as well as to sign their consent for participation. The average of the interviews was between one hour and a half to two hours. The participants were given the right to go for a break or conduct the interview in two parts in different timing but most of them want to complete it in one go, there were just two cases that had bad internet connection, so we had to reschedule the interview.

4.3.3.1 Sampling Frame and Participants' Recruitment

This research project employed two methods of data collection that involved human-subject the online survey and the semi-structured interviews. I adopt the purposive sampling technique

in recruiting participants of both tools. The participants must be Algerian, Teacher of English, currently practice teaching in Middle School; the population will consider both genders as well as novice and experienced teachers, located in either urban or rural area, located in either north, south, east or west of Algeria. Some of them holding BA degree in didactics, other have MA degree and very few have PhD degree. In addition, their teaching experience varied from one year teaching experience to twenty-year of teaching experience. The online survey aimed at around sixty participants from all over Algeria, as opposed to the semi-structured interviews that was conducted with smaller sample of 16 participants. There is a difference between the population intended for a quantitative study and that is designed for a qualitative one. In quantitative research 'the larger the sample the better' (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018,p.203) as this helps not only in giving 'greater reliability' but also provides 'more sophisticated statistics to be used' (p.203). While the qualitative studies require fewer sample size. The sample size should not be selected from randomly, there should be a purpose behind the selection as recommended by Uprichard (2013) who states that the 'sample size' and sample error are 'meaningless' unless the researcher knows how and why they matter (p.7). There are factors that might affect the sample size; these are listed by Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018) for example: the cost – in terms of time, money, stress, administrative support, the number of researchers and resources' (p.204). This purposive selection was chosen because I believe that the chosen category best reflects the aim and the focus of the study also the sampling will provide rich and comprehensive data that can address and answer the research questions. In support of this Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018) say 'the quality of a piece of research stands or falls by the appropriateness of its methodology and instrumentation and by the suitability of the sampling strategy that has been adopted' (p.202). They added that 'Factors such as expense, time and accessibility frequently prevent researchers from gaining information from the whole population' (p.202).

4.3.3.2 Sampling strategies

In the current research, several strategies were planned to reach the potential population as well as the suitable sample size that serves the aim of this investigation and assuring the data saturation, which is a frequent concern in qualitative research (Fusch et al., 2015). The initial strategy was going home country (Algeria) and addressing Middle School Directors, asking them for access authorisation to the school as well as spreading the word among teachers who willing to volunteer in my research. This would include the provision of all the needed information about myself as a researcher, and the purpose of my investigation, how the

participants will be recruited (tools of data collection, interviews and handed questionnaire), how they can reach me (E-mail, phone number, social media), and deciding on interviews` time and location. However, the implementation of this strategy failed due to the pandemic and the closure of borders and schools in Algeria (2020-2021). Thereby, I went for the option of leading the process of data collection virtually. The alternative plan then was posting on Facebook groups that are created by Middle School Teachers of English language. This method deemed as an easier, time consuming, and more effective comparing to the traditional methods. According to Thornton et al. (2016) and Spahrkäs et al. (2021), there is dramatic increase in the number of research that use social media in data collection process especially the use of Facebook. This includes large range of domains such as medical, psychological and health research, and social sciences (Kosinski et al., 2015). I considered introducing myself, explaining the aim of my research while advertising on these groups. To guarantee the confidentiality of my participants` details and identity, I requested sending me a private message by the participants who were willing to participate. Once I have been texted, I provide the participants with my contact details either the formal means (personal and student mail, phone number), or informal means such as Instagram, WhatsApp, Viber and the other used platforms to maintain the contact with them. While waiting for responses via this process, I used other strategy, I approached my colleagues who are also PhD researchers in the UK and who were teachers at Middle Schools before coming to pursue their PhD studies in the UK. I requested them to invite their friends and colleagues to take part in my research. This was the most effective method I used, in which it able me to accelerate the progress of data collection duration. The last method I used is the snowball sampling, in which I requested the participants who I could reach to advertise for my research and spread the word among their teacher friends and colleagues. This strategy was fruitful as well. It enabled me to reach a wider range of population. According to Parker et al. (2019), snowball sampling is the most widespread method of recruitment in qualitative research. It is associated to networking and referral criterion, by which the researcher started with a small number of volunteers and asking them to recommend other people who have research requirement to participate and continuing in the same way. Snowball sampling method is one of the non-probabilistic samplings, in which the size or the frame of sample is not known or limited (Tansey, 2007). In the present investigation, the snowball sampling technique was supported by the use of FB. According to Dosek (2021), the use of FB enhances or reinforces snowball-sampling method, in which it helps accessing the hard-to-reach population. Dosek argued that FB could overcome the limitations of snowball sampling and permit to establish an initial key information about the targeted population. At

the end, the range of techniques and strategies I utilised enabled be to recruit sixty-four participants who answered the online survey and sixteen accepted to be interviewed for one-to-one hour and half.

Demographic overview of the online survey:

Gender		Duration of Teaching experience				Current location of teaching	
Male	Female	Year or less	1to 5 years	6to 10 years	More than 10 years	Urban	Rural
18	46	9	14	30	11	38	26

Table 05: Demographic Data of the Participants of the Online Survey.

Demographic overview of the semi-structured interviewed participants:

Pseudonym	Gender	Years of experience	Location of institution	Interview duration
T1	Female	7	Central part of Algeria	1h, 10mn
T2	Female	1	Eastern part of Algeria	1h, 5mn
T3	Female	5	Central part of Algeria	1h
T4	Female	5	Western part of Algeria	1h, 15mn
T5	Female	4	Western part of Algeria	1h, 5mn
T6	Female	2	Central part of Algeria	1h
T7	Male	8	Southern part of Algeria	1h, 20mn
T8	Male	20	Southern part of Algeria	1h, 10mn
T9	Female	28	Southern part of Algeria	1h, 30mn
T10	Male	20	Western part of Algeria	1h, 20mn
T11	Male	2	Southern part of Algeria	1h
T12	Male	8	Southern part of Algeria	1h, 15mn
T13	Female	3	Southern part of Algeria	1h, 10mn
T14	Female	20	Southern part of Algeria	1h, 30mn
T15	Female	5	Eastern part of Algeria	1h, 5mn
T16	Female	5	Western part of Algeria	1h, 10mn

Table 06: Demographic Data of the Participants of the Semi-structured Interviews.

4.3.3.3 Online Survey

The online survey was conducted with the aim of contextualizing the data and building initial idea about the teachers views and awareness of the introduction of values policy. This tool is the most conducted by different researchers as it is easy and economical to manage, yet this tool has both advantages and disadvantages (Gillham, 2007). first it is a low cost in time and money, second it is easy to get information from people quickly, respondents can complete the it when it suits them, the analysis of the survey is straightforward (Gillham, 2007). Another advantage is less pressure for immediate response, moreover the respondents’ anonymity can be assured, there is lack of interviewer bias, standardizations of questions (when all participants

get same questions, a source of bias is eliminated) (Gillham, 2007). However, this tool has potential drawbacks, for instance the quality of data and is likely to get a low response rate, problems of motivating respondent, also there is a need for brevity and relatively simple questions as the misunderstanding cannot be corrected (Gillham, 2007). In the current study, the limitation of clarity and/or ambiguity of the questions were reviewed during the pilot study where the volunteering participants were asked to provide feedback if the questions are clear, understandable, or ambiguous. After each section, the participants were provided a space in case they wished to expand on their responses. I tried to motivate more participants to take part through the introductory sentences I include whenever I share the questionnaire in different forums for instance, the survey questions are straightforward, and the survey is not time consuming. For the quality of data as mentioned earlier a space was provided after each section to provide further discussion or explanation. The participant cannot move to the next section until all questions of current section are answered. The anonymity of participants was highly assured as well. The introductory paragraph in the questionnaire explains how the data will be accessed and that only the researcher will have access to the data. In addition, the data will only be explored for the aim of the current study.

There are several motives that highlighted the choice of this tool, first and foremost is the accessibility as the online survey can be accessed from anywhere with an internet connection, making it convenient for participants to respond at their own pace and convenience. This accessibility increases the reach of the study to a wider and potentially more diverse audience. Also, conducting surveys online is often more cost-effective than traditional paper-based surveys i.e. there are no printing or postage costs involved, and data can be collected and stored electronically, reducing administrative expenses. Furthermore, this tool is efficient as it allows quick dissemination and data collection, the researcher can reach a large number of participants simultaneously, reducing the time required to gather responses compared to traditional methods. The use of online surveys enhances the data accuracy as it can minimize errors in data entry and transcription, as responses are directly entered into a digital format. This reduces the likelihood of data entry mistakes and ensures the accuracy of the collected data. Another privilege is anonymity and confidentiality, because most of the time Participants may feel more comfortable providing honest and candid responses in an online survey due to the anonymity it offers. The online survey can automatically collect and organize responses, making data management more efficient. I was able to easily export data for analysis and reporting, saving time and effort in data processing. I was able to track survey completion rates and monitor

responses in real-time. This allows for immediate adjustments or follow-ups to improve data quality and participant engagement.

4.3.3.4 Semi-structured interviews

The use of interviews is crucial to investigate motivation, attitudes, beliefs, feelings, perceptions, and expectations through including open-ended questions (Corbetta, 2003). Since I am exploring EFL teachers' perception on engaging with values values, I saw interviews to be optimal to gather the data. The data obtained from the online survey helped me in reviewing and redesigning interview questions as described by Morse et al. (2002) who argue that the new ideas that emerges from obtained data, which had been examined and verified, is a process known as theoretical thinking, and it is a verifying strategy establishes the reliability and validity of the obtained data.

The interview is 'a conversation between interviewer and respondent with the purpose of eliciting certain information from the respondent' (Mosar and Kalton, 1971, p.271). Commenting on this description Bell and Waters (2018) argue that the interview process is not as straightforward as stated in the definition, conducting a good interview is a complicated process. 'Preparation for interviews follows much the same procedures as for surveys, topics need to be selected, questions devised, methods of analysis considered and a schedule prepared and piloted' (Bell and Waters, 2018, p.210). Some guidelines on how to write appropriate interview questions helped me in the design of the interview questions for instance, the words of the questions should be clear, concise, and open, the questions should be clear and not too long, also unjustified assumptions should not be involved and finally, the response types (open-ended/closed-ended questions) should be determined before the interview (Judd et al., 1991).

The reason of choosing this particular tool is that as a researcher, I believe that interviews are ideal tool for data collection in qualitative research as it allows in-depth exploration that helped me to delve deeply into the perspectives, experiences, and insights of participants. Through open-ended questions and probing, I was able to uncover rich and detailed information that may not be captured through the online survey tool. Interviews provided me with rich, nuanced data that offer a comprehensive understanding of the research topic. Participants can elaborate on their thoughts, feelings, and experiences, providing context and depth to the data collected.

During interviews, I was able to seek clarification on responses, ask follow-up questions, and explore unexpected avenues that arise during the discussion. This flexibility allows for a more thorough exploration of the research topic. Interviews give participants a voice in the research

process, allowing them to share their viewpoints, opinions, and narratives directly with the researcher. This participant perspective is valuable for gaining insights into the lived experiences of individuals. In addition, interviews provide an opportunity to establish rapport and trust between the researcher and the participant, this positive relationship can encourage participants to share openly and honestly, leading to more authentic data. Moreover, in face-to-face interviews, a researcher can observe non-verbal cues such as body language, facial expressions, and tone of voice. These non-verbal cues can provide additional context and insights into the participant's responses. Most importantly, interviews can be tailored to individual participants, allowing the researcher to adapt questions based on the responses provided, this personalized approach ensures that the data collected is relevant and meaningful to each participant.

4.3.3.5 Mediated Interviews

Both tools of data collections were conducted virtually because of COVID-19 pandemic and lockdown, the travel restrictions and schools closure in Algeria. The approaches that are conducted virtually called mediated, mediated interviews occur via 'technological media' such as 'a telephone, a computer, or hand-held electronic device' (Tracy, 2020, p.186). The researcher may resort mediated interviews for many reasons such as 'it is more convenient, geography, cost, disability, social anxiety, or refusal to meet in person' (p.186). There are two types of mediated interviews, synchronous mediated interview, which means both the researcher and participants, interact at the same time, via telephone, webcam conversation, WebEx. Asynchronous mediated interviews are those in which parties interact in 'unfolding interaction at different times' such as in emails, internet forums, online qualitative surveys (p.186). The advantages of this approach are first, the cost is very economical and suits most researchers, the researcher can reach the participants who are 'distributed across a wide geographical area' or those prefer to stay at home due to a disability or anxiety. It allows comfort and safety that participants feel when they are in the same context. In addition, it is useful for participants who are shy or might be concerned worried about their social desirability to be less anxious and feel more active in virtual approaches (O'connor et al., 2008). In the other hand, the virtual approach has also some drawbacks for instance, mediated Interviews reduced the verbal and embodied data, the sample is limited to those who have technological access and expertise, also there is a possibility of respondent distraction from his surrounding (checking emails, responding to messages, or raised noise). Usually, participants in virtual approaches show drop out early (this can be due to other urgent commitments), in some case

participant may seek out input from others, but this occurs more in asynchronous mediated interviews. I encounter some of these drawbacks and other issues of timing, social desirability bias. Those disadvantages were minimised in the current study through setting timeline for the interviews process helped me in not exceeding the time constraint. Concerning the social desirability bias that may occur during the interviews (Bhattacharjee, 2012) it was avoided through assuring non-interference in participants' answers, assuring that questions were asked in a general way that does not direct the participant toward precise answer or direction. I made sure to meet the participant when they are available and not engaged in other appointments or commitments and in case of something urgent shows up, there was always a possibility of rescheduling the interviews. I asked the participant to check the devices (phone or laptop and internet connection) well before the interview, and preferably choosing quiet and isolated place.

4.3.4 Data Analysis Process and Techniques

The data gathered through the online survey were analysed descriptively by generating the total number of answers for each question whereas the data gathered through semi-structured interviews were analysed thematically using NVIVO Software. Glaser (1992) defined qualitative analysis as type of analysis where findings, concepts, and hypothesis are produced, the analysis of data that are not arrived at by statistical methods. The qualitative analysis consists of essentially three activities, data reduction, data display, and data drawing/verification (Miles and Huberman, 1994, p.10).

4.3.4.1 Thematic Analysis and NVIVO 12

The analyses of semi-structured interview data were approached qualitatively using the thematic analysis method. Thematic Analysis is 'a method of identifying, analysing, and reporting patterns (themes) within data' (Braun and Clarke, 2006). I chose this approach as it fits the aim of the study which is obtaining themes and patterns that would describe how EFL teachers perceive the core values embedded across the Middle School curriculum, identifying how teachers engage with these values in their daily teaching as well as highlighting any potential challenges or affordances reported by the teachers. Initially the analysis was conducted following six steps of Braun and Clarke (2006), familiarizing myself with the data through reading and re-reading of the transcripts, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining, and naming themes, and finally producing the reports.

I began the process by listening repeatedly to the record; the interviews were in English even though participants were asked to choose to speak either in English, Arabic or Algerian dialect,

so there was no need for translation. Then, I start the transcription process carefully to avoid any mistakes and redundancy, during this stage initial codes were identified. The data were just transcribed, described and sometimes comment on without any changes. After that, the ideas were organized and categorized. I had every interview transcript in a separate word format then labelled everyone as T1-T16 (teacher one, teacher two...), I inserted them in NVIVO (version 12). The following step was to open each file and started the coding, similar codes were grouped together to obtain a more comprehensive theme. Next, I provided each theme with a name that are clear and concise. At the end a written report of the themes and results obtained was developed.

4.4 Researcher Positionality and Reflexivity

The fieldwork is an important stage in the research process. The researcher may select specific locations and a sample of participants that may be familiar or new to the researcher, such as the society to which the researcher belongs, or people he might know. These factors influence the process of the research as well as the data gathered and therefore positionality and reflexivity of the researcher should be addressed. For the current study, I have many things in common with the participants: the cultural background, linguistic features and belonging to the education sector, more precisely with those I interviewed. I have a formal and professional relationship with some and informal friendly relationship with others and for some others it was the first time meeting them. My own experience and familiarity with the participants cultural, linguistic and sometimes professional context interfered in this study as an insider, as well as an outsider when I perceived the participants' responses and while analysing the data. Yet I maintained critical reflexivity and assured that the whole process went in an ethical way.

Positionality is 'the steps taken by researchers to explain their position in relation to their study (Hammond and Wellington, 2013. p.118), in other words how the research might be influenced by the researcher' own beliefs, values and background (p.118). Discussions about positionality is more and more debated and controversial as not only problems of 'subjective interpretation' but also the 'gap background knowledge' matters (Mistry, Berardi, and Simpson, 2008). Particularly in qualitative research as it is considered to be interpretative, and the researcher is likely to be in contact with the participants for certain time which might be 'sustained' and 'intensive' which also may result in some 'personal and strategic issues (Locke, Spirduso, and Silverman, 2013). Thereby, there is an inquiry for explicitly identifying a reflexive biases value, and background such as gender, history, culture, and socioeconomic status which shape the researcher interpretation during conducting the study or other ethical issues (Creswell and

Creswell, 2018). Reflexivity includes two crucial points: ‘past experience’ which means the factors that directly link the researcher and to the study through participating or choosing the setting of the study for instance, past educational or work experience, culture, ethnicity, race, socioeconomic status or others (Creswell and Creswell, 2018). The second factor is about ‘how past experiences shape interpretations, these past experiences shape and influence the interpretations which are developed during the study by the researcher for example, the experience may affect the researcher preferences, or make him believe in a certain themes rather than others and try to support these themes (Creswell and Creswell, 2018).

An interesting question was asked by (Creswell, 2016), ‘How can reflexive thinking be incorporated into your qualitative study? the answer to this question is by involving the process of taking notes about the researcher’s personal experience while conducting the fieldwork (Creswell and Creswell, 2018). These notes can be details of the observation process, guesses on what you are learning and ideas or intentions about participant’s reactions. They refer to these kind of notes as ‘memos’, these might help the researcher in developing themes and in the coding process. Another way for a researcher to reach ‘sufficient reflexivity’ is through reflecting on his personal experiences, importantly he should consider how this experience shape his interpretation of the result (Creswell and Creswell, 2018). Also, a critical friend or seeking feedback from his supervisor might be useful.

4.5 Ethical Considerations

In the present research, I followed the ethical criteria proposed by the British Educational Research Association (BERA, 2018), and the UWS ethics guidelines. The following criteria were successfully addressed. First, ensuring the privacy and confidentiality of the data, providing consent for participation, submitting an application to the ethics committee and receiving approval as a condition for conducting the fieldwork (UWS), including the right to withdraw for the participants and the confidentiality of the data storage (BERA, 2018). The ethical considerations for the current study were fully considered. The initial step begun by applying for ethical approval that requires filling in a detailed form about the process, the participants, attaching a copy of the online survey and the semi-structured interview form as well as the consent form and participants information sheet. The Ethics Committee of the School of Education and Social Sciences at UWS carefully examined the application and the details provided, also ensuring that the questions are clear and straightforward, and they do not include any kind of deception, threatening or cause fear or stress to the participants.

Nowadays research studies regardless of their field are subject to some ethical excesses or issues, and thus researchers should pay attention to the ethical considerations of their research. The information provided by the researchers to the participant must be sufficiently detailed, relevant, and accurate. The participant information sheet should outline clearly and honestly all aspects of the research that are relevant to a decision of providing a consent. Nowadays almost all universities and colleges require students' researchers whom their studies contain 'human subject' to apply for ethical approval and this requires filling in an ethical form provided by their departments or institutional ethics committee before proceeding their fieldwork (Wilson, 2014. p.89). Thus, ethics can be defined as 'the principles, norms, and standards of conduct governing an individual or group' (Treviño and Nelson, 1999. p.12). The ethical framework in the other hand requires conducting a study which is harm-free for the participants, ensures informed consent of participants, respects participants' privacy, avoids any deception (Gray, 2013, pp.73–80).

4.6 Informed Consent/ participants' information sheet

The 'consent' as a term means 'seeking permission for something to happen or for something to be done' (Wilson, 2014. p.96). Thus, 'informed consent' conveys the meaning that the researcher must be responsible for explaining accurately to the participant the 'nature of research and the role the individual has in the study' (p.96). In addition, the informed consent should ensure that the participants are, competent (they have the intellectual capacity and psychological maturity necessary to understand the nature of the research and their involvement in the study), autonomous (they are making self-directed and self-determined choices. Others such as parents or guardians, cannot make the decision of participation for them), involved voluntarily (they must be aware of the research being conducted) (O' Leary, 2004). Furthermore, research on humans cannot be conducted without their knowledge and consent, being aware of the right to discontinue, not deceived which means; researchers need to be honest about the nature of their research, about the affiliation or professional standing, and the intended use of their study. Not coerced (positions of power should not be used to get individuals to participate in a study, as for instance an employers or teachers apply pressure on their charges to engage in research). Not induced which means offering money or some other reward that entices individuals to participate in research that they would otherwise avoid, this is considered an inducement. While it may be acceptable to compensate individuals for their time and effort, it should not be to an extent where it compromises a potential participant's judgment) (O' Leary , 2004 .p.53). On the other hand, Burns and Burns (2008) focus on what

informed consent should include, information about the nature and purpose of the research, a statement that participation is voluntary, including the choice to opt out at any time, information about the data collection methods and the option to agree/refuse to being recorded (if applicable), a description of the extent to which confidentiality will be maintained and an option to choose anonymity. Besides a description of any possible risks or discomforts to participants, a description of any possible benefits to participants or others, contact addresses, emails and/or telephone numbers for any questions about the research, a description of the intended uses of, and disposal/storage and documentation procedures for data, including an option to agree/disagree with these procedures. Finally, an option to agree or refuse to participate (signature of participant, date, signature of witness/researcher) (p.35). For my project, before collecting the data I will submit an informed consent form to the Ethics Committee of the School of Education and Social Sciences at the University of the West of Scotland, for review. I will make it accessible to all participants in order to know the nature of the research in order to see that anonymity is maintained, there are not forced to participate, they can withdraw at any time, and they have the right to refine their says if they feel that they tackle things that might cause harm.

4.7 Confidentiality

Another crucial aspect that should be considered in the research project is confidentiality, which is a way of ‘protecting a participant’s right to privacy’ (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018, p.130). This can be done through ‘the promise of confidentiality which means not disclosing information from a participant in any way that might identify the participant or that might enable the individual to be traced’ (p130). Confidentiality can also mean ‘not discussing an individual’ information with anybody else or passing on the information to others in any form that can identify individuals’ (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018. P.130). It is highly recommended that ‘researchers must be explicit enough in explaining to the participants what the meaning and limits of confidentiality are in relation to the particular research project (p.130). There are a number of ‘techniques’ for valid implementation of confidentiality. first of all, a researcher shouldn’t consider any ‘identifiers’ (names, addresses or others), a researcher should consider general information rather than specific ones, for example asking about the profession rather than the speciality and the year of birth but not a specific date. Also, it is better that the focus be on the average data rather than the individual data, last but not least being careful of introducing any errors in the individual record without consider changing them after (Frankfort-Nachmias and Nachmias, 1992). A ‘signed statement’ is a good way for the

researcher to protect confidentiality, this signed should contain ‘non-disclosure’ of the data gathered from participants unless approval was asked (Cooper and Schindler, 2001), in similar cases the research may require an ‘insurance’ to protect the researchers from any unexpected occurrence (Wilson, 2014, p.96). As for the current study confidentiality was assured by avoiding collecting detailed information of the participants such as name, home, or work address. Also avoid collecting sensitive data about their personal or professional life.

4.8 Quality and Validity in Qualitative research/ Semi-structured Interviews

Examining quality and validity of any conducted research is an essential part in qualitative study (Patton, 2002; Merriam and Tisdell, 2016; Flick, 2014). The acceptance of any work is conditioned by respecting the adequate efforts for realising that and leading research, in which validity measurements is vital (Morse et al., 2002; Hayashi, 2019). However, the use of conventional quantitative criteria for validity and reliability in qualitative research is becoming increasingly problematic and confusing (Johnson and Christensen, 2014; Tracy, 2010; and Stenbacka, 2001). According to Smith and Osborn (2008), Hammarberg et al., (2016) and Thompson (2011), there is a distinction in epistemological, ontological, and paradigmatic underpinning between quantitative, qualitative, and mixed method. The variation includes also the purpose of each of these approaches as well as the availability of literature. This does not mean one of the approaches are dominant or better than the other approaches. They are different but they could complete each other (Hayashi, 2019). As evidence, recently there are an increase in the integration and collaboration between the two quantitative and qualitative methods of research (Creswell, 2009; Brannen, 2017; Molina-Azorin et al., 2016). While the assessment of validity is common in quantitative research since the evaluation criterion rooted in the positivist school. The use of the same criterion in qualitative research used to be debatable and it needs a reconsideration (Drapeau, 2004; Golafshani, 2003; Hammersley, 2007). Smith (1984), Smith (1989), Smith and Deemer (2000) argued that the attempt of applying the quantitative study criterion on qualitative study would unavoidably rescind the philosophical assumptions of qualitative approach which tend to be more naturalistic. Thus, the literature about quality in qualitative research claimed that the criterion should be revised and discussed by which quality, coherence and reliability between research problematic, data, and methods are maintained in the qualitative research (Leung, 2015; Mukamurera et al., 2006; Bell, 2010). Validity in qualitative research has different connotations and meanings that refers to “trustworthiness”, “Rigor”, “appropriateness” and even “quality”. Thus, validity can be expressed through a wide range of terms (Golafshani, 2003) to assess the value of the

qualitative research and its quality (Johnson and Christensen, 2014). In the same context, Lincoln and Guba (1985) labelled qualitative research quality as “Trustworthiness”. Among the ongoing debates and perplexity to decide on which characteristics should qualitative researchers respect to sustain quality and validity of their studies, Lincoln and Guba (1985) proposed four criteria: credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability. Several models have been created in an attempt to figure out this confusion about qualitative research’s measurements such as Yardly’s four criteria (2000), Elliott et al. (1999) seven criteria and Furlong and Oancea four criteria (2005). In the current research I am adopting Lincoln and Guba model, because the mentioned guidelines are either too general in their scope such as Elliott’s model, Furlong and Oancea. The two could be used for both qualitative and quantitative studies. Yardly four criteria is commonly used in IPA research, by which it was proposed by Smith et al. (2009) in his book. Moreover, these criteria are deemed to be suitable for studies in psychology.

4.8.1 Credibility

According to Lincoln and Guba (1985), Credibility in qualitative research refers to the honest representation of findings, by which the results accurately interpret and depict the respondents' initial reflections, and they are consistent with the original data. They proposed several techniques about how credibility is promoted such as triangulation, participants’ validation of the interpreted data, peer review and debriefing, data saturation and negative cases analysis, reflexivity, prolonged engagement with participants. These techniques were all applied in this study. The engagement with my participants was prolonged through the data collection tools and process. At first, I created initial contact with my participants via different platforms (social media) as I mentioned previously in sampling strategies section. I prepared my participants for actual fieldwork by explaining the aim of my research and sustaining contact with them. The participants were involved in one-to-one hour and half interview in addition to the online survey they answered before. Different methods were used to gather a significant quantity of data (triangulation), in which I asked my participants to send me emails, messages, or memos in case they remember any information they forgot to mention it during the interview. To assure findings’ validity and the accurate interpretation of data, I consulted with my participants whether my reflections as a researcher upon their narrations is adequate to what have been recorded. For the plausibility, I used quotations and extracts to inform the reader that the presented data is consistent to participants’ reflections and interpretation regarding the core of my research. Finally, I did peer reviewing with my doctoral fellows who belong to the same

host university to insure both the credibility of my research, and ethical norms of writing PhD thesis set by the institution.

4.8.2 Transferability

Validity and quality of qualitative research should include the character of being comprehensible for external readers, by which known as the generalisability of findings (Merriam and Tisdell, 2016). This can be guaranteed throughout maximising variation of the sample (distinctive criteria of the sample to enhance the possibility of generalisability). Typical sampling i.e. sample that represents the whole targeted population. Providing a thick description of the studied phenomenon, in which the researcher describes intensively and deeply the context and the scope of the conducted research. This includes research design, environment, participants' feelings and engagement, time, methods, and other details that enable the reader to clearly understand and evaluate the research and apply it in other contexts (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). In this study, I tried to extremely report all the details regarding teachers' perceptions of values embedded in the school curriculum, how they enact these values, and I did also interpret their concerns and challenges they encountered. To back-up the literature and the background of my research, I referred to the experience of teaching values and value studies in other countries such as Kuwait, Turkey, South Africa, and UAE, by which the findings of my research will be transferable to other researchers in the domain of values education design from other nations. Regarding the sample I used, I recruited Algerian Middle School teachers from different Algerian regions in order to, first, generalise the findings in terms of the Algerian context since Algeria is a large country. Thus, the focus on specific or small area would limit the scope of transferability. Secondly, the sample I used was homogenous and purposively selected to report a general overview about the outcomes of the experience of interacting with values introduced in school curriculum designed in Algeria compared to other nations.

4.8.3 Dependability and confirmability

Dependability is the third Criteria that assess the trustworthiness in qualitative research, in which it linked to reliability and bias free in conducting qualitative study (Janis, 2022; Lincoln and Guba, 1985). It has been defined in literature as the use of same context, same methods, and same participants would results in the same conclusion (Lincoln and Guba, 1985; Forero et al., 2018). Thus, the researcher must be prudent with his preconceptions and assumptions, in which the researchers should control and realise their bias during the stages of the qualitative study (Machi et al., 2016). In the same context of Bias- free, confirmability refers, or it is

similar to the credibility that entails qualitative researcher objectivity in and neutrality in collecting and presenting the data as it has been altered and viewed by participants (Hamberg et al., 1994). According to Lincoln and Guba (1985), Confirmability can be achieved by Audit trail. That is to say, researchers can use audit trails to record the entire data analysis process, including how themes were identified, how sub-themes were organised, and how decisions regarding pertinent insights were reached. This shows that the conclusions are solely dependent on the opinions provided by respondents, which helps avoid researcher bias. Peer reviewing, triangulation and reflexivity (formerly discussed in section of credibility) are techniques that serves the transparent depictions of research process, stages, and results. As I explained in the previous sections, I made sure that the data I am collecting and analysing is not contaminated by the projection of my presumptions and personal judgment of the studied phenomenon. The confirmability of the present research has been illustrated as well in the section of positionality and reflexivity. I explained my attitude and position as an insider and outsider at the same time, by which I tried to restrict my role as a researcher who aims to discover a phenomenon from Algerian Middle School teachers' perspective.

Conclusion

To sum up this chapter, both theoretical stand as well as the practical methodology were considered and described in this chapter. Based on the research questions and the aim of the study the philosophical assumption, ontology (social constructivism) and epistemology (interpretivism) were identified. The current study also followed a qualitative research approach which was described and discussed. In addition, for the aim of gathering data both online survey and semi-structured interviews were employed. A description of chosen the sampling and the recruiting strategy were explained. And finally, the ethical considerations and other related concerns of assuring confidentiality and anonymity of participants were elaborated. The process of data collection, analysis and how the researcher maintained the quality and the validity of the qualitative inquiry were also discussed.

Chapter Five

Perceptions about the Values in Curriculum

Introduction

This chapter presents the analysis of the data generated from both the online survey (64 participants) and the semi-structured interviews (16 participants) in regard to the first research question “How do teachers perceive the values underpinning the second-generation curriculum?” The presentation as well as the interpretation of the findings are considered. The themes resulted from the analysis of the data in relation to the first research question are supported by numerical data from the online survey. In the online survey, the participants were provided with different statements where they were asked to answer according to a “Likert scale” by choosing among the following, strongly agree (SA), agree (A), neutral (N), disagree (D) and strongly disagree (SD) (see Appendix 03). These statements are mentioned under each diagram (diagram title).

The data from the online survey will be presented in charts followed by an interpretation and a discussion of these data. Second, the data generated from the semi-structured interviews will also be presented and discussed. Following that, the implications of these data for the research will be discussed in relation to the literature reviewed. The aim of the first research questions is to understand how Algerian EFL teachers understand and perceive the core values of national identity, conscience, citizenship, and openness to the world.

5.1 The SGC reform does not Foregrounds the Teaching of the Core Values

The introduction of these values in the school curriculum was through a policy which stated the necessity of embedding core values in the Middle school curriculum and were introduced as part of a reform called the Second-Generation curriculum as stated in the policy and official documents (Ministry of National Education, 2016) for instance, the official bulletin, the English language programme, and the teacher guide. These documents highlighted these values to be the core of the reform and the rationale of this curriculum change is promoting the teaching of values as part of the Middle School curriculum. Initially, it was crucial to discuss the teachers’ understanding of the SGC reform and the policy of promoting the teaching of the core values. Surprisingly, the teachers did not seem to perceive that the SGC reform foregrounded the teaching of the core values. According to the data resulted from the interviews, most teachers (13/16) do not perceive the link between the SGC reform and the values. This theme is not supported by data from the online survey, as this is an open-ended

question ‘what is the core of the SGC reform?’ was included in the interviews only (see Appendix 04). During the interviews, T1(teacher 1) affirmed:

The second-generation curriculum focuses on teaching English using the competency-based approach to form competent users of language of science and technology to meet the requirement of globalization.

T2 added:

the core of the recent curriculum reform as mentioned in the policy documents is to help the learner to build a capacity for detachment, critical thinking, decision-making and independent learning.

Similarly, T3 believed that:

the core of the new reform is to foster the students’ autonomous learning with the guidance of the teacher, providing them with the needed materials and tools, instead of teacher-centred teaching. This will encourage the learners to gain certain capacity of critical thinking.

T4 clearly answered:

the so-called second-generation curriculum is a new educational system, or a reform as called by the policymakers, initially adopted in 2003, which focused on the use of CBA and later on has been revised in 2016 to focus more on CBLT, learners’ autonomy, learners-centred learning process and enhancing the students’ communicative skills.

T9 justified:

The focus of this reform was initially to focus more on the use of language for communication and shifting the task from storing the knowledge to building it with the students. So, the students would gain some capacity of critical thinking, developing skills such as discussion instead of passively receiving the information and storing them.

In addition, T5, T6, T8, T10, T12, T14, T15, and T16 Share similar perspectives with T1, T2, T3, T4 and T9. According to these teachers the SGC reform focused on enhancing the teaching pedagogy, the implementation of the competency-based approach in more effective way, enhancing students’ communicative skills and the use of language for communication, enhancing students’ autonomy and independent learning where the pupils are at the centre of the teaching process rather than teacher dominating the process of teaching/learning, as well as developing critical thinking. These teachers did not refer to the core values or the introduction of the core values while talking about the reform. This indicates that teachers do not perceive these values to be the core of the SGC, they also believe that these values have always been considered in the schools’ curriculum. T2 for example claimed that:

these values of identity and enhancing pupils' national identity have always been presented in the curriculum, all the lesson were about Algeria, making the pupils know more about the country and the heritage of their country.

T8 also believed that:

The school curriculum always talks about Algeria, principles of the country, its history and background also about geographical location, policymakers always want pupils to know about their country and be proud of their culture and belonging.

Similar idea also shared by T14:

We are always teaching our students about their country, about their culture, these things need to be immersed on our children since young age. When they grow up, they need to be proud of their country and they need to contribute to the development of their country.

The data denotes that curriculum content has always reflects these core values mainly in more implicit way, the curriculum also intended to foster the values of national identity and citizenship through designing lesson and activities that reflect the country, the culture, background, the history... etc.

On the other hand, only three teachers, T7, T11, T13 perceived the introduction of the core values to be the contribution of the Second-Generation curriculum. They believed that the SGC reform named explicitly the "core values". T11 stated that:

The SGC focuses more and explicitly on the core values, before in the policy documents and the teacher guide never mentioned these core values, the curriculum contained lesson about Algeria yes, but core values were not mentioned in detail and included in the structure and the lesson plan.

T7 believed that:

The school reform introduced the teaching of core values explicitly, this means the reform focuses on values, we can see this in the curriculum of English language book, in the teacher guide, and the yearly planning also when we did the training programme the inspectors referred to the teaching of core values. Also, teacher needs to include them whenever he or she is planning the lesson.

By explicitly mentioned in the SGC reform, T13 meant:

these values are mentioned in the official documents like the teacher's guide. Adding to this, the teachers were introduced to the idea of values and the mentioned list of values during workshops or during teachers' trainings.

The data resulted from the interviews denotes that the core values of national identity, conscience, citizenship, and openness to the world values did exist before introducing the SGC reform as the curriculum content has always focus on the students' national identity,

citizenship, and culture through including lessons and activities that reflect the students' national identity, citizenship and has always support students to learn foreign languages and know about foreign cultures. However, they were not named as such or mentioned explicitly in the policy documents. Furthermore, there was no focus on teaching these values in the classroom therefore, this is what has been introduced in the SGC reform.

Nevertheless, the fact that the vast majority of the interviewed teachers were unable to recognise and to acknowledge how the new reform of the SGC foregrounds the policy of promoting the teaching of the core values as part of the school curriculum, alerts us that there is a lack of teachers' clear understanding and lack of teachers' knowledge of the new reform and a new policy. In other words, policymakers failed to effectively deliver the new reform of the SGC and the policy of promoting the core values within school curriculum to teachers. It is noticeable, there policymakers and teachers are not on the same page regarding the core reform, the contribution, and its implications. This lack of consensus between the two parties can result in number of issues for instance, teachers' failure to grasp the significant of the reform and the policy of promoting the teaching of values, therefore, there will be a lack of effectively incorporate these values into the teachers' teaching practices. The literature tackled this issue widely, Lack of consensus between teachers and policymakers regarding educational reforms can have significant consequences on the effectiveness and implementation of these reforms. When teachers and policymakers do not align in their understanding and support of reforms, it can lead to confusion, frustration, and a lack of commitment among teachers towards the proposed changes (Xu and Cepa, 2018). This lack of alignment may result in teachers feeling disconnected from the reform policies, leading to unintended consequences and potential failure of the reform initiatives (Cheng and Huang, 2018). The lack of consensus between teachers and policymakers can result in a disconnect between espoused values and actions, leading to challenges in implementing reforms effectively (Kulophas, Hallinger, and Ruengtrakul, 2018). Aligning teachers' understanding of the SGC reform and the policy of instilling core values in the classroom, helps in promoting consistency in how core values are taught and reinforced across different classrooms and schools. they are more likely to prioritize and emphasize these values in their teaching practices. This alignment can lead to a more coherent and purposeful approach to values education, ultimately benefiting students by fostering a positive learning environment that promotes the development of essential values and skills.

This finding highlights the importance of aligning teachers' understanding of the SGC reform and future reforms introduced by policymakers, also ensuring teachers' comprehension of the policy of promoting the teaching of the core values within the intended reform objectives. Policymakers should develop direct and clear contact with the teachers regarding new introduced reforms and policy in order to ensure teachers' understanding of these reforms.

5.2 Perceiving the meaning of the Core Values

The policy of values education was introduced to be part of national curriculum in schools in Algeria by policymakers, in the academic year 2016/2017. It was crucial to inquire about teachers' understanding of the policy of values education and the list of the chosen values as well, because understanding teachers' comprehension of policy messages is crucial for effective implementation (Coburn, 2001). Furthermore, teachers play a significant role in interpreting policy messages and making decisions on how to apply them in classrooms. Teachers' beliefs and values, especially regarding the purpose of education, are central to policy implementation (Jonglai, Pike, and Lamb, 2021). Therefore, assessing teachers' understanding of core values within policies can help identify potential challenges in aligning their beliefs with policy objectives and implementation.

In the online survey, teachers' answers about the statement saying "the list of values as stated in the policy documents are clear" were as follows: most teachers (39%) who agree and (5%) strongly agree that the values are clear, whereas (28%) disagree and (3%) strongly disagree with the statement. Teachers' views fail to reach a concord on whether the list of values is clear, this suggests that the teachers differ on the way they understand the policy of values education and the mentioned list of values.

On another statement saying "I can differentiate between the three listed values of national identity, conscience, citizenship and openness to the world" which seeks teachers understanding and making sense of what each core value means and how each core value differs from one another. Answers were the vast majority of 74% agree that they can differentiate between them whereas the minority of 26% disagree that they can distinguish between the core values listed by the policymakers. It is noticeable that an accord among teachers' views on whether they can differentiate between the listed values of national identity, conscience, citizenship, and openness to the world could not be reached.

In the online survey, teachers were also asked about how they perceive "the interpretation of the implementation of these values in the classroom, through the way they are presented or

tackled in the policy documents. 44% of teacher agree that they are confused in interpreting the implementation of these values in their teaching practice, 8% are strongly concerned about this. Whereas 22% of teachers do not face this issue and 3% that are extremely clear about the implementation of the values in their teaching. On the other hand, 23% mask their sentiments about this statement. The data generated from the online survey show that there is no consensus among teachers on the clarity of the implementation of the core values as tackled in the policy documents. Teachers have different understanding and differ on the way they perceive the clarity and comprehensiveness of policies and instructions provided by policymakers. for some policies and instructions given in the PD might be clear and can be easily interpreted the practice of these policies in their daily teaching whereas others may not be able to make sense of policies and instructions provided in official documents. This signifies the fact that undertaking and addressing a new policy and circulate it to teachers through policy documents, does not guarantee the clarity of the policy and does not guarantee teachers' understanding of the new policy. This issue also addressed in the literature, research suggests that teachers' understanding, and interpretation of policies are influenced by various factors beyond written documents (Palmer and Rangel, 2010). Teachers do not passively accept policy instructions but rather filter them through their own knowledge, experiences, and considerations for their students' best interests (Palmer and Rangel, 2010). This active sensemaking process by teachers highlights the limitations of relying solely on policy documents to ensure effective policy implementation. Furthermore, the complexity of policies and the need for coherence in understanding them further emphasizes the limitations of relying solely on written documents (Russell and Bray, 2013). This highlights the need to consider the broader educational ecosystem beyond policy documents to ensure effective communication and implementation of new policies. Conveying new policies to teachers requires a multifaceted approach that considers teachers' sensemaking processes, professional autonomy, involvement in decision-making, and the role of other parties for instance, administration, inspectors, and teacher educators. In addition, policymakers need to engage with teachers beyond policy documents to ensure that policies are effectively understood, accepted, and implemented in educational settings.

Discussing teachers' familiarity with the core values during the interviews was important to explore in depth their perspectives on the meaning of values education and what is their familiarity with the three core values. Exploring teachers understanding and interpretation of the meaning of values will help in understanding how teachers value the values education and

their implementation in the classroom. According to the data generated from the semi-structured interviews, all teachers (16 teachers) were able to express their familiarity with the values that were introduced in the school curriculum, they were able to list these values, categorized them (national and international values), and provided general definitions.

According to T2 values are:

...collective conceptions of what is considered good, desirable, and proper or bad and undesirable and improper within the context of certain culture, for example familiar values are wealth, loyalty, independence, equality, justice, fraternity, and friendliness.

The teacher definition is in line with the definitions provided by Schwartz (2011) and (Shaver and Strong, 1976) which also according to them values are the standards by which society members assess concepts, judge ideas, items, people, events, and acts as good, worthwhile, desirable, wrong, worthless, or undesirable. On the other hand, T3 believes that:

values are kind of morals and principles which should be set in every lesson plan for instance, if the lesson deals with daily activities, the core values should be about time management, setting time plan and respecting it, whereas if the lesson plan is about food, the values should be about charity and economic consumption.

T5 added:

the values included in the curriculum lay on valuing people's citizenship and life experience such as, family, school, friends, personality, dreams, and memories in addition to build their readiness of receptivity and responsiveness on other successful figures and other parts of the world.

T8 believed that:

Values are the principles that guide someone's behaviour, it is the reference we consider to judge whether we are right or wrong, for example our religion is full of values that we need to respect them and follow them. Also we need to teach these values to our children and our pupils in school.

The different ways teachers defined and explained the meaning of values signifies that each individual develops his unique understanding of a concept or a phenomenon and perceived it from different aspect according to his background, area of interest, environment. Some of them related it more precisely to their teaching profession others for example may perceived the concept in more moral and religious sense, according to some others the concept of values is a cultural aspect. Other factors that may affect the way teachers understand the concept of values education, its implementation as well as its importance can be whether they received training or not and their personal or professional experience this is supported by many research in the literature. Some research indicates that teachers' professional identity, experiences, and training play a significant role in shaping their perceptions of educational concepts, including values

education (Beijaard, Meijer, and Verloop 2004). Additionally, teachers' personal values and cultural backgrounds can influence their understanding of values education and how they prioritize different values in the classroom (Cojocariu, 2015; Seah, 2016).

5.3 Perceiving the Rational of Embedding the Core Values in the Middle School Curriculum

Figure 03. The rationale behind introducing these values is clear.

Another aspect the teachers were asked about in both the online survey and the semi-structured interviews is whether they are familiar with the rationale of values education policy. Recognizing the rationale of instilling values in pupils and introducing them as part of the national curriculum, will help us understand teachers' perspective on values education as to how they value and prioritize the implementation of this policy in their teaching practice.

In the online survey, the number of teachers who are familiar with the rationale of values education is 36% (including those who strongly agree and agree) and 35% (including those who strongly disagree and disagree) are not familiar with the rationale of this policy. Both percentages are close

During the semi-structured interviews, also the teachers' answers differ about their familiarity of the rationale of the values education policy. T16 stated:

These values have always been in the curriculum, but there was not great focus given to them. Consequently, stakeholders wanted to shed more light on the teaching of the values through including them as part of the school curriculum. The rationale of this decision is to strengthen the students' sense of belonging and prepare them to be successful citizens who will be beneficial for the society.

T7 added:

the reason of introducing these values is to help our society to live in harmony with modernity by providing the learner with linguistic tools essential for efficient communication. Also he can introduce himself and his culture, he can talk about his country and the different customs and traditions to foreigners. Emmm...maybe in online chat or during travels. So it is important to learn about these things in school.

T12

the reason is to give every learner the opportunity to have access to science, technology and world culture while avoiding the dangers of acculturation. Because now the world is becoming like a global village due to globalization and technology. everyone is connected to others via internet and electronic devices. School needs to keep pace with the development, but first thing needs to immerse the values of the society in the students and these values need to be maintained inside and outside the school.

Furthermore T13:

Algeria has large population of different ethnic groups, for instance, Arab, Amazigh (Kabyle, Shawiya) each group has a different linguistic repertoire, different culture, traditions and believes, in most of the time this creates kind of conflicts and disputes between them. Thus, those values were introduced in the schools as part of the curriculum to create a unity between these different ethnic groups.

This data agrees with what has been provided by T1:

Algeria is large country with many ethnic groups living together, there are many spoken varieties and also deferent cultures, traditions and costumes. The government is concerned about any raised quarrels and disputes between them, that is why policymakers want to spread unity by teaching values and morals also reminding the children that what matters is that all of them are coming from same country, same religion, same identity which they need to be proud of and preserve it lifelong.

Almost all teachers' answers convey the same idea which is the rationale of values education is about instilling national identity and sense of belonging on pupils, also about character and citizenship; how can pupils be good citizens in the future and how can they positively contribute to the development of the society and their country. These findings are supported by many research in the literature worldwide, among them the study of Mattar and Khalil (2011) in Egypt. According to Mattar and Khalil (2011) The aim of character education is to communicate high levels of moral development, components of identity in order to promote effective social habits and productive future leaders, with further focus on equity, efficiency, and excellence. Arthur (2005) also believes that character and values education encourage pupils to engage with work experience or apprenticeships as preparation for future employment. Furthermore, in the UK for instance government has authorised the centre called "Jubilee centre", which provides materials and guidelines to promote the character education

programme with the stated goal of influencing the "future attitudes and behaviours of the British people" (Jubilee Centre for Character and Virtues, 2019).

On the other hand, there are some teachers [T3, T6, T9, T14] who claimed that they are not certain about what is the rationale of introducing these values in the school curriculum. T6 claimed that:

I cannot recognize why this decision is introduced, you know because teachers are not part of policy making, therefore most teachers do not know the intention of stakeholders when introducing some policies and reforms.

similar idea expressed by T3:

I am not sure about the rationale behind this policy because I am not part of making this policy or deciding about policy, sometimes if teacher is not taking part in deciding about certain policy or curriculum, he or she can not understand even the meaning of this change or what is it for.

This signifies the fact that when teachers are not part of deciding and designing a policy, it affects their ability to understand it, make sense of it and to recognize the rationale behind introducing it, therefore this will influence the ability of effective and proper implementation of this policy. In this sense, the Algerian EFL Middle School teachers do not have the required knowledge about values education, they are not familiar with the rationale of introducing values education in the national curriculum due to the fact that the policy of introducing values education was a top-down policy, imposed by policymakers without considering teachers' contribution. This finding is in line with many studies in the literature, those studies have shown that teachers may feel disconnected from policy decisions when they perceive a lack of consultation or involvement in the policy-making process, leading to challenges in policy acceptance and implementation (Thomas, 2005). Also, teachers' professional autonomy can be constrained when they feel excluded from the decision-making process (Thomas, 2005). This implies the necessity of involving teachers and considering their contribution in designing curriculum, or considering teachers' feedback when assessing a reform and deciding about policies as they know more about real practice and classroom practices as well as the students' needs and learning requirements. This also crucial for policymakers to ensure teachers' clear understanding of values education and effective implementation of the teaching of core values in the classroom.

There are other factors reported by few teachers [T7, T8, T9] that influence teachers' ability to recognize either the meaning, the aim, and the rationale of a policy in general and the policy of values education in particular. These factors either help or hinder the teachers to arrive to a clear understanding of what is the motive of considering the teaching of values to students within the school national curriculum. These factors are, the teachers' training programmes as the findings revealed that some teachers received training for the new policy of values education during which they were introduced to the concept of values education, the core values, and their implementation, the rationale and the aim of teaching core values within school curriculum as well whereas some others did not receive any kind of training. Some teachers complained about the effectiveness of the training programmes they received as being general, dealing with general teaching concerns such as teaching methods, students' needs and learning styles, but the training did not address the main policy which is values education and its implementation. This finding reflects what has been found in the literature, for instance the study of Julia and Supriyadi (2018) and Junaidi, Sunandar, and Yuwono (2021) which claimed that the level of involvement in training programs or professional development related to specific educational initiatives, like inclusive education or character education, can contribute to differences in teachers' perceptions. For instance, teachers who have received training on certain educational approaches may have a more nuanced understanding of the underlying principles and goals of those initiatives, leading to variations in how they perceive the importance and implementation of values education (Julia and Supriyadi, 2018) and (Junaidi, Sunandar, and Yuwono, 2021). This finding implies the importance of designing effective programme for teachers that address the values education and their implementation in the classroom.

Another factor that influences the teacher's ability to develop clear understanding of what might be the rationale, or the meaning of values education policy is the teachers' collaboration (T1, T14, T15). The teachers' collaboration also helps some teachers in discussing values related concerns with each other and develop a sense of why this policy was introduced. Experience (T2, T5, T7) on the other hand also plays a role in this matter. Experienced teachers already encountered and experienced different policies during which they develop awareness of the intentions of the policymakers. Finally, competence, commitment, and skills, (T4 and T16) as teachers have different professional skills, personal abilities, and level of commitments to their job. These are somehow like what has been found in the literature, that the context in which teachers work, such as the type of school or the cultural expectations regarding

citizenship education, can shape their perceptions of what constitutes valuable education and how it should be delivered (Hui et al., 2016; Lee et al., 2015).

5.4 Perceiving the aim of Embedding the Core Values in the Middle School Curriculum

Figure 04. The Aim of Embedding the Core Values in Curriculum is Clear

Understanding the aim of values and character education is particularly important for teachers as they play a central role in imparting these values to students. Teachers serve as role models and examples for students, making their own character and behaviour crucial in the inculcation of character values (Panggabean, 2022). Furthermore, Character education is essential in shaping students to become well-rounded individuals who are not only academically proficient but also morally upright and socially responsible (Hidayat and Rozak, 2022). Character education aims to develop students who are not only intelligent but also emotionally intelligent and capable of embodying goodness in their social interactions (Hidayat and Rozak, 2022). Therefore, teachers must comprehend the aim of values and character education to effectively impart these essential qualities to students. By understanding the aim and the significance of character education, teachers can play a pivotal role in shaping students' character, fostering a positive learning environment, and contributing to the holistic development of individuals. Accordingly, it was pivotal to enquire about whether the Algerian EFL Middle School teachers are aware of the aim of values education and what is it.

The majority of teachers 42% disagree and 11% strongly disagree about the statement “the aim of embedding the core values in curriculum is clear”. Whereas according 22% who agree and 3% strongly agree that the aim is clear.

Data generated from the semi-structured interviews could elaborate more on teachers' perspectives on the aim of fusing values in the school curriculum. and whether it has been achieved or not. Like the data resulted from the online survey, teachers' answers in the semi-structured interviews also differ between those who were familiar with aim of values education and between those who did not.

T1 and T8 for instance, confidently reflect on the questions and declared that the aim of these values is to develop communicative competences and skills, through engaging learners in real life problem-solving contexts and situation integration, in this case the aim has not effectively achieved as the students still encounter difficulties in communication and oral skills. The answers provided by T1 and T8 do not really reflect the real aim of values education which signifies the lack of proper understanding of the policy which may result in lack of effective implementation of the policy.

T5, T7 and T10 believed that the aim is to learn about values of proper behaving, success, and prosperity and apply them in real life. Also enhancing the national identity on students and developing good and successful citizens, again in this case the aim is partially achieved i.e., values of food habit, behaving in the classroom, for example, can be observed and controlled but for some other values, it is hard to be observed like citizenship (T7). Similar idea expressed by T9 who explained:

...for instance, if the values are about daily behaviour and values of respecting the teacher, helping your friends and colleagues, being nice to old people and behaving properly in the classroom. These can be easily maintained and evaluated but if they are about larger or general scoop like citizenship or identity there is no way a teacher can judge or evaluate whether it has been achieved or not.

This is strongly resembled with the idea suggested by T5 who explained:

if we consider values as a lesson to be taught/learnt, we can say that relatively the aim is or can be achieved, but if these values are to be regarded as life's principle to be maintained, it is not possible to decide. Because there is no precise way to decide or judge whether these has been maintained as the target initially that the students should employ those values and skills in real-life or in other words outside the classroom. Thus, it not possible to be evaluated. Moreover, no values tend to be relatively stable enduring.

On the other hand, T6 declared:

the aim is not clear thus this cannot be judged whether it has been achieved or not...It is not clear because, I am not sure why I need to include some values in my teaching also these values are not clear. Also the policy is not clear...we have some official documents that dealt with this but they did not provide details of the aim and rationale, I think teachers are struggling to teach these because there is no concrete guide that you can follow or rely on.

Similarly, T14 stated:

the aim of values inclusion in the curriculum is not clear, I can say many teachers do not seem optimistic or positive about teaching values, I think there is a confusion and lack of clear understanding of these values like aim and rationale. Consequently, there is a difficulty in employing them in the classroom. And as I mentioned before, the reason for that is that teachers are not part of policymaking.

Again, there are two major reasons for the lack of understanding and recognizing the aim of introducing the core values of national identity, conscience, citizenship, and openness to the world. One is the lack of effective training programmes. Teachers may not have received adequate content training or may not have the necessary knowledge and skills to effectively incorporate values education into their teaching practices (Aydın, Margerison, and Worsley, 2021). The second reason is disregarding the importance of teachers' contribution and participation in designing policies, considering their feedback on values education for instance and what values need to be fostered in the classroom. As they are the ones in direct contact with the students and know more about them, also they know more about the real teaching practices. The findings underscore the necessity of redesigning effective training programmes for teachers to address the new policies and address their needs. For instance, their need for clearly understanding the policy of fusing the core values in the school national curriculum, the aim, and the rationale of this policy as well as clear instructions on the implementation of values education in the classroom.

5.5 Prioritizing and Valuing the Core Values

Prioritizing and valuing the teaching of core values is crucial for teachers to enhance their teaching effectiveness of core values, promote positive student outcomes, and contribute to the holistic development of students' character. By integrating core values into their teaching practices, educators can create a nurturing learning environment that fosters academic growth

and the development of essential life skills and values. However, in the current study the data gathered through interviews demonstrated a disagreement between teachers' perspectives on valuing and prioritizing the teaching of core values. Some teachers (T1, T4, T7, T13, T15) perceived the teaching of core values as worthwhile; these teachers consider the values as both framework through which they can plan the lesson and a guide to help them decide about the method that should be used and the content to be taught. Moreover, they agree that the list of the chosen values is important in shaping good citizen and effective member of the society. Moreover, these core values prepare individuals who are proud of their identity and belonging as well as their history, culture, and heritage. In addition to being ready to respect and protect the national symbols. Teachers 5 and 12 declared that these values are important and crucial but also have been imposed on teachers, which means the teacher has no role in deciding and designing what values should be taught and delivered to the students. T5 commented:

These values are good for the pupils, but they are much imposed, there should better be an opportunity for the teachers to choose the values to be taught in the classroom, because they know their students better, they know what they need. No one knows what actually happen in the classroom more than the teacher. For that reason, the imposed policies from stakeholders will never work unless, they consider taking into consideration the teachers feedback and evaluation of real-life teaching.

In the literature, this refers to as teachers 'agency and accountability, which means the teacher's role should not be limited to teaching only, but it has to have a part and an active role in the decision-making of curriculum design and curriculum reform by considering their feedback and evaluations of the real practices of teaching and the outcome of the policies. Interestingly the data gathered correlate strongly with many literature texts that criticize the systems where teachers are "passive recipients" rather than "investigators of innovation and change" (Harris, Jones and Huffman, 2017, p.1). Because teacher have crucial role in successful change and positive school system improvement (Hargreaves and Fullan, 2012). The literature declared that educational reforms' failure resulted from marginalising teachers' views and perspectives (Harris, Jones, Huffman, 2017).

[T12] added:

there should be an assessment of these values. The choice of these values with teachers, and then the teacher needs to assess them with the students, i.e. see how the students perceive these values, how they are benefiting from them and what are the consequences. Besides, there should be an evaluation to the

policy as a whole. Planning phase followed by assessment period. Not only that, but also this should be discussed with the administration principles and parent (parents association) and the teachers' syndicate.

The proposed idea by T12 is important as having regular discussion throughout the application process, which also should be as testing out of any policy. This helps to address gaps in the policy, resolve or eliminate issues and strengthen the implementation of the policy. In addition, it gives the teachers good platform where they can share their practices, knowledge, and resources. This finding resonates strongly with the theory of change by Fullan (2007). The change process according to Fullan, (2007) consists of three main phases. The first phase, initiation, where a decision for a change is made. Second, "the implementation" or the 'initial use' (the first 2 or 3 years) which is the first attempt of implementing this change and where the change will be examined and evaluated. The last stage is the 'continuation" where a decision to either proceed with the change or discard it, will be made.

On the Other hand, T9, T10, and T11 believed that the teaching of values is not a priority in their teaching practice, but sometimes could be seen as a starting point to choose the method of teaching and the focus of the lesson.

T9 affirmed:

As a teacher, I am interested more in how to make the lesson easier without giving much importance to the values. The lessons are long compared to the time we have and most of the time require focus to deal with, you cannot distract your focus by including other aspects like core values.

T10 complained:

The teacher life in Algeria is difficult, he is doing noble job, yet his contribution is overlooked and underappreciated. The salary of the teacher is the least, they are not well paid...we are not receiving proper support from administration or from the ministry. How can we teach values in situations like this. To teach values the classroom needs to be equipped also the programme has to be well studied and well designed.

T11 sharply declared:

values are a luxury to be considered in a class or in a system that has many challenges that should be better solved... crowded curriculum content, crowded classroom, lack of teaching aids and materials, shortage of time in addition to unclear reforms and many other issues which the educational system in Algeria is facing.

This data strictly contradicts with many research in the literature that are trying to highlight the necessity of teaching values as part of the school curriculum. According to the literature (Bills and Husbands, 2005) and (Thornberg and Oğuz, 2013) there is an increasing tendency of

research that are interested in educational values and their importance in various disciplines. Tonga (2016) for instance falls for the common idea that says, despite the modern era we live in, and the constant developments humans will always need established values to be understood.

However, the findings are also in accordance with some studies that indicate that teachers who do not prioritize teaching values may be more influenced by personal utility values such as salary, job security, and career status, as suggested by (Luen, 2022). These teachers may focus more on intrinsic rewards or personal benefits rather than societal contributions. Whereas there are teachers who value the teaching of values due to a strong desire to make a social contribution or give back to society, as highlighted in studies by (Watt and Richardson, 2007) and (Padhy et al., 2015). The findings signifies that there are factors that influence teachers' prioritization and valuation of the teaching of values besides the lack of teachers' agency and accountability in decision-making and the lack of effective communication between policymakers and teachers regarding the teaching of the core values policy, there are other personal and professional factors. For instance, lack of support and assistance from administration and policymakers as well as social factors. The findings underscore the necessity of offering professional supports to teachers mainly from policymakers and administration in regard to policies implementation. Besides, taking into account the social challenges and the challenging factors teachers might be facing which influence the quality of teaching practice and hinder the teachers from managing the effectiveness of instilling the core values on pupils in the classroom.

5.6 Some core values contradict with the students' culture.

Data from the online survey suggested that majority of teachers (20/64 agree and 8/64 strongly agree) agree that the core values introduced to be included in the curriculum represent and reflect the culture and the background of the country (Algeria). Whereas minority (11/64 disagree and 8/64 strongly disagree) believe that these values fail to reflect the culture and the background of Algeria. This strongly resonate with what has been raised by some teachers [T11, T7] during the interviews.

The data reported that some teachers [T11, T7] assuredly advocated that some introduced values do not match with learners' culture and contradict with their believes and background. [T11] explained in the lesson of the "past tense", there is an example of an English Grandmother who talks about her life before and at present where she tells different stories, the lesson also shows different pictures; these are different from what represent the Algerian society and what Algerians believe in. For instance, the lifestyle, way of clothing, dwellings, terms such as boyfriend/girlfriend, which do not reflect the beliefs of the Algerian society. I think this is important, as it is a way where the learner will be introduced to other cultures in terms of dwellings, traditions, food etc. However, the teacher can adjust or avoid what he thinks or believes is unnecessary or inappropriate which also mean the teacher should not follow the coursebook blindly instead adjust it according to the students' needs and principles. In line of this discussion, some teachers [T8, T11, T7,] reflected on what other values they prefer to be taught to their

students apart from national identity, citizenship, conscience, and openness to the world, which reflect the Hofstede (1989) model, which categorises values as national typology. Other values are religious values, wealth, loyalty, independence, equality, justice, fraternity, and friendliness. These values are in line with Schwartz (2006) egalitarianism orientation. Also, they linked with what has been found in the study of Gökçe (2021) where from teachers' perspectives, the most important five core values that the students should acquire at schools are "virtue, respect, affection, conformity, and sympathy" which also falls under egalitarianism orientation. This suggests that in most of the time the teachers support the students to acquire high level of egalitarian values.

Conclusion

This chapter answers the first research question "How do teachers perceive the values underpinning the second-generation curriculum?" The perspectives on the core values (national identity, conscience, citizenship and openness to the world) that were introduced to underpin the curriculum change, are polarized between two different positions, in terms of perceiving the meaning of these values, the rational of values inclusion in school curriculum, the aim of teaching these values to the students and prioritizing them in the daily teaching practices. The data suggested that there is a lack of consensus in teachers' perspectives on the meaning of these values and their place on the second-generation reform also not all teachers recognize the Rational of Including Core Values in the Curriculum. Not all teachers can effectively develop a sense of the aim behind teaching values, as a striking finding that some teachers perceive some values to contradict with the students' culture and finally, not all teachers value and prioritize the teaching of values in their daily practice in the classroom.

CHAPTER SIX

ENACTING THE VALUES Embedded in the Curriculum

Introduction

The data presented and discussed in this chapter will answer the second research question “how teachers engage with the core values in their daily practices in the classroom?” The findings resulted from the analysis of the questionnaire survey (total number 64) will be presented first in form of diagrams where teachers were asked to evaluate different statements according to Likert scale (strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree and strongly disagree), followed by interpretation of these data. Following that, findings resulted from the interviews (16 interviews) will be presented and discussed as well.

The findings are synthesised with the literature for better understanding and for the aim of answering the research question. The aim of the second research question is to find out how teachers teach and perform these values to their students, what methods, techniques or strategies they follow in their everyday teaching.

6.1 The Representation of the core values in the policy documents

Figure 05. The policy document provides teachers with the way to teach these values.

The findings from the online survey demonstrate, the number of those who agree (33%) and strongly agree, 4% strongly agree that the policy documents provide the teachers with ways and methods to teach these values is almost equal to the number of teachers 30% who disagree, 8% and strongly disagree that the policy documents tackle no methods or ways of teaching values in the classroom.

The data generated from the interviews also suggests that the teachers hold different opinions about the guidance in the PD in relation to enacting values in the classroom.

The finding linked closely to the teachers answers to previous statement “the policy document provides teachers with the way to teach these values” in which the teachers’ numbers between those who agree and disagree were almost identical. This mainly suggest that those who consider their process to be identical with what has been provided in the PD are those who suggest that initially the PD provide them with the ways to teach these values and consequently they follow the process as described in the PD and thus they ended up with identical process as described. However, those who disagreed that their process of teaching values being similar

to what has been provided in the PD are mainly those who initially disagreed about the PD provided or suggested any methods of interacting with these values in the classroom.

Group of teachers [T7, T5] believe that the PD provide instructions on how the values should be taught i.e., the content (lessons) is identified, the aim and objectives for each level are set. Also, each unit (different units mentioned in the student's textbook, for example, family, food...) is specified. All these help the teacher in the task of engaging with these values. Moreover, they are convinced that there is a congruence between how the process is described in the policy documents and how the process is accomplished in the classroom since the content, objectives and the aim were designed and decided by the policymakers, and thus the teacher task is just to conduct it the way it is described in the PD. As supported by [T7] "teachers only apply what the policymakers and the government decided to convey and what to be taught, in other words the teachers just translate the curriculum." [T5] Concluded:

the way these values were introduced and described in the policy documents for example and the type of activities suggested in the students' textbook deduced from real life situations i.e., examples deduced from Algerian society, famous national and international celebrities and figures are mentioned, besides common topics such as sport, travel, hobbies, food...; therefore, they are taught as real as possible.

Other teachers [T8, T14, T15] believe that although policy is important as it helps the school to establish rules and create standards of quality for learning and without these policies, the schools would lack the structure and the function necessary to provide the educational needs of the students but sometimes these policies are source of confusion. For instance, [T14] 'the policy documents address the values and methods to be taught, but in order for the decision to be made about the design of these values and teaching them in the class, the real-life classroom situation should be considered and well-studied'. On the other hand, [T15] claimed that 'policymaker do not have direct contact with students, only teachers do'.

[T8] believed that 'theory is different than practice, you cannot plan or decide about anything if you are not aware of the real situations of the classroom and the students.'

policymakers do not have access to real-life classroom, which made the plan ineffective in most of the time, this led to teaching values policy sounds practical and valid at theoretical level only. This is in line with what has been stated in the literature that too often in the school systems, policies are implemented without adequate consideration of the returns and outcomes and where teachers are in side-line and marginalized (Harris, Jones and Huffman, 2017). Moreover, in some cases, these documents complicate the task for teachers as believed by [T5] who claimed, "Some values cannot be manifested in the classroom as the documents implied." [T8] declared, "Teachers do not comply the instructions of the policy documents and they adjust it according to their students' needs, level and learning styles and strategies." T5 and T8 ideas resonate with what is referred to in the literature as "teachers' resistance", as they clearly show preference to maintain the old practice in their teaching (Giles, 2006). Besides disobeying the policy instructions (Achinstein and Ogawa, 2006; Giles, 2006; Van Veen et al., 2005).

There are also those who complained [T1, T4, T6] that the policy documents neither tackled the values clearly nor show how values should be taught. Compared what was claimed by [T7, T15] about their need for more guidance on how to conduct and perform these values in their practices, contradict with what has been argued by [T5, T8, T12] about the fact that the policy of teaching values, the chosen list of values and the suggested ways to conduct them in classrooms are imposed. They also feel they are compelled to follow the instructions. This suggests that there a tension among teachers between requests for more guidance and a desire for autonomy.

The data also suggested that these values are enacted or in other words, are taught implicitly, and the students are not aware that they are learning these values. The teachers believe that the reason policymakers want these values to be addressed implicitly is because they believe that the effective way through which values will be naturally acquired and maintained. The implicit mode of delivering a curriculum or certain aim in the curriculum is referred to as hidden curriculum (Kelly 2009; Arweck and Nesbitt 2004; Thornberg and Oğuz ;2013; Morales-Vives et al., 2013). This strongly matches Kelley's (2009) definition of the hidden curriculum, which according to him it is the things students learn in the school without them being conscious about.

6.2 Algerian EFL Middle School Teachers Perform Values through Being Role Model

Teachers play a pivotal role in modelling values and fostering a positive learning environment that promotes ethical behaviour and social cohesion among students (Brady, 2011). Several studies in the literature highlight the significance of teachers in promoting character education. (Muhtar and Dallyono, 2020). The Findings from the semi-structured interviews were in line with what has been discussed in the literature. The data suggested that “the role model” is the most common answer opted by teachers [T2, T6,T9, T11, T14,T16] which seem to be the optimal way through which they enact the embedded core values. T14 believed:

a role model means the teacher's behaviours and attitudes should reflect what he wants his students to acquire, moral values are more about what the students see rather than hear, it will be more effective for the students to see their teacher arriving on time, respecting his colleagues and doing his job sincerely, rather than spending hours teaching them about these. And maybe if the teacher is not doing what he says, the students would be confused about the contradiction that might happen.

T2 clarifies:

A teacher can play a good role model, through reflecting the right behaviours to his students, and these include honesty, showing respect to others, taking responsibility for one's actions, cooperation and caring, showing respect for the community components, whether it is culture, environment, religion...etc.

T6 Added:

the students are the reflections of their teachers i.e. the way the teacher acts, behaves and talks, is observed and evaluated by the student. Even in small acts that teachers may not pay attention to them. Many students like to imitate their teacher in the way he talks, in the way act maybe even in the way he dresses up. That is why, it is important for the teachers to be careful of his behaviour and attitude especially inside the school.

This finding resonates with what has been revealed in the study of Al-hooli and Al-shammari (2009) that the children are very good observers, therefore, teachers should reflect good attitudes and present ideal model.

T9 incorporates:

the role model in education is when a teacher makes his students influenced and inspired by her/his behaviours, the rapport he develops with them and the positive learning environment he creates for them help them to acquire and maintain good values and not only inside the classroom but outside and in real-life as well.

This definition influences relatively Dewey's idea (1902) that the students learn not only lessons in the curriculum or only learn inside the classroom but rather throughout the school. In another expression, teacher's behaviours and attitudes are an input to the students. However, the literature also criticizes the negative influence a teacher may have. As discussed in the study of Maphalala and Mpofo (2018) where there is a high concern raised by the parents in South Africa that despite values are taught explicitly, the students will not maintain them as some teachers fail to be role model and fail to represent good behaviour.

T16 believed:

teachers play a fundamental role in shaping students' moral and ethical growth; I believe that only parents and teachers can achieve this task successfully, because conveying the right values require non-verbal communication or instruction, it requires children to observe and maintain.

T16 made an interesting reference to the role of family and parents in instilling values, which has been widely discussed in the literature. For instance, the study of Zurqoni, Retnawati, and Apino, (2018) that stresses that teachers, along with other school members and parents, are key in implementing character education through role-modelling, character-oriented activities, and support from educational stakeholders.

6.3 Algerian EFL Middle School Teachers Enact Values through Authentic problem-solving situations.

Teachers play a crucial role in enacting values through authentic problem-solving situations in educational settings. Research suggests that to effectively guide students through problem-solving processes, teachers themselves need to engage in authentic problem-solving

experiences (Chahine, 2018). By understanding and experiencing authentic problem-solving scenarios, teachers can better facilitate similar experiences for their students (Chahine, 2018).

The data generated from semi-structured interviews revealed that authentic problem-solving situations is another method that is widely employed by the teachers [T7, T5, T1, T13, T7, T9] to engage with values in the classroom. T5 explained:

Authentic problem-solving situations is where the teacher put his students in real life situations to acquire new or used prior acquired values during which the students are asked to match what they have learnt with situations from their real life.

This is somehow similar to what is discussed in the study of Maphalala and Mpofu (2018) about the role-play and the case study as teaching methods. In the role-play, the learners are given a situation or a problem to which they have to respond by assuming a particular role. In the process, they are able to construct their own knowledge through exploration and problem solving.

T9 on the other hand believes:

Authentic problem-solving is to confront a situation which is related to real life and the students are required to find some solutions by using appropriate skills in an accurate way. This method encourages students' creativity, and the use of their reasoning skills to come up with a solution for specific situation.

T13 provided a detailed explanation on how he enacts the embedded values using the authentic problem-solving situation:

As a teacher I should put the learners in a real situation starting from the problem –solving situation which will be solved by the end of the sequence. each situation in every lesson. Learners in every lesson have a situation which is derived mainly from real life in a communicative way. Teacher should then start her/his lesson by warming up (presented a game either related or not to the topic of the lesson. Generally used to motivate learners in the lesson of articles using the topic of jobs and family members. After showing some pictures to present the topic of the lesson (pictures of some jobs and asking learners to match each job with its appropriate name with drilling), after that the teacher presents a situation. Ask the students some questions around the situation; What is the name of Peter's father /his job? What is the name of Peter's mother /Her job. This is an example of grammar lesson where the focus is on article. And the core values we should be focusing on is valuing the different jobs, valuing working, and to be proud of family members' jobs. At the end solving the situation by presenting Peter to the students (through images) and his family members.

Teachers' answers signifies that each teacher uses the same method of authentic problem-solving situation distinctively. The literature emphasizes the importance of diverse instructional methods such as authentic problem-solving skills among students, Authentic assessment is highlighted for its capacity to evaluate real-life

tasks and enhance learning outcomes in subjects like Science (Suastra, 2017). It has been demonstrated to enhance prospective teachers' problem-solving skills Kinay and Bağçeci (2016) and contribute to students' competence in problem-solving (Trang,2023).

6.4 Algerian EFL Middle School Teachers enact values through Story telling.

Teachers T1, T7, and T13 during the interviews declared that they also prefer to use the story telling strategy to teach their students the core values of national identity, conscience, citizenship, and openness to the world. [T13] added:

storytelling is another method commonly employed among the teachers where they prefer to tell stories about historical heroes, achievement of public figure or celebrity, or any story that tells the importance of collaboration for example, and other stories that inspire them to acquire a certain value.

This definition resonates with [T1] definition, “Storytelling: is a space for learners to express themselves freely and creatively in a real and authentic way.” This finding is also well-supported in the literature in the study of Al-hooli and Al-shammari (2009) who found that most values transferred during story telling activity as most teachers believe that this is the best way to teach moral values especially during early years education (fundamental schooling).

6.5 Algerian EFL Middle School Teachers enact values through Vivid examples/real life situation method.

The findings generated from the interviews signified that some teachers [T14, T7, T3] follow the vivid examples method to enact the core values in the classrooms. [T7] explains, “is somehow similar to storytelling method, but the teacher here should introduce a character or a situation that is well known to all students.” similar idea expresses by [T3], “vivid examples is showing and presenting a real and clear image to the mind of the students in a detailed way so that the students can reflect on what is intended to be explained.”

6.6 Values in Middle Schools Are Embedded in the Lessons of the English Language Curriculum

According to the findings generated from the interviews, the teaching of values in the Algerian EFL Middle School classrooms are conducted in a different way T12 explain:

the teachers while planning the lesson they need to write down the title of the lesson, the aim and objectives of the lesson and the target to be achieved at the end. Additionally, they choose one core value to be taught implicitly in the lesson, they also need to assign which skill among the four language skills they need to employ in teaching this core value, is it through listening, reading, speaking, or writing. This can be grammar lesson, vocabulary etc.

This data suggests that the values are enacted (implicitly taught to students) and also these values are embedded in the lessons, and they are not taught separately as an independent subject. Some teachers [T7] trust that the stakeholders embed these values or in other words, prefer the core values to be taught implicitly because they do not want the students to deal with these values as lesson to be learnt in the class. Instead, those core values should be built inside them i.e., permeated in the students; they should

be developed as part of their common sense, and should be firmed in their subconscious. This implicit method of teaching values was tackled in the literature, but the aim does not actually resemble the one targeted in the Algerian EFL middle school classrooms. For instance, Thornberg and Oğuz (2013) refer to the implicit method as the progressive/constructivist approach, where the learners are required to imply their reasoning, personal judgement, discussion, and interaction in order to arrive to the fair conclusion (Ferreira & Schulze, 2014; Kohlberg, 1981). The implicit method of teaching the core values as previously mentioned it represents what is referred to in the literature as hidden curriculum (Kelly 2009; Arweck and Nesbitt 2004; Thornberg and Oğuz ;2013; Morales-Vives et al., 2013). However, in the Algerian curriculum, the aim is not to make students deduce or arrive at the conclusion or in other words, what is the values to be taught, instead this is the intention of policy makers to foster these core values implicitly so that they will be firmed and permeated in the students.

Few teachers on the other hand believe that the implicit way that was imposed to teach these values is not effective, as they believe that values should be taught explicitly; the students need to be aware that they are learning values, and the target is to learn these values. Because these teachers believe that, the implicit way is not always effective and may confuse or mislead the students. Those teachers mainly support the direct explicit approach, which the literature refers to as the traditional and classical approach, which initially was introduced in the work of Durkheim (1961), and it supports the direct instruction of values by an adult (most of the time the teacher). The purpose of the traditional approach is the explicit transmission of values in order to assist learners in conforming to societal norms and rules (Jones, 2009). In addition, this approach offers the student an active role to deduce the values from the values transmission process (Nieuwenhuis, 2007).

The data also incorporated that according to the teachers [T8, T14], assessing these values can be through what teachers refer to as ‘the production’ where the students at the end will be asked follow-up questions about what they have understood, or through their writings (as assessment can be oral or written), in order to evaluate the students understanding on what has been taught.

6.7 The Critical Role of the Teacher in Promoting Values

The discussion raised during the interviews with the teachers manifested that some teachers [T7, T1, T2] believe that the teacher has crucial role to play while teaching values and he should not just maintain his usual way or task as a knowledge provider. It is worthwhile and crucial to employ some techniques and develop some awareness during this process to successfully ensure that the target achieved. These teachers criticize those who maintain no more than their usual task as in teaching any other grammar or vocabulary lesson. As they stated that, the teacher should not only focus on how to monitor the class, transfer the lesson, or only consider providing knowledge. Instead, the teacher has to develop a critical view or reflection on what should be other tasks they need to develop and implement while including a teaching of a core value in the lesson or when values are embedded in the curriculum. T7 stated:

the teacher needs to consider the students different backgrounds, interests, and needs, then he needs to adjust the values to fit with these, without a tension to raise values, that contradict with their own believes and principles, also he should aim to achieve what is intended to be achieved (the aim and objectives) through the lesson and values.

This is strongly resonated with what has been raised by other teachers previously that Algerian school is heterogeneous, and the classes contain students from different ethnic groups (Arab, Amazigh) thus the teacher should not be biased to one group rather than other, he/she also needs to be careful not to raise any values that may contradict with the believes of either group which may lead to a tension or a conflict. Yet the teacher should ensure the fair and equal opportunities in learning to all the students regardless of their origin, background, or culture.

Conclusion

This chapter answers the second research question, “How do teachers enact these values in their daily practices in the classroom?” The data gathered from both the questionnaire and interviews suggest that Algerian EFL Middle School teachers employ the following methods to enact values in their everyday teaching practice, role model, storytelling, authentic problem-solving situations, and vivid examples/real life situation method. Besides, the teachers also revealed that values in the middle schools are taught implicitly (enacted) as required by the policymakers. Moreover, those values are embedded in the curriculum. The teachers also reflected on the awareness a teacher should maintain along with implementing the right skills while enacting these core values in the classroom.

CHAPTER SEVEN

Challenges and Affordances of Enacting Values in the Curriculum

Introduction

This chapter presents the analysis of the data generated from both the online questionnaire-survey and the interviews regarding the third research question, “what are the challenges or the affordances if any, do teachers encounter during teaching the core values?” The themes appeared during the analysis are listed and some of them are supported by statistical data from the questionnaire. In the questionnaire the participants (64 participants) were asked to evaluate different statements according to a “Likert scale” by choosing among the following, strongly agree (SA), agree (A), neutral (N), disagree (D) and strongly disagree (SD). These statements are mentioned under each diagram (diagram title).

The data from the questionnaire will be presented graphically first, followed by an interpretation and a discussion of these data. Following this, the data generated from the interviews will also be presented and discussed. After these findings will be discussed in relation to the review of the literature in order to answer the research question.

The aim of the third research question is to find out whether the Algerian EFL Middle School teachers came across any challenges or encountered any affordance during their experience in teaching the core values of national identity, conscience, citizenship and openness to the world and what are they.

7.1 The Challenges

7.1.1 The SGC Reform Failure

Most teachers (13/16) throughout the interviews designate negative attitude toward the second-generation curriculum reform. [T11, T9] complained that many aspects about the reform were not effectively studied, starting from the rationale of introducing a new curriculum, the aim meant to be achieved and no new methods or ideas have been introduced. This closely correspond with [T5, T7], the reform did not look at the most important issues of time, complex curriculum content compared to students’ level, condensed classes, lack of teaching aids and materials. [T7] SGC does not solve previous curriculum and reforms limitations. [T5] SGC does not address teachers and students needs [T6]. [T1] considers the educational system in Algeria as being inconsistent. He believes that there is a regionalism between schools in the north being well equipped and create better learning environment compared to those in the south and rural areas, where still teachers and students have to walk miles and sometimes in very harsh weather conditions to get to their schools. He believes that it is ironic to teach these students about nationality and citizenship after all that. He added that true reform should look at these concerns first, creating safe learning place to children, occupy the schools, providing school transportations. These are of high priority from introducing gibberish policies that

barely bring any benefits to the students or the system as whole. [T12] believes that this will have negative consequences, for example, the budget or public resources that has been wasted in this project could have served another well studied reform, also a policy failure may lead families and citizens to lose confidence and patience in the stakeholders and schooling system as whole. As explained by [T11] who trusts that changes to curriculum structure rarely offers any gain. As there is no evidence that making changes to a curriculum result in any positive outcomes, because all efforts go into planning and structure, then what is encountered in real life classrooms is different. This requires a re-designing and re-planning and usually in the nuances that the gain come, and these will not be seen until much further down the line [T7].

Some teachers [T7, T11] criticize the word reform as they are convincing this policy was not in any sense of radical change or attempted to elimination previous curriculum' limitations and issues. [T7] declared, "I cannot call it a reform, as nothing has been changed. The teaching approach remains the same which is the CBA, and the values were already there in previous curriculums." This idea is in line with Taba's (1962) definition of the curriculum as he sees it as "the amorphous product of generations of tinkering." [T9] added "this curriculum change is poorly managed in many levels, the schools environments, the lack of ITC in school where the students are supposed to be introduced to some authentic situations, prepare them to integrate in a modern society, rehearse their communicative skills to be used in different virtual platforms. According to him, a successful reform needs to consider the following conditions, effective management for the school environment and space, developing effective methods of teaching which can be maintained through effective teachers' training programs.

7.1.2 Teachers' Training Programme

Figure 06. There was an effective training for this reform.

The data generated from online survey signifies that the majority of teacher 26/64 (disagree) 10/64 (strongly disagree) have negative attitude toward the training they received, whereas 13/64 (agree) and only 3/64 (strongly agree) hold positive attitude as for the training they received as been effective.

The graph reflects teachers' perspectives on the training, more precisely in relation to aspects related to the core values and teaching them in the classroom. As it is noticeable, the majority (total of 63%) between those who disagree and totally disagree that the training effectively tackled the teaching of the core values. In the other hand, 33% agree and only 4% strongly agree that actually the training did tackle values and effectively prepared them for teaching values.

The data from both graphs deliver same result, although there is an absence of consensus between teachers' answers on whether the training was effective and whether it covers the teaching of values, hence the majority reflect negative attitude toward it.

The data reflected in the questionnaire is in agreement with those reported in the interviews. Another challenge notified by the teachers during the interviews was the training. The teachers [T1,5,7,11] expressed their disappointment about the training they received, as they believed the training should focus on the new reform and the policy of teaching values within the school curriculum. However, the training was about a general teaching and learning methods and strategies. [T5] "I expect the training to cover some pedagogical exchange and methods on teaching values, but it was about general teaching concerns".

Some of them [T9, T13, T15] claimed that the training did very little in regard to introducing these core values to the curriculum but still this considered much more theoretical, and nothing mentioned about how these should be conducted in the classroom. Others [T1, T5, T7, T11] in the other hand, complained about the training being very much general and did not tackle the core values in any way. There were also those who denied having any training [T7]. For example, [T5] declared, some aspects were covered in the training as inclusive education and other aspects that are far from being possibly implemented in real life classes.

7.1.3 Family Interferes in the Process of Fostering Values in the School

Only two teachers [T6 and T7] during the interviews they mention "family" as a factor interfering the process of teaching values to the students. Both of them agreed that they do not support the teaching of values to children at early age, as they believe they are too dependent to their families and parents, and closer to them. This suggest strong resonance with (Bozkurt,

2010) when insisting that children come from different backgrounds and learn in distinct ways at home thus what to be delivered at schools may contradict with the family values. Similar idea expressed by (Karabacak and Nermin, 2021).

[T6] Explained, the children spend most of their time with their families; the relationship and the strong feelings they have toward their families, results in the children imitating them, listening and obeying their instructions impulsively. Thus, if the teacher attempt to teach or deliver any value, believe or a principle that may not be in accordance with what this child is used to at home, he may have strong reaction toward it which may result in discomfort, losing interest in the lesson, the subject and why not the school as whole. This finding is in line with Tonga's (2016) who claimed, the family is considered as the starting point of values education, it is the foundation of all upbringings, and where an individual's educational journey begins.

[T7] Trusts that the school and more precisely the teacher, their role should be delivering knowledge in the first place, also there is no harm in reflecting on good deeds and behaviours from time to time. For instance, honesty, caring about others, respect, friendship but not to go far with it to include topics that have to do with religion, culture or identity for example.

The literature reports the lack of consensus between studies concerning the role the family has in transferring values. There are those who highly support the family contribution in fostering values and they believe it has positive impact (Aspin, 2007) and (Ozoliņš, 2010). As opposed to this belief, other studies for instance (Aktepe et al., 2020; Çelik, 2020) and (Karabacak and Nermin, 2021) trust that family contribution has negative influence which may contradict with the school's aim.

Another group hold the belief that there should be a collaboration between the school and the family in transferring and fostering values. As the values-learning process begun informally at home and carried out formally in schools (Yazıcı, 2006). Besides it is important to mention that individual education is greatly influenced by both the family and the school as this cooperation between them is critical in students' academic, social, and personal development (Kocabaş, 2006).

7.1.4 Teachers Reflect on their own Values while Engaging with the Core Values

During the interviews, the findings suggest that some teachers [T5, T6 and T7] reflect their own values and believes while teaching i.e., in many situations the teacher's own values influence what he is teaching and how he teaches as well. [T6] revealed, "I prefer to give religious examples while teaching the core values, as I believe those provided in the curriculum do not match the students' culture and religion." This is similar to what has been declared by

[T7] that some content in the curriculum, especially which deals with “openness to the world” where there are examples of other religions, examples of non-Arab and non-Muslim characters, [T7] believes that it is not appropriate to deliver this content to the students and especially at this early age. As at this early age the personality of the student is still not fully built, thus he can easily be dragged and tricked. Therefore, [T7] declared that he avoids giving these examples and prefer to adjust the content to what he thinks is appropriate.

[T5] in the other hand, believes that there are many examples in the student’s textbook and curriculum about politicians and political figures. According to him, this can be biased, as he perceives this as an attempt to deceive the students toward specific party. This is in line with what has been claimed by [T10] that the recurrent school reforms and changes signifies that the school nowadays are becoming a stage where policymakers are setting policies to work their aims. [T5] added “I try to keep my students away from all these and give examples about other things for instance; cartoons or enemies as I believe these create more fun and help students learn better.”

The data signifies that the teacher’s personality believes, and values influence his professional preferences, this can be another factor that challenge the teaching of values, especially when it is introduced as a policy requirement where everything is imposed (content and structure). This strongly resonates with what the literature has found; someone’s values reflect his decisions and reflections (Harland & Pickering, 2011). For that reason (Gökçe, 2021) highlighted the importance of the preservice teachers’ training to examine the existing values they carry. Because throughout preservice education, the teachers’ professional values and beliefs, which they have acquired since childhood, are strengthened, or changed (Lortie, 2002; Zeichner & Gore, 1990).

7.1.5 Lack of Teachers’ Agency and Accountability

Figure 07. I was involved in the decision-making of this reform.

The data generated from the online survey (figure.12) signifies that the vast majority of teachers 44% strongly disagree and 31% disagree about being involved in a decision making of any reform.

The interview data in the other hand revealed that all teachers (16/16) never been involved in the decision of any reform and their perspectives never been considered. [T7] revealed many things are imposed on us as teachers, curriculum content, strategies, even the planning of the

lesson. [T8] added, a reason many teachers do not support curriculum reforms and most new introduced policies, is it because they are always ignored during the design stage. [T3] I highly recommend considering teacher's feedback because no one knows the learner better than the teacher does. No one can give a practical feedback, limitations, and suggestions than teachers [T11] teachers are the ones who have direct contact with the students, they best know about them; their learning styles, their needs, strengths and weaknesses. Consequently, sometimes the teachers have to changes some aspects in the lesson or the curriculum according to what suit the students. As previously mentioned, in the literature this refers to "teachers' agency and accountability" which considers the teacher as change agent that should participate in a decision making of curriculum/school reforms and changes. There is considerable literature that support this view for instance, (Harris, Jones, Huffman, 2017), (Hargreaves and Fullan, 2012).

Both data generated from the questionnaire and interviews conclude that EFL Middle School teachers in Algeria do not have a role in designing curriculum content and methods of teaching neither their perspectives are considered in the decision making of curriculum reform. In other words, the teachers' agency and accountability is not considered in the school-context in Algeria.

7.1.6 Teachers Resist the SGC Reform

Different statements from teachers signify there is a resistance toward the SGC in general and the teaching of values in particular. For instance, the fact that the policies being imposed, the lack of effective training, no support from stakeholders. Teachers being more concerned about delivering a lesson without considering the core values. Teachers who do not prioritise the values in their teaching. Teachers considering values-inclusion to be a luxury in an educational system that is full of challenges. Those who trust that some values contradict with their students' culture and background. Teachers whom they adjust the content and the methods of teaching according to their own choices and preferences. Those who declared that neither the rational nor the aim of values-inclusion curriculum are clear. Also, those who declared that SGC reform failed in every aspect.

Initially, almost all the mentioned reasons in this study have been already reported in the literature, which signifies that the experience of the EFL Middle school teachers in Algeria is similar to the experiences of teachers in other parts of the world. First of all, the literature considers "teachers' resistance" as a sign of a policy or a reform failure (Zimmerman, 2006). The resistance acts enable the teachers to reject the imposed policies and programmes, or other instructions contradict their teaching' principles and believes (Achinstein and Ogawa, 2006; Giles, 2006; Van Veen et al., 2005). One of the most motive behind teachers' resistance which also has been reported by my participants is when a reform fails to set a clear reason and aims of the change (Greenberg & Baron, 2000) as this affect teachers' willingness to support and accept the change (Greenberg & Baron, 2000). In addition, the experience of former failure or unsuccessful reform may develop wary for teachers to accept any further attempt for a new reform (Greenberg & Baron, 2000).

Talking about teachers 'agency, Troudi and Alwan (2010) revealed that the fact that teachers are excluded from curriculum design and development affect teachers negatively as this is a reflection of the authoritative top-down policy, which made teachers resist the policy

instructions. Some others claim that introducing a new reform could be challenging for teachers. Thus, they prefer proceeding with the old strategy.

7.1.7 Teachers Lack Interest in Teaching Values

Through the data resulted from the interviews, it appears that another most challenging factor the teachers may face while delivering values-inclusion curriculum is when the teacher has no interest in teaching values. [T1, T9 and T11] represent an example of that. [T9] declared, “The focus is more on how I deliver my lesson without paying attention to these values.” [T11] agreed that teaching values is a luxury to be considered in a programme that has other challenges and should better be solved. [T1] these core values of national identity, conscience, citizenship and openness to the world has always been considered while designing the school curriculum, when selecting the content of the curriculum and the students already know that they need to proud of their identity, culture and represent their country in a good way. Besides maintaining good behaviours and good deeds are already taught at home, thus [T1] believes including these in the curriculum has no crucial significance.

This finding correlates with what has been reported earlier that teachers also differs on the way they value and prioritize the teaching of the core values.

Reflecting on teachers’ responses, what may lead to teachers lacking interest in teaching values is that, first, imposed and forced policies. Second, teachers not participating in decision-making also lack clarity for the rational and aim of why to teach these values. In addition, some values may not reflect teachers’ own values and preferences or do not reflect their students’ background and culture.

7.1.8 Language Teacher is Always Involved in Teaching Values

Some teachers [T2, T6, T8, T10,] believe that language teacher always teach values, because a language is not only about learning vocabulary and grammar of this language, but also about the lifestyle, culture, and values, thus they see that the relationship between the two is integral and inseparable. Regardless of whether this will be maintained implicitly or explicitly, whether is a policy requirement, values are always included in teaching a language.

[T2] confirmed:

The teacher of language by the very nature of their course, they teach values. The language we learn and speak impact the way we think and how we see the world, how we live out the lives. When students learn a second language, they learn more than words or language. They learn about culture, lifestyle, and how to accept differences. The values should be taught and focused on are the values that allow the students to be open, tolerant, respect and accept these culture but at the same time reassuring to maintain their own.

T2 claim resonate with T10, as he trusts that when the students learn a foreign language, they mainly use this language to communicate with foreigners (speakers of that language) usually people communicate about common topics for instance, weather, food, traditions. In the first place they need to introduce themselves, their identity, nationality, country, traditions, culture and sometimes believes. During which value will interfere, and it is important that these values should have been maintained correctly, a person (a student) should be open to accept the others

while still adhere to his own. Thus, this is the target the schools and the language teachers should aim to achieve.

Similar idea communicated by T8 about integrating the values of national identity, conscience, citizenship, and openness to the world in teaching of English as second/foreign language in the Algerian Middle Schools, help in leading the learners to what is called “language and culture tolerance” this means the student will be open toward learning foreign languages and cultures. This will enable them to be entitled to use this language in different social contexts, while traveling, in social media platforms, while studying abroad. This results in the students being embedded in the culture (no gap that prevent him from integrating and communicating with others) but without falling in “acculturation”.

In the other hand [T6] believes that considering the teaching of values in EFL class benefits the students through “the consistency in practice, inside and outside the classroom” i.e. talking about hobbies, memories, and friendship. Those common topics that are widely consumed by social media users.

7.2 Affordance/ Coping Strategies

The data gathered through interviews signifies that the teachers highlighted no affordances encountered throughout their experience in enacting the core values, instead they developed some coping strategies that help them minimize the effect of the numerous challenges they are facing. For example, the use of social media as a source to help in their teaching practices, collaboration between the teachers and organizing different academic events such as study days and seminars.

7.3 Social Media Helps the Teachers in their Experience of Engaging with Values

The social media platforms and other online resources is a common coping strategy famous among teachers [T5, T6, T8, T9]. According to some [T5, T6] the forums and platform that are voluntary created on social media enable the teachers to share their experiences, thoughts, methods or even raising a discussion on common concerns and challenges in approaching the core values in the classrooms. This finding resonates with what has been communicate by [T11], teachers sometimes do not find the appropriate guidance in the policy documents or programme, thus they resort to other online resources and materials as these are considered to be more helpful and do the job in most of the time. Similar idea claimed by [T9], most teachers will tell you that they do not rely on the teachers’ guide or curriculum textbook to prepare the lesson, instead they use supportive programme or software, which means these documents are not providing the right guidance.

Another teacher [T8] claimed a different use of ICT. In the area of values-mastery assessment, he trusts that SGC provides more flexibility in the way of assessment and evaluation, where the emphasis will continue to shift away from paper-pencil tests to “more authentic

assessments” of curriculum mastery i.e. more emphasis on assessments of the products of students’ performances and portfolios throughout the academic year.

7.4 Teachers Collaboration Helps in Sharing knowledge on How to deal with Values in the Classroom.

[T12] Stated that there is collaboration between them and their colleagues within the school. The aim of this collaboration is to share concerns related to the teaching in general and teaching values in specific, [T6] “we share, lesson plans as it helps in exchanging ideas, lesson handouts, the flashcards. Besides, we attend with each other at least once a week. Also, we discuss the tests and exams topics and questions.” Similar idea expressed by [T4], there is what we call “internal meetings” where novice teachers (mainly) meet with the inspector, during which the inspector observes the teacher presenting the lesson, at the end they have meeting where he comments on his performance and provide recommendations, guidelines, or critics. [T9] added the “Joint teaching” where a group of teachers (of the same subject) attend with one of them in his class while teaching, at the end they will have group discussion in terms of strengths, weaknesses, what works well and what requires improvements, also this sometimes comes as training for the internal meeting.

7.5 Workshops, Study days, Seminars help Teachers in Developing Ways on how to Engage with Values

[T4, T5,T8,T9,T11] Organizing these academic events allow the teachers to discuss the limitations of their practices in teaching values and the challenges as well, since the training some of us had, did not address our concerns and the specific matters we have in regard to the new policy of teaching values. This initiative is voluntary organized by some teachers, is not part of the programme, curriculum, or policy.

[T 9] added, there are many objectives for these academic events, among which, help teachers to understand this policy of including these values within the school curriculum, give the teachers the opportunity to talk about their teaching experiences, exchange information and ideas related to the teaching of values. In addition, enable teachers to talk about their challenges and difficulties, discuss the methods used to perform these core values, seeking to develop these methods and suggesting more so teachers can vary in their teaching strategies and methods. Also, discussing the students’ product and evaluating the outcome.

Conclusion

This chapter answers the third research question, “what are the challenges or the affordances if any, do teachers encounter during teaching the core values?” The teachers highlighted number of challenges they encounter while experiencing the new policy of values inclusion in the curriculum that was introduced as part of the second-generation curriculum reform. For instances, The SGC reform failed to meet the effective reform requirements and failed to address the teachers and the students’ needs and expectations, the teachers’ training did not meet the teachers’ expectations and the family’s role in transferring values to their children which sometimes considered as having negative influence. In addition, the teachers own values sometimes reflect and influence their teaching of these core values, the fact that teachers are not part of the policymaking resulted in many of them resisting policies and curriculum reforms and lack of interests in these values inclusion from both teachers and students.

In the other hand, the teachers affirmed that they did not encounter any factors that they could perceive as affordances, instead they developed some coping strategies to help them deal with this new introduced policy also to achieve the target of successfully delivering these core values. Among these coping strategies, social media, and online resources that teachers rely on while planning the lesson, collaboration between teachers help in sharing concerns and challenges related to teaching values. Moreover, the teachers volunteer to organize different academic events as, workshops, study days, seminars help teachers for the aim of discussion common challenges and difficulties related to the teaching of values, seek assistance from other teachers and experts, discuss the different methods in use and possible ways to develop enhance these. Last but not least the teachers. Finally, the findings also signifies that some teachers believe that a language teacher always teaches values even without attempting to, as they trust that a language is not only about grammar and vocabulary, it rather a culture and values.

Chapter Eight

Conclusion

8.1 Summary of the process

This study of exploring the experience of how Algerian EFL teachers engage with the core values that were introduced to Middle School curriculum attempted to investigate the teachers' understanding and perspectives toward these core values. Besides, investigating how teachers interact and enact these core values during their teaching in the classroom. In other words, to identify what methods, mediums, and techniques are employed by the teachers to address the values. Furthermore, the current study aimed at identifying the difficulties and challenges or any other factors that EFL teachers might encountered during their experience in engaging with the values. Also, to identify the affordances if any or supportive factors that might helped the EFL teachers during this experience.

The process went through theoretical and empirical stages, the starting point was to familiarize myself as a researcher of the research topic what I know about the chosen topic and what do I need to know. Exploring materials in the Algerian context, some policy documents that tackled the recent reform of the Second Generation curriculum, the initial idea I had for the research was to investigate the reform, deepening my reading resulted in the fact that the idea was general and vast as the reform contains many factors a researcher can tackle for instance, curriculum content, students textbook, policymakers perspectives, students' learning experience in the new reform, teachers perspectives, teaching methods, each of these ideas can be investigated as independent study. The task then was to find out a gap that needs to be addressed. Consulting Algerian literature related to the recent reform showed that some ideas have already been consumed by researchers and educators such as, the factors affecting the implementation of the new reform (Boudouaia, 2022), the CBA (Bader and Hamada, 2015), the teaching methods in the new reform, the textbooks (Selougi, 2020), a comparative textbooks analysis in the new reform (Selama, 2018). Besides exploring students and teachers' experiences in the new reform (Derrahi, 2021) However there was a crucial idea that captured my attention about an important factor not being explored which is the introduction of the core values of identity, national conscience, citizenship and openness to the world which policymakers announced it to be main contribution of the new reform (Chenni, n.d), this factor was highly valued by policymakers and gained great focus. Reading through these materials helped to develop the background and a context of the study as well as to find the gap in the literature in the Algerian context, yet this was preliminary idea.

At that early stage my reading was progressive, familiarizing myself of key terms that the study covered such as education, curriculum, education policy, curriculum reforms and innovation, then gradually started to be narrowed and more precise. After setting the research questions, aim, and objectives the idea of the research became more clearer, and the focus of the study was more narrowed and precise. The following step required being selective about the materials that need to go in the literature review chapter. For instance, the importance of values education, methods of teaching values, challenges of introducing the teaching of values in the school curriculum and teachers' perspectives to values education.

In order to address the gap, answer the research questions, and meet the research aim and objectives, an empirical study was conducted. Based on the research questions and the aim of the study, the study is framed by social constructivism and interpretivism as it focused on human beings and their interaction with external world in social life where their experience is taking place (Gray, 2009). Therefore, the meaning and knowledge are generated and constructed by participants socially and people come to know about this reality through their contacts with others. In addition, people construct knowledge and reality; this means there is multiple interpretations of this reality where it is up to the social context to define the attempted meaning. Thus, people have different interpretations of meaning and this supports the use of the interpretivism approach.

the qualitative approach was chosen as it supports the aim and the nature of the study of exploring EFL teachers' perspectives and lived experience of engaging with the core values. This approach enables the researcher to get deep understanding of a phenomenon as experienced by several individuals, hence the researcher in the current study collected data from individuals who have experienced the same phenomenon, developed a composite description of the essence of the experience of these individuals (EFL Middle School teachers), then interpreted the meaning of the participants' lived experience (Creswell and Poth, 2018). The participants recruited in this research were Algerian EFL Middle school teachers, first because the Second-Generation curriculum reform focused on teaching/learning English language, in addition, the researcher has access to the language repertoire as I have been both an English language learner and teacher. Moreover, my area of interest in Education more precisely, the teaching of English as foreign language.

Two tools of the data collection employed in this study, the online survey, and the semi-structured interviews. The online survey was conducted for the aim of contextualizing the data and developing initial understanding of the data related to teachers' awareness, understanding and attitudes toward the policy of the core values and interacting with values in the classroom. Interviews, on the other hand were crucial in investigating attitudes, beliefs, and perceptions, through including open-ended questions (Corbetta, 2003). Therefore, for the aim of exploring EFL teachers' perception on enacting values, interviews were optimal to use. The online survey resulted from a larger population of 64 participants, whereas 16 teachers took part in the semi-structured interviews. The data resulted from the online survey were assessed descriptively. Whereas thematic analysis using NVIVO (version 12) software were implemented to analyse the findings resulted from the interviews. The findings were classified thematically according to the research questions and aims where the data for each research question were analysed, interpreted, and discussed in separate chapters which resulted in three discussion chapters named respectively, perceiving the core values, enacting the core values, and challenges and affordances of engaging with core values.

8.2 Summary of the findings

The current research that studied the experience of Algerian EFL teachers in engaging with the core values embedded in the Middle School curriculum is crucial and valuable as it will have significant contribution to the knowledge in the field of values education in national Algerian context and global context. Besides this study will have important implications to be considered by future researchers, educators, policymakers in Algeria, and EFL Middle School teachers.

In the Algerian context this pioneer study will have unique contribution and implications in the area of values education in the Middle Schools curriculum as it voices the teachers views and believes about the policy of embedding values which later on can be considered by the teachers themselves, policymakers and educators. Besides the study will contribute to raise awareness of the necessity of values education. A reference and a source of a discussion of the different methods that might help the teachers to transmit the core values. The current study will contribute to reduce the effects of the limitations and constraints of the reform and the policy of embedding values on teachers, through highlighting some possible supporting strategies that both policymakers and teachers can adopt. The research provides an overview and understanding of the teachers experience which might be considered by teachers of different subjects. Thus, the study will enhance the teachers experience in interacting with values in the classroom and it will help in the quality of values education in the Algerian Middle Schools, which would be reflected and influenced in better practices by teachers and promoting the essential values in the students. The study will help the researchers through identifying the various study areas that need to be explored and investigated. On the other hand, the school principals, trainee teachers and educators will benefit from the findings of the current study by reflecting on their role in the process of promoting values in students and how can they have positive role in helping teachers throughout this experience.

At global context, the current study will contribute to the existing body of the literature in values education, teachers' perspectives on teaching values, teachers' perspectives on the introduction of values in school curriculum, teachers' experience in engaging and enacting values in the classroom by exploring the of Algerian context in a research study and by providing new results from a new context. Therefore, the implications of the findings can be considered by researchers in other contexts. This study will inform the existing literature in three main area understanding teachers' views, beliefs, and perspectives about values that are introduced to be taught as part of the taught curriculum in schools. In addition, understanding different methods that teachers employ to promote and engage with values. Furthermore, this research elucidates some problematic aspects concerning the intended challenges that teachers may face during their experience in interacting with values in classrooms.

8.2.1 Algerian EFL Middle School teachers' perspectives of the core values

The first part of the discussion aimed to answer the first research question:

How Algerian EFL Middle School teachers perceive the core values underpinning the Second-Generation curriculum?

The findings suggested that according to the Algerian EFL Middle School teachers, these core values of 'identity, national conscience, citizenship, and openness to the world do not foreground the SGC reform. Although the policy documents (The Official Bulletin, 2008; MPN, 2016; teachers' guide) focus largely on the introduction of these values to the school curriculum and afford them an equal priority as pedagogical competencies (cross-curricular competencies and communicative competencies), yet teachers believe that the SGC focuses more on the CBA approach, enhancing students' autonomy, and promoting the students' communicative abilities in English language. Moreover, they believe that these values have been always considered in the school curriculum as the topics and activities that are included in the curriculum have always included stories from the history of Algeria, national heroes, supporting the students to be proud of their identity and to preserve the national heritage of

their country. This signifies that policymaker and teachers do not value the introduction of these core values in the curriculum in the same way. However, it is worth mentioning that few teachers (3/16) who participated in the semi-structured interviews believe that the values underpin and foreground the SGC reform as the reform and policymakers explicitly name them “core values” and they focused largely on promoting these values in the students in the school also they added that these values are mentioned in the official policy documents such as, (the Official Bulletin, English Language Programme and the teacher’s guide), in addition, the teachers were introduced to the concept of values and the mentioned list of values either during workshops or during teachers’ trainings.

The teachers perceived the meaning of the term ‘values’ in different ways. T2 for example, defined values as ‘collective conceptions of what is considered good, desirable, and proper or bad and undesirable and improper within the context of certain culture.’ The teacher’s definition is in line with the definitions provided by Schwartz (2011) and (Shaver and Strong, 1976) which also according to them values are the standards by which society members assess concepts, judge ideas, items, people, events, and acts as good, worthwhile, desirable, wrong, worthless, or undesirable. In addition, T3 believed that values are “kind of morals and principles which should be set in every lesson plan.’ T7 on the other hand, stated that ‘values are the principles we should encourage our students to maintain.’ T11 affirmed that ‘values are ethics.’ T13 definition is compatible with T3 definition, she declared that ‘values are set of principles that the teacher needs to consider in designing the lesson’. Thus, this signifies that each individual develops his unique understanding of a concept or a phenomenon and perceived it from different angle according to his background, interest, as some of them related it more precisely to their teaching profession others for example may perceived the concept in moral sense.

Concerning the rationale behind introducing the values to the school curriculum, data revealed that there is no consensus among teachers’ perspectives on what is the rationale of embedding values in the curriculum. Supporting this discussion by the findings from the online survey where results demonstrated that, the percentage of teachers who are familiar with the rationale behind introducing values to school curriculum is 33% agree and 3% strongly agree. Whereas 33% disagree and 5% strongly disagree. However, 29% remained neutral. T11 underlined that the rationale of including values in the curriculum is:

to promote national and universal values, to develop students’ critical thinking, tolerance, and openness to the world, to contribute to the shaping of a good citizen that is aware of the changes and challenges of the modern society.

Furthermore, T15 proclaimed:

Algeria has large population of different ethnic groups, for instance, Arab, Amazigh (Kabyle, Shawiya) each group has a different linguistic repertoire, different culture, traditions and beliefs, in most of the time this creates kind of conflicts and disputes between them. So these values were announced to create a unity between these different ethnic groups.

Similarly, an agreement between teachers’ perspectives of the aim of embedding core values in the Middle School curriculum could not be reached. Some of them believe that the aim as it mentioned in the policy documents ‘...is to develop communicative competences and skills, through engaging learners in real life problem-solving contexts and situation integration.’ Said T7. Similar idea expressed by T3 who believe that ‘the aim is to learn about values and apply

them in real life.’ The findings from the online survey also revealed that most teachers 42% agreed and 11% strongly agreed that the aim is not clear or in other words is hard to recognize. Whereas 22% disagreed and 3% strongly disagreed about the aim being unclear (which means for them the aim is clear).

According to the data, the factors that helped those teachers who seem certain about the rationale and the aim of the policy of embedding values in the school curriculum to develop this awareness and understanding are, either teachers’ training where they have been introduced to the values, the aim and the rationale. Also, collaboration between the teachers where they had the opportunity to discuss this policy and its potential scope. Experience on the other hand also have a role to play, as experienced teachers seem to be more aware of the intentions of the policymakers when introducing policies. Commitments and professional skills help some teachers to be more reflective and show high abilities in adapting with new introduced policies and make use of the materials provided. However, teachers believe that it is not always possible to assess whether the aim has been achieved or not i.e., if the value is about daily behaviour for instance ‘respecting others, respecting the teachers’, this can be observed and assessed whereas if the value is about citizenship or identity, which their practices cannot be observed in the classroom as they are maintained more in real-life or in other words outside the classroom, in this case, it is not possible to evaluate whether the aim has been achieved or not.

Teachers’ answers signified that although the policy of embedding values in the school curriculum was introduced by the policymakers and this was supported in the policy documents, some teachers are still unable to develop clear understanding of these values, they still seem uncertain about the aim and the rationale behind this policy. They declared that this is due to unclear instructions provided in the policy documents and also because of the fact that they are not part of the decision making of this policy, also because of the lack of clear and direct communication between teachers and policymakers. The only means of communication between the teachers and policymakers are, policy documents, official documents, inspectors, and trainee teachers. However, even the training programme for some teachers did not tackle the policy of embedding values, therefore this resulted in teachers being unable to understand many aspects about this policy of embedding values in the curriculum.

The data revealed a dissonance between the Algerian EFL Middle School teachers’ perspectives on valuing and prioritizing the practice of these values in the classroom. Therefore, some of them consider these values as a necessity to be considered in the curriculum and to be promoted in the students who are the future generation of this country. In addition, it is crucial that students maintain these values that will help them to develop a good character and to be a good citizen who will contribute to the development of the society. Whereas others strictly declared that they are more concerned and focused on the lesson and whether the lesson is understood by the students without giving importance to promoting values. The latter group believe that the school is not the right place for teaching values as values can be maintained within the family as it more relevant for the child especially at this early age where they are more attached to their parents and family thus the process of promoting values will be more efficient rather than in schools where the values that are introduced in the school may contradict with what has been fostered at home or the teacher who is in charge of transmitting values believe in different set of values. Besides, the teachers are more concerned about the educational system, the curriculum and their challenges for instance, crowded classes,

condensed curriculum content, time constraint, lack of teaching aids and materials. Therefore, the general atmosphere of the class does not help in transferring values.

The findings disclosed that some teachers perceive some values to contradict with the students' culture precisely those lessons that introduce foreign cultures to the students in the unite of 'openness to the world' as these lessons have too many aspects that do not match with the students' culture and do not reflect the students neither cultural nor religious background, thus those teachers perceived them as extraneous.

8.2.2 Algerian EFL Middle School teachers experience in enacting core values in the classroom.

The second part of the discussion tackled the analysis, presentation of findings, and discussion of the data related to the second research questions:

How Algerian teachers enact the core values underpinning the Second-Generation curriculum?

The findings revealed that there is no agreement between the Algerian EFL Middle School teachers concerning the representation of core values in the policy documents in relation to providing ways or methods of enacting these values in the classroom. Some teachers claimed that the PD tackled values clearly and provide ways to enact them whereas others affirmed that PD do not provide any practical guide on how this should be done.

The findings revealed that the core values of identity, national conscience, citizenship, and openness to the world are embedded across the curriculum in all the fields (modules) and are not taught separately or as independent subject. Besides the core values are implicitly taught to the students i.e., the students are not aware that they are learning or required to learn these values. Algerian EFL Middle school teachers employ different methods to engage with these values in the classroom for instance, through authentic problem-solving situations, storytelling, vivid examples/real life situation method. Moreover, the teachers believe that values can effectively be transferred through teachers being role model, as the teacher have critical role to play in the process rather than being knowledge provider or curriculum translator.

8.2.3 The Challenges and Affordances encountered by teachers while engaging with values.

The last part in the discussion aimed to answer the third research question:

What are the challenges or affordances, if any, the teachers encountered while enacting the core values underpinning the Second-Generation curriculum?

The findings disclosed so many, fundamental challenges and constraints that have been reported by the teachers where the affordances were hard to identify. However, the main affordance was the willingness and motivation of the teachers themselves which resulted in developing some coping strategies that could overcome the effect of the constraints.

Among the challenges that have been encountered by the teachers and which obstructed them from successfully engaging with the values are the SGC reform failure as they believe that the reform neither meet their requirements nor addressed their needs and expectations, also did not consider the constraints and the limitation of the previous reforms. The teachers' training on the other hand did not meet teachers' expectations as the focus of the training was on general

aspects related to teaching rather than values. Furthermore, the family interference in the process of fostering values which may affect the children readiness to acquire other values especially if these values contradict with those maintained in the family. Some teachers reflect on their own values while teaching, where some of them confidently declared that they base their examples on religious values as they believe these were ignored in the policy of embedding these cores and that most of the core values focus more on nationality and identity or openness to the world which do not reflect the students believes. The fact that teachers are not part of the policymaking or as it is described in the literature lack of teachers' agency results in unclear understandings of new introduced policies and all aspects related to them. What has been reported by teachers signifies that the Algerian EFL Middle School teachers resist the SGC reform and for some teachers they do not support the policy of embedding values in the curriculum. Another challenge revealed is that the language teachers are always involved in teaching of values.

As previously mentioned, the data unveiled that the teachers highlighted no affordances encountered while engaging with the core values, instead they developed some coping strategies to help them during the process, besides other supporting factors that successfully help them to perform the values in the classroom. For instance, the social media helps the teachers in their experience of teaching values where they create Facebook groups and other online platforms to share their experience in interacting with values besides discussing any potential challenges and sometimes sharing some solutions to these potential challenges. The teachers' collaboration helps them in sharing knowledge on how to enact values in the classroom, especially between experienced and novice teachers where the novice teachers can benefit from the recommendations of the experienced teachers. In addition, the academic events such as workshops, study days, seminars help teachers to come together, motivate the teachers to share their experiences, discuss the outcomes, and also to develop common ways that might help them on how to enact values in the classroom.

8.3 Implications of the Study

The current study explored the Algerian EFL Middle School teachers' perceptions about the values embedded in the curriculum and their implementation in the classroom. Therefore, the study provides a comprehensive understanding of teachers' different perceptions of values education. In addition to the different methods, they said they implement in enacting values. The current study also highlighted the challenges encountered by the teachers when enacting values. Consequently, the findings of this research resulted in identifying opportunities, and strategies for promoting values education in Algerian Middle Schools and beyond. The study highlights the following implications based on the obtained findings:

The study revealed that Algerian EFL Middle School teachers have varying perceptions of the core values embedded in the curriculum, regarding the aim, rationale, and valuing their implementation in the classroom. This finding highlights the importance of aligning teachers' understanding of core values with clear policy objectives through considering a broader

educational ecosystem beyond policy documents to ensure effective understanding and implementation of the embedded values.

Findings signifies that teachers tend to teach the core values implicitly rather than through explicit instruction, as recommended by stakeholders. This finding underscores the need for professional development opportunities to enhance teachers' pedagogical approaches to ensure effective integration of values across the curriculum.

The study identified number of challenges faced by teachers in enacting the embedded values for instance, the lack of effective training programme, lack of teaching aid and materials, and the lack of guidance in the policy documents on how to enact the embedded values. These challenges emphasize the necessity of providing adequate support and resources to facilitate the enactment of core values in the classroom. In addition to designing effective training programmes that address the values education.

The findings revealed that imposing policies and disregarding teachers active role in taking part in deciding about the curriculum reform, the new introduced policies, and the values education resulted in teachers resisting the reform and curriculum change.

The study offers recommendations for policymakers, to consider teachers participation in curriculum design, addressing the lack of teaching materials and aids, and focusing on meeting students' needs effectively. These recommendations aim to empower teachers in navigating challenges and enhancing their practices in promoting values education.

The findings of the study contribute to the existing literature on values education and teachers' perspectives, particularly in the Algerian context. The implications extend to informing future research endeavours, guiding educational policymakers, and enhancing values education practices globally.

8.4 Limitations of the study

-Generalization is not taken for granted, therefore it may not be relevant in this study as the data derived from small number in both the online survey (64 respondents) and the interviews (16 participants) which can relate more broadly to other EFL Middle School teachers, but not to every teacher in every Middle School in Algeria. Other EFL teachers and other Middle Schools may share some similarities with the findings of this study however they could also be different in positive or negative way. Moreover, larger number of participants might have given different results. Therefore, there is a call through this study for more researches to be conducted in the area of character education and enacting core values in the context of Algerian schools.

-The analysis of the data was completely self-conducted and self-reported and without the verification of another coder, therefore, it might be seen as a possible reason of bias in the analysis process. However, this does not undermine the findings in this current research project. To mitigate bias in this study, I maintained ethical procedures throughout the study. During the data collection and analysis, I maintained objectivity and reflexivity in narrating participants stories, describing and reporting their answers as well as interpreting them.

-Lack of policy documentations that clearly discuss the policy of embedding values and lack of Algerian literature in the area of values education, embedding values, and enacting values hampered the researcher at some points. However, it also highlighted the need for this academic research at this point.

-Data collection conducted online during pandemic. Due to COVID-19 pandemic the travel was banned between the UK and Algeria in addition to all schools' closure in Algeria which required conducting the data collection online, it took me longer time to reach the participants. The data collection process took roughly seven months.

-Participants withdrawing their participation last minute. Five of the participants who previously agreed to take part in the study, they later on and on the day of the interview withdraw their consent to take part without giving further explanation. I looked for another five participants to take part in the study and to replace those who withdrew their participations.

-ICT and internet issues in Algeria, some of my participants were not well-versed in technology and others faced some issues during the interview which most of the time resulted in rescheduling the interview.

8.5 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this research study and on the limitations mentioned above, the following recommendations are offered.

8.5.1 Recommendations for teachers

-In this research, teachers themselves suggested some recommendations that they see as solutions to improve the situation. During the interviews the teachers commented on different topics related to values, curriculum, and their experience. There were many aspects that they wish the policymakers are aware of or consider. They believe that the focus should be on the students when writing curriculum as they believe it is not about writing the best lesson plans or developing a perfect set of in-class projects and assignments. Instead, it's about meeting the needs of the students in a way that ensures the material is understood, maintained, and applied in and out of the classroom.

-Reforms and policies should be well studied and evaluated before implementation; teachers should be part of the process of designing the curriculum, deciding about a policy, and also should be part of any reform programme.

-Policymakers must take into consideration the lack of some applying curriculum materials in schools and isolated areas in Algeria which are far from technology.

-Recent reforms in the education system have mainly focused on language policy, which has put more pressure on English language teachers as they are at the front-line for the implementation of the new reforms.

-The teachers also provided some recommendations that they believe other teachers should consider. They should not rely only on the materials provided by the policymakers or inspectors, there are plenty of supportive programs or software, online programs, or basic planning maps that can be used as a guide and also to vary the lesson planning resources. These resources enable teachers to access curriculum anytime and make modifications for future use. Some of them are free, for those with low budget.

-My recommendations as a researcher to the teachers are, it is necessary for EFL teachers to have enough knowledge about the core values, embedding values in school curriculum, values education before attempting to employ them in the classroom.

-Teachers should not rely only on materials provided by the policymakers, they rather should seek other materials, other methods, search for what best suit their students.

-Teachers should also consider collaboration with other teachers as it helps sharing common concern and challenges in regard to embedding values and also discuss possible solutions.

-Teachers should seek other ways to voice themselves, their needs, and their students' needs to policymakers for instance creating virtual platform where they can give feedback, rate current curriculum, participate in further introduced policies and reforms.

-Teachers should not allow personal values to interfere in their professional life

-Teachers should consider collaboration with families to ensure promoting values to the students and not perceiving family as negative factor influencing values education.

8.5.2 Recommendations for policymakers

-The findings revealed that there is a lack of proper training programmes, thus there is a need for increasing the number of training sessions and increasing the quality of the training for teachers. Training programmes should also be up to date with new introduced policies and reforms.

-The training programmes should focus more on the introduction of values, embedding values in the teachers' daily teaching and more precisely on the different methods that can be followed by the teachers to embed these values effectively and successfully in the classroom.

-The teachers should consider employing several methods to promote values in the students, also they should ensure that the method used fit the nature of value and the aim of the lesson.

-Policymakers and teachers should work collaboratively to ensure best learning and teaching experience for both teachers and the students as this will ameliorate the education outcome. Besides, they should work collaboratively to ensure promoting the relevant values in the students successfully. Also, they should agree on same values that need to be introduced in the curriculum and there should be no dissonance between them on deciding about the values.

-Educators, inspectors, school principals should consider planning more academic events such as conferences, workshops, and study days to help teachers engage more in the teaching process and more precisely engaging with the values embedded in the curriculum.

-Administration and school principals should think of social events to gather, build a contact between parents and teachers to discuss students' level, progress and performance related to acquiring values as it is important for both.

-There is a lack in the teaching materials and aids, therefore policymakers must make sure to equip the schools with the necessary materials. Schools have also to be equipped with updated technologies in order to make the teaching process easy and learning much easier.

-The findings revealed that there is a lack of equal opportunities between people in south and north. Therefore, policymakers and the government must ensure equal opportunities for all populations in Algeria, in the sector of education.

-The findings revealed that teachers are not in any way considered in the curriculum design, curriculum reform yet this should be considered by policymakers to consider teachers views and feedback while designing a curriculum or deciding about new reform or policy.

-The findings also revealed that teachers cannot develop clear understanding of many aspects in the curriculum and policy documents, thus policymakers must consider the clarity of the curriculum materials.

8.5.3 Recommendations for further research

-An important next stage for research in the future is to follow up with the new ideas that emerged from the data analysis which turns in highlighting a huge gap in the literature on values education and engaging with values in Algeria

-An implication of the present investigation indicates that there is a need for researching more on the teachers' experience in engaging with values in the classroom.

-Future researchers can study values embedded in other curriculum or field (module) for instance, French, Arabic language, history...etc.

- Other studies can explore teachers' perspectives on values considering other context for instance, Primary school or Secondary school.

-Another area of research can investigate the evaluation of the policy of embedding values.

-Future researchers can explore students experience on learning values.

-Further research can focus on exploring the perspectives of other parts for instance policymakers, family, inspectors or school principles on the policy of embedding the core values in the school curriculum.

-The results of this study suggested that educators, inspectors, and trainee teachers are not providing any information about values and teaching values when training EFL teachers. Hence, it may also be significant to interview these teacher educators in order to examine the lack of importance given to these values during the training programme.

-Family collaboration in the process of value-education in Algeria, may also be important to conduct research regarding the collaboration between parents and teachers in working together for the purpose of promoting core values at both school and home.

-Additionally, it is crucial to conduct research where parents or family can be interviewed in order to dig deeper into their understanding, points of view and awareness of promoting values, because this research revealed that parents or family may influence the process of promoting values in the school.

- Another part of this research showed how teachers have a lack of self-esteem in engaging with values in the school because of the lack of pedagogical knowledge in how to effectively perform this to meet their students' needs. Therefore, this worth more investigation.

-Further research can also consider analysing the policy document to examine the representation of the policy of introducing values into the school curriculum.

- the literature review showed very little information about administration, the educational system, and curriculum regarding values education and supporting teachers to engage with values in the school. Therefore, it might be noteworthy to study the role of Algerian administration in facilitating the educational environment for engaging and teaching values.

8.6 Personal Development

The Ph.D. journey has provided me with a deep understanding of various aspects in the area of this research. During the first year of the journey, I started to learn more about developing an academic writing and critical thinking, in addition to enhance my search skills and abilities using different databases and electronic libraries. Later, I learnt about the different research methods, paradigms, approaches, theoretical/analytical framework, and the philosophical underpinning of the ontological and epistemological perspectives, these were completely new knowledge to me, however these added a lot to my background information as a researcher. Moreover, I learnt using various software programmes such as NVIVO, SPSS, Mendeley, and Endnote.

Throughout this journey I attended and participated in many academic events, some of them were organized by the University of the West of Scotland, School of Education and Social Sciences for instance, writing retreat, SPSS/NVIVO workshops, research colloquium, research webinars, Teach-meets, and Research festival. Among the conferences I participated in, the 2nd International Conference on Language Education and Research LERC2020, International Conference in Innovation in Language Learning, and 6th and 7th Qatar University Annual Conference on English Language Teaching and many other inter-disciplinary doctoral conferences. Besides, presenting a paper in BERA Conference 2023. These conferences and academic events helped me to explore the different research methods of various research students, The conferences and seminars also helped me to deliver various types of presentations (in person/hybrid), helped me to enhanced public speaking and open discussion among colleagues and experts in the field and also to overcome speaking anxiety. Furthermore, during these events I had the opportunity to reflect on issues regarding teaching, English language teaching, curricula reforms, planning and innovation, values educations, and their implementation.

During my journey I volunteered in some English classes for Ukrainian refugees where I was able to develop valuable experience as a teacher on how to present, deliver, and plan lessons and how to deal with vulnerable students, besides developing awareness of trauma informed pedagogy. I also had the chance to deliver Arabic classes to children's Arab emigrants where I learnt how to deal with students from different age groups and different backgrounds and how to maintain good relationship throughout.

Research is endless process and lifelong learning process; it has been challenging and stressful yet rewarding. During this time, I develop other skills related to time management, meeting

deadlines and chiefly how to be patient. In addition to practice being precise, critical, and explicit in my writing.

Based on this valuable research journey, it is my responsibility now as a researcher to employ all the knowledge, skills, and methodological aspects which I have learnt and developed about the field of education, English language teaching, curriculum, reforms and innovations and more precisely on values education, in Algerian context. I intend to make contribution in the field of values education, by spreading more awareness on this aspect which clearly is not getting much attention neither by policymakers, nor teachers, educators, inspectors, and researchers as well. Implications of the current study will be shared through different academic events like conferences, workshops, and study days, also through academic publications. I am intending to make collaboration to the teaching of values, methods used to engage with values in the school and classrooms, reduce the influence or the effect of the challenges and limitations raised by teachers in order to make the situation of enacting values more applicable and valuable.

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Appendices

School of Education and Social Sciences

Participant Information Sheet

Title of the study: “How Algerian Teachers Engage with the Values Embedded across the Second Generation Curriculum”.

Introduction

I am Meriem Abid, a PhD candidate at the University of the West of Scotland in the School of Education and Social Sciences. I am conducting this research project as a part of my degree.

What is the purpose of this study?

The aim of this research project is to explore teachers’ perspectives and experiences in engaging with values that are the core of the recent reform, so-called Second-Generation curriculum. First by exploring the teachers understanding of the core values, identifying the different methods used to engage with these values in the classroom, and finally identifying any challenges or affordances encountered by the teachers during this experience.

Do you have to take a part?

The participation in this research study is voluntary and those of you who choose to be take part will have the right to withdraw at any time during the process of data collection without penalty of any form.

What will you do in this research project?

When you agree to take part in this study, you are than required to fill in a questionnaire. This questionnaire is about your teaching experience of the English language throughout the new reform (Second Generation curriculum), your understanding of the new reform and the values that underpin the new school curriculum, also your perspectives and attitudes toward them. The questions in this questionnaire require no more than a tick, choosing the most relevant

answer. However, participants in the semi-structured interview that will last between 45 to 1h minutes will have open questions, which required more discussion, explanation and expanded answers.

Why have you been invited to take part?

Your participation is required in this study because you are an EFL (English as a foreign Language) Middle School teacher in Algeria.

What are the potential risks to you in taking part?

There will be no potential risks to you in participating in this study, except devoting some time to complete the questionnaire and the interview. Bear in mind that all provided data are anonymous and you can choose to skip or not to answer questions that bother you in any way.

What will happen to the information in this research project?

All sort of information and data collected from the participants will be completely anonymous and confidential, they will be in a password-secured laptop and securely stored within the locked office at the university or my locked room, only my supervisory team and I have access to. They will be disposed of six months after the end of the project.

What will happen next?

If now you are happy to take part and willing to proceed, first you will have to sign a consent form to confirm your participation. I am very grateful yet thankful for your involvement. Once this study is completed, report on its findings will be available on request for those who wish to read more about it.

This research project was granted ethical approval by the School of Education and Social Sciences Ethics Committee.

Thanks for your patience in reading through these information, if you have any questions/concerns, during or after the data collection process, contact details are available, or if you wish to contact an independent person for further details please contact:

Supervisor:

Professor Donald Gillies
Dean of the School of Education
and Social Sciences
University of the West of Scotland
Ayr Campus

████████████████████

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Researcher Contact Details:

Meriem Abid, PhD candidate
PhD Candidate
School of Education and Social Sciences
University of the West of Scotland

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Personal details withheld.

School of Education and Social Sciences

Informed Consent

Title of the study: “How Algerian Teachers Engage with the Values Embedded across the Second-Generation Curriculum”.

Dear Participants,

I am Meriem Abid, a PhD researcher at the University of the West of Scotland, at the School of Education and Social Sciences.

I am carrying out this study as part of my PhD research. The purpose of this research is to investigate the teachers’ perspectives and experiences in engaging with the embedded core values that underpin the Second Generation curriculum, as well as identifying the potential limitations and challenges that might be encountered by the teachers during this experience.

My main participants in this study will be Algerian EFL teachers at Middle Schools regardless of their gender, teaching experience or where they are located in Algeria. This research project has been approved by the Ethics Committee of the School of Education and Social Sciences at the University of the West of Scotland.

- 1- I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet for the above project and the researcher has answered any queries to my satisfaction.
- 2- I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw from the project at any time, without having to give a reason and without any consequences.
- 3- I understand that I am going to:
 - a- Complete a questionnaire (about 10 mins)
 - b- Participate in an interview (approx. 45-1h).
 - c- Be audio-recorded during the interview.
- 4- I understand that any information recorded in the data collection process will remain confidential and no information that identifies me will be made publicly available.

5- I consent to being a participant in the project.

Name of the participant:

Date:

Signature:

Name of the researcher:

Date:

Signature:

Online Survey for EFL Middle School Teachers

Dear teachers,

This online survey is designed as a part of a Doctoral study entitled "How Algerian Teachers Engage with the Values Embedded across the Second-Generation Curriculum". for the purpose of collecting preliminary data.

I would be very grateful if you could take few minutes from your precious time to answer it. Please tick \surd the relevant answer

Demographic data:

Gender

Female

Male

Teaching Experience

A year or less

1-5 Years

6-10 years

More than 10 years

Current place of teaching

Urban

Rural

Section One: School reform

Please read the following statements and tick the relevant box closet to your opinion.

1-strongly disagree; 2-disagree; 3 – neither agree nor disagree; 4 –agree; 5- strongly agree

The statement	1	2	3	4	5
1-The concept 'Second generation' curriculum is familiar to me.					

2-The implementation of this reform was straightforward.					
3- The new curriculum reform has been stated by a known official body.					
4-This reform is worthwhile; has clear objectives and will have positive impact on the learning of English in Middle schools.					
5- There was an effective training for this reform.					
6- The training tackled all aspects of the reform and efficiently prepared the teacher for real-life classroom.					
7-There are supporting documents that help the teacher enact the new curriculum clearly.					

Is there any comment related to this section that you wish to add?

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Section Two: Teachers’ agency

To what extent you agree or disagree about the following statements, tick the relevant box.

1-strongly disagree; 2-disagree; 3 – neither agree nor disagree; 4 –agree; 5- strongly agree

The statement	1	2	3	4	5
8-I was involved in the decision-making of this reform.					
9-My perspectives were taken into consideration in the design of the previous curriculum reforms.					
10- I can suggest changes to the teaching of the new curriculum beyond the teaching community of the current school.					

Is there any comment related to this section that you wish to add?

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Section Three: The policy documents.

Please read the following statements and tick the relevant box closet to your opinion.

1-strongly disagree; 2-disagree; 3 – neither agree nor disagree; 4 –agree; 5- strongly agree

The statements	1	2	3	4	5
11- The policy documents represent all aspects of the new reform.					
12-The aim and objectives of this reform are explained.					
13-The reasons for the recent curriculum innovation are explicit.					
14- The policy document of the new curriculum defines the procedure of teaching clearly.					
15- The values stated in the policy documents are clear and understandable.					
16- I can differentiate between the values stated in the policy document.					
17- The policy documents provide teachers with the way to enact these values.					
18- The way the process of teaching described in the policy document and how I actually conduct the teaching are compatible.					

Is there any comment related to this section that you wish to add?

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Section Four: Teachers’ perspectives about the factors/ evaluation of the SG reform

19- The school environment such as trust and collaboration between the colleagues, instructional leadership or the administration service, involvement in educational events related to the SG curriculum) help in the implementation and help to make this curriculum successful.

Section Five: Teachers perspectives toward values-based curriculum

1-strongly disagree; 2-disagree; 3 – neither agree nor disagree; 4 –agree; 5- strongly agree

The statements	1	2	3	4	5
19- What’s intended to be achieved by the new curriculum is hard to understand.					
20- The values generate mass confusion over your interpretation or/and your implementation.					

21-The values stated and the rationale behind them are clear.					
22- These values address the students' needs and expectations.					
23- These values reflect teachers' background, needs, and expectations					
24- These values represent the background of the country (Algeria)					
25-This values-based curriculum promote collective values such as; rights and duties, socialising, solidarity...etc.					
26-This values-based curriculum promote individual values such as; honesty, loyalty, honour...etc.					
27- The new curriculum reform helps in anchoring the national identity of the students.					
28-it helps in reinforcing the national consciousness and citizenship of the learners.					
29-It also helps the learner to be open to other cultures and keen to learn about other markers of the identity. (openness to the world)					

Is there any comment related to this topic that you wish to add?

.....

Thank you.

Interview for English Middle School Teachers

This interview is designed as a part of a Doctoral study entitled “An exploration of teachers’ perspectives related to the values that underpin the teaching of English as a Foreign Language in the Algerian EFL middle schools (second generation) curriculum”

Introductory Questions:

Name:

Teaching experience:

Place of practising the teaching:

Questions related to the reform:

1- What Is Second Generation curriculum?

2-Who introduced this new curriculum of the Second Generation?

3-What is the core of this change?

4-Does the new reform take into consideration the limitations of the previous school curricula?

5-How would you evaluate the new reform? According to the content, availability of the materials, and teachers’ readiness.

Questions related to the teachers’ agency and accountability:

6-Where you involved in the process of reforming the school curriculum?

7-Have you ever been involved in the process of designing a curriculum?

8-Does the official body consider the teachers’ perspective and feedback while designing a curriculum?

9-How do you believe that teachers should take part in the decision-making of the design of the school curriculum and that their role should not be limited to delivering the curriculum only?

Questions related to the values that underpin the SG curriculum and the English language teaching:

10- In what way do you see that these values are helping or will help the English language teaching/learning experience?

11-How do these values contribute to the development of the learning process of the English language for the students?

12-How does this reform helps in dealing with the teaching of English as global language?

Questions related to the teachers perspectives about the reform and the values that underpin the Second Generation curriculum:

13-What is your familiarity with the values that are considered the core of the new curriculum?

14-Are they clearly shaping and forming the curriculum?

15- How would you evaluate the values that the new curriculum is based on?

16-During the teachers training for the new reform, was there a focus on values and in what way?

17-How do you enact these values?

18-What is the role of teachers in values enactment?

19-How does this new reform help and promote students' national identity, national consciousness, citizenship, and openness to the world?

20-What are the challenges and affordances of the new curriculum?

21- Is there anything you wish to see in the new reform that is not actually there?

22- Is there any comment related to the topic you wish to add or any points of interest that the questions above did not tackle?

23- What factors you see that affect the implementation of the curriculum?

24- What issues you see that hinder the effective implementation of curriculum?

25- The school conditions (environment) such as trust, leadership and collaboration helps or hinder the effective implementation of the second-generation curriculum?

Thank you

Pilot Study Questionnaire/Interview Checklist

Criteria	Questionnaire	Interview
Timing		
Readability (ambiguity/difficulty).		
Clarity (content/meaning).		
Validity		
Reliability		
Practicability.		
Redundant/irrelevant items.		
Attractiveness: interesting/boring.		
Facts: brining sth new does not exist in real-life.		
Structure: too long/too short.		
Any sensitive/ threatening/ intrusive/offensive Items.		

Validity: the question measures or describes what it is supposed to measure or describe.

Reliability: consistency; the extent to which that same questionnaire would produce the same results if the study were to be conducted again under the same conditions.

Practicability: easy to construct, administer and interpret.